

University of the West of Scotland

School of Business and Enterprise

A CRITICAL INVESTIGATION INTO THE RELATIONSHIP
BETWEEN CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY,
EMPLOYEES' ENGAGEMENT AND EMPLOYEES'
RETENTION IN THE UK BANKING SECTOR

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Abstract

Employees' engagement (EE) is an important issue faced by many businesses around the world. Research reveal that the UK's employee engagement levels have dropped over the years and unengaged employees cost UK companies over £37 billion a year. Since the global financial crisis in 2008, CSR became a prevalent concept that has obligated banks and other businesses to conduct transparent and ethical business practices. Corporate Social Responsibility is considered as an instrument that helps with increasing the engagement levels of employees. The main aim and purpose of this study is to evaluate the relationship between the notion of corporate social responsibility and employee engagement within the UK banking sector. This study further expands the research objectives to understand the impact CSR has on Employees' Planned Behaviour (EPB) and Employees' Retention (ER).

The significance of this research is that, at the completion of the study, the knowledge gap of the relationship between CSR and employee engagement along with the relationship between CSR and employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention will narrow by a substantial amount. This study adopts a quantitative strategy to evaluate the relationship between the variables. The correlation analysis indicates that there is a positive relationship between corporate social responsibility and employee engagement. The principle component analysis has been conducted to identify proxies to represent each key variable (CSR, EE, EPB, ER) in the regression analysis. The ordinal logistic regression analysis has indicated that the CSR tends to have the positive and significant impact on the employee engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention.

This study contributes to the academic literature by identifying that there exists a positive and significant relationship between the CSR practices of the organisation and the engagement of its employees. From the findings, it can also be concluded that by undertaking different CSR promotions to improve the well-being of society, top management of the corporation can upsurge the organisation's identification of their workers, which in turn, can lead the employees to experience the success or failure of their organisation as if it were their own success or failure; something policymakers can also benefit from in order to enhance the employee engagement and retention levels within the organisation.

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List of Abbreviations

CBES	Climate Biennial Exploratory Scenario
CFP	Corporate Financial Performance
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EBF	European Banking Federation
EE	Employee' Engagement
EFA	Exploratory factor analysis
EPB	Employee' Planned Behaviour
ER	Employee' Retention
GRETLM	Gnu Regression, Econometrics and Time-series Library
HR	Human Resource
HRM	Human Resource Management
ITES	Information Technology Enabled Services
JE	Job Engagement
KMO	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin
OCB	Organisational Citizenship Behaviour
OE	Organisational Engagement
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
SET	Social Exchange Theory
SIT	Social Identity Theory
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
TBL	Triple Bottom Line
TRA	Theory of Planned Action
UK	United Kingdom

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Corporate social responsibility became a predominant practice since the global financial crisis in 2008. However, in the 21st century, corporate social responsibility has evolved into a worldwide phenomenon as stakeholders expect contemporary organisations to perform more in the society than merely create revenue and follow regulations. Ethics and philanthropy support social responsibility demands imposed on contemporary firms attempting to thrive in tough, evolving and international economies (Carroll, 2015). The influence social responsibility has on a company's performance is a topic area that has been debated for years in business related studies. Existing researches focus on CSR's impact on consumers, employees' or organisations, such as the relationship between corporate social responsibility and consumer behaviour or job satisfaction and organisations profitability. Nevertheless, existing researches of how corporate social responsibility impact corporate level consequences by influencing work engagement of employees' is relatively inadequate (Kunz, 2020). This current research contributes to the literature by evaluating the effects of corporate social responsibility on the engagement of employees.

The main purpose of this study is to evaluate the relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and employees' engagement. When an Employee is able to express themselves at work, they feel motivated and connected to their jobs (Gifford & Young, 2021). The concept of employees' engagement has been embedded as a crucial HR practice during the past 2 decades, especially since the role of employees in attaining competitive advantage have been predominant in the current competitive market. Employees' engagement has also been a pivotal indicator of organisational health for business managers and investors (Gifford & Young, 2021). According to a CIPD research, employee engagement is an umbrella term used to define a broader concept, which includes motivation, organisational commitment and engagement, intellectual engagement, and work engagement.

Furthermore, the research also evaluates the influence of CSR on employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention. Planned behaviour is a concept which suggests that humans behave and act in a way that aligns with their norms and attitudes (Ajzen, 2005). Researches in the area of planned behaviour have identified that personal values, attitudes and personality traits influence the decision making of an individual. Although, these factors don't

always directly influence the decision making and behaviour of an individual, they subconsciously determine the behavioural conduct of humans. Intentions of an individual influence the behaviour and effort they are willing to put forth in performing a task (Ajzen, 2020). Therefore, in this research, the concept of Planned behaviour has been applied to predict and analyse the behavioural patterns of employees towards and as a result of CSR. Thus, the concept of Employees' planned behaviour has been developed. As a result, it enables the researcher to identify the influence of CSR on employees' engagement and also on employees' retention – which is another critical issue many businesses around the world are facing. In the US in 2006, one quarter of the employees left their jobs. Comparatively, the UK statistics suggests that in average, the turnover rate is at 35% (CIPD, 2023). Employees' retention does not only focus on how business can retain their employees, but also helps businesses identify different concerns and motivation factors of their employees. It is crucial that businesses focus on retaining their talent after investing in employee training and grooming the employees to be acquainted to the corporate culture (Gorde, 2019).

CSR has been considered as an important phenomenon with which organisations engage for improving their corporate reputation and complying with corporate governance mechanisms (Nwaneri, 2015). However, it has been perceived that CSR helps organisation to grow its reputation in the market (Lee, 2020) and also impacts on the engagement of employees and their behaviour in the workplace (Glavas, 2016). Furthermore, there are many studies that have been conducted on employees' engagement (EE) since this has been considered to be an important issue. Retention of employees (ER) is also an area of concern for many organisations since increasing employee turnover leads to lower organisational productivity and performance and for this reason retention is highlighted to be an important issue. Therefore, this study evaluates the impact of CSR on engagement and retention of employees. The study also focuses on the employees' planned behaviour (EPB) as the employees' perception of the company plays a vital role in their behaviour pattern.

This introductory chapter presents the background of the study which will provide a context to the study and the researched area. Different studies will be discussed briefly and they will be evaluated further in the literature review. The aim of the study is to critically investigate the relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility, Employees' Engagement and Employees' retention in the UK Banking Sector. Furthermore, this chapter provides the objectives of the study and research questions that will help to analyse the problems that have

been identified. In addition, this chapter provides a rationale of the study and its significance and has also provides a dissertation structure to show how the study will be carried out.

1.2 Background to the study

The international financial crisis in 2008, caused several well-known institutions to close their operations and face a default situation. Numerous studies were carried out in order to examine the causes of and reasons for the crisis, its outbreak, and to identify solutions to overcome the damage. As a result of such studies, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) was recognised as amongst the most effective strategies to reduce or eradicate the impacts of the crisis. Since then, CSR has become one of the most widely researched areas (Yelkikalan & Kose, 2012). In order to control and mitigate the preceding damages caused to the environment and the global economy by business organisations, the world-wide demand for corporate executives who can develop new associations amid firms and the communities has enhanced (Lins et al., 2019). Firms and financial institutions are considered as integral parts of the wider society and they influence other constituents of society, therefore, it is imperative that they be considered as a part of the society in which they operate (Tasnia et al., 2020).

Institutions are consequently needed to uphold greater levels of agreement from the society on how they operate, which has made CSR an international phenomenon (Jamali and Karam, 2018). Referring to Gharleghi et al., (2018) CSR arises when firms or institutions deliberately decide to advance and increase the social welfare of the society they operate in, through their strategies and policies. By implementing CSR policies and strategies, business and financial institutions help to harmonising their operations in alignment with society's wider benefits. Adapting from Farid et al. (2019), CSR refers to the diverse clear practices carried out by firms for the development of voluntary relationship with the stakeholders and community. Currently, practices of CSR are undertaken by institutions for managing the effect of their actions on their stakeholders including customers, employees, suppliers, top management, investors and shareholders (Su and Swanson, 2019).

According to the CEO of General Electric between 1981-2001, Jack Welch, the success of the firms are indicated by three factors one of which is employees' engagement, which leads to customer satisfaction, and profitability. According to Welch, any financial institution cannot achieve success without a motivated, empowered and engaged workforce. Engagement has

been defined as a combination of several elements, such as dedication, participation, affiliation, motivation, passion, good attitude, and behavioural appearance that contribute to employees' productivity, which is significantly associated with organisational growth (Gupta and Sharma, 2016). A motivated workforce builds organisation citizenship behaviour and aligns employees' loyalty with the firm's, mission and vision (Forrester, 2020).

Furthermore, employees' engagement is explained by Jamali and Karam (2018) as the commitment levels of workers towards a business that is signified by their hard work and their period of employment with the firms. An engaged, and empowered workforce is one of the important sources of building competitive advantage for financial institutions that results in higher performance, productivity with reduced turnover or absenteeism (Gharleghi et al., 2018).

Businesses face different challenges in managing employees' engagement in the constantly changing business environment. According to human resource professionals, if a worker is not motivated, his best efforts cannot be expected towards the firm. If satisfied workers demonstrate robust levels of dedication and professionalism towards their jobs and a fairly strong connection to the company's wellbeing, they meet the standard of an engaged worker, who is very invested in company's operations and develops a strong enthusiasm to meet business objectives (Madan, 2017). Consequently, numerous corporations around the globe invest in establishing policies and processes to nurture engagement of employees and commitment towards the business (Farid et al., 2019). For instance, in 2007, the UK reported the maximum drop in the Employees' engagement (EE) score among 29 other large economies (AON, 2018). From 2016 to 2017, the EE score of the UK dropped three points and characteristically it takes numerous years for a country to recuperate after dip of this size. As per the benefits and trends survey conducted by AON in 2018, it was revealed that around 25% of the UK companies have developed specific objective pertaining to employees' engagement. However, the majority of the employers has agreed the importance of understanding and engaging with the employees (AON, 2018).

On the other hand, in terms of the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement, Penn and Thomas (2017) is of the opinion that firms focus on their CSR practices as they can increase profitability by improving employees' engagement, loyalty and risk management through CSR policies. While considering this fact, the main focus of this study is to examine the association between CSR and Employees' engagement in the UK Banking Sector. This is

because previous studies were mainly conducted on business organisations and present literature did not focus on the banking sector. Further, evaluation is conducted on how banks in the UK can utilise CSR as a tool and technique to bridge the employment engagement gap in the financial institution sector. Two types CSR have been found which are categorised as external and internal CSR. External CSR deals primarily with welfare and betterment of external stakeholders including environment, the wider society, customers, and suppliers, whereas internal CSR deals with focus on the welfare of workers and offering them growth opportunities, participation and monetary benefits (Penn and Thomas (2017)). Both these facets of CSR are considered in carrying out the investigation and its influence on EE. Tsourvakas and Yfantidou (2018) found that employees' engagement practices are enhanced and strengthened due to the engagement of the organisation in corporate social responsibility. The above study has highlighted that organisations that are engaged in contributing towards, and providing benefit to the external society tend to have employees who are more engaged with their job and hence more productive. The CSR practices are also focused towards the employees of the organisation which leads to the increased engagement of the employees to the organisation. Therefore, it is implied that CSR has an important role to play in increasing employees' engagement and hence it leads to the higher productivity of the employees. The literature has provided that the association between CSR and the attitude of the employees are culture driven. In this way, it elaborates the significance of various CSR definitions due to the variations in the cultural, economic, social and political attributes. It is provided that the organisations that are operating in western countries have the higher constructive perception regarding CSR. There are many different scholars that have noticed that the citizenship is strongly related with the social system of the country. Hence, the CSR activities have to be adjusted in this way (Metaxas and Tsavdaridou, 2010). It has also revealed that these activities have led to the higher performance and productivity of the employees which leads to the higher satisfaction of the employees towards their work.

Pertaining to the research of Hur et al. (2018), CSR has a major connection with employees' planned behaviour (EPB) as it was demonstrated in their study that CSR influences on employee behaviour which then enhances their productivity and performance. In addition, Glavas (2016) illustrates that the CSR activities can support employees to become more motivated to work as CSR enhances their work quality and also leads them to become more engaged with their work. Therefore, it is evident that EPB is drastically influenced by an organisation's CSR activities. Moreover, Ahmad et al. (2017) states that preceding researches

that investigated the impact of CSR on behaviours and attitudes of stakeholders towards firms were poorly developed and no authentic evidence was served. Without appropriate understanding of the influence of CSR practices on the behaviour and attitudes of staff, the financial institutions cannot improve employees' engagement. Therefore, further empirical and theoretical attention is required to investigate the relationship between Employees' planned behaviour, Employees' engagement and CSR practices in the financial sector. Furthermore, it is argued by Jamali and Karam, (2018) that employees' engagement analysed in current academic literature is not adequate.

According to the study of Ikram et al. (2021), the element of employees' retention cannot be denied in the current unstable global environment caused by Covid-19. According to the estimates of Gallup (2003), high employees' turnover and absenteeism cost the Britain's economy over £37 billion a year. Employees' retention is considered to be a critical task for the human resource department in any organisation. However, Ikram et al.'s study has demonstrated that employees' retention can be influenced by CSR activities due to two reasons; firstly that CSR activities lead to attracting potential employees that are conscious of the challenges facing the environment and society. Secondly, the internal activities of CSR can increase the meaningfulness for the employees both in work and outside the workplace that can lead to a decline in their intent to leave the organisation.

Many organisations are recognising how employees are becoming more involved in their jobs as a result of CSR. Consequently, academics have recently started to examine the relationship between CSR and engagement, with research revealing a significantly positive connection between the two (Caligiuri et al., 2013). However, despite the extensive research on CSR and its advantages, very little is researched regarding its connection with employees' drive to perform better. Nevertheless, there is very limited knowledge and understanding about how employees are motivated and engaged under the influence of CSR, particularly in the banking sector.

When Ikram et al. (2020) examined the impact of CSR on the performance of organisations, in terms of employee commitment and financial performance, their study was wholly conducted in developed markets, particularly in the western economies, however, the effect on the financial sector and other financial institutions was left out and the UK was not emphasised in the study. The present paper, consequently, outlines an investigation that aims firstly, to examine the adoption of CSR practices among the banking sector in the UK and secondly, to

examine the association between CSR and employees' engagement within the financial sector in the UK.

1.3 Rationale of Study

Employees' engagement has been one of the main issues in today's corporate world and most managers are concerned with increasing the engagement levels of their employees. According to Gallup (2013) the companies that have a higher engagement score have been identified to have greater success and better long-term performance. It has been determined that efforts to increase the engagement of the employees in organisations has been increasing in order to enhance success and performance in the long term. Glavas (2016) points out that the USA loses around \$500 billion each year from reduced productivity which has resulted from the lower engagement level of the employees. Hence, it has been determined that employees' engagement in the organisation also tends to have an influence nationally. Therefore, employees' engagement is considered to be an important issue to be studied from a management perspective. There are many studies that have highlighted the issue of a lack of employees' engagement and how it can be a negative aspect for the organisation. From the perspective of the study by Turner (2019), employees' engagement influences on the overall productivity of the organisation since lower level of engagement of the employees be associated with lower performance as well. In light of the study by Kertiriasih, Sujana and Suardika (2018) it is also highlighted that the employees that show lower engagement tend to affect the organisation's tendency to perform efficiently. Therefore, it is considered to be significant to study the employees' engagement issues in the organisation.

Furthermore, CSR has also been considered to be an important aspect for organisations as it is considered that the implementation of CSR practices shapes the organisation's image. CSR has been indicated to influence on the external society and its people and also benefits the organisations as well. The organisations with a good level of CSR practices tend to have a positive employee behaviour and hence this has been studied to identify the influence on the employees' engagement practices. According to the study of Ali et al. (2020), a study conducted to identify the relationship between CSR practices and employees' engagement, employees' engagement has been identified to be an important factor for the success of the organisation. The objective of the current study is to evaluate the impact of CSR on employees' engagement

and to identify how CSR can be used as the instrument for filling the engagement gap. Hence, conducting research in this area has been justified for filling the employees' engagement gap.

The study further explores the relationship between CSR practices and the employees' planned behaviour. It is considered that the employees' planned behaviour tends to be influencing on organisation performance as well. It is also considered to be an important issue identified in different studies. For example, the studies of Vveinhardt and Sroka (2021) and Hur et al. (2018) have highlighted that CSR practices have a positive association with employee behaviour and that the employee who engages in CSR can contribute to the productivity and performance of an organisation. Therefore, it is important to study the impact of CSR on employees' planned behaviour. Moreover, Glavas (2016) has also reported that employee behaviour is connected with the quality of work where CSR activities can enhance the motivation of the employees to be more engaged with their work and CSR also influences on employee behaviour.

Furthermore, the current study is also aimed at identifying the impact of CSR on employees' retention. It has been identified from the study of Kurdi, and Alshurideh (2020) that employee turnover is an important issue that increases organisations' costs. It has been identified from the analysis of the different studies that employee turnover tends to increase organisation recruitment costs as employing new employees and the exit of the old employee both incur costs for the organisations. The study of Meier and Hicklin (2008) has also highlighted that employee turnover is one of the crucial aspects of the organisation that tends to reduce the organisation's productivity. The study of Kim, Milliman and Lucas (2020) highlighted that CSR tends to increase employees' retention. Therefore, the objective of identifying the relationship between the CSR and employees' retention has been conducted to determine the impact in an effective manner.

A research study by Dhingra et al., (2016) has stated the issues that are faced by the banking sectors within the UK. It mentioned that UK based banking sectors have faced issues in balancing their economic losses after Brexit. With the passage of time, organisations have adopted technological approaches and good management skills that have helped both employees and organisations. UK banking sectors have adopted intervention schemes and debt moratoria for stabilising their financial affairs and values (Grant Thornton, 2021). According to the research study by Einola and Alvesson, (2021) good leadership is very important for maintaining a healthy environment in organisations. Employees' performances are the reflection of their comfort levels and satisfaction (Chadburn et al., 2017). It has been

discussed that the leaders give guidance and education to their employees so that their firm can compete strongly with similar organisations. Leaders and management departments have to analyse and assess the issues that are faced by their employees so that they can be reduced quickly (Ginter et al., 2018). It raises the good relationship among each other and furthermore helps in dealing with the consequences easily. Corporate social responsibilities are directly linked with the employees' behaviour. It has been concluded in a research study that societal attributes can impact the organisational image (Almeida and Coelho, 2019). Branding sustainability in the marketplace also relies on the customers' satisfaction that could be attained by the efforts of the employees. Greater productivity and the collective efforts of the employees work in favour of attaining the loyalty of the customers.

The research study by Alzaydi et al. (2018), mentioned several aspects that are linked with the customers, including the attitude of the organisational staff, services and the quality of products offered. Furthermore, consumers are now following the concept of word of mouth in order to purchase services from the leading brands (Lai, 2020). Promotion and advertising practices have shifted from manual procedures to digital technologies during the past decade. Consumers are more active on the digital and electronic media, and they want information about the brands via electronic means such as reviews, emails, and blogs etc. These factors have changed the strategic plans of organisations and they are now focusing on IT-based interventions. Similarly, a research study has stated the influence of CSR practices on the engagement of clients in the banking sector (Dell'Atti et al., 2017). They discussed that corporate social responsibilities help in achieving positive outcomes for the customers as it increases loyalty rates and the purchasing intentions among the customers. CSR also influences employees' engagement that leads towards organisational sustainability. Societal attributes that are linked with the organisations help in boosting the branding image (Qasim et al., 2017). It is the social responsibility of a company to empower their employees and adjust corporate resources for good productivity.

1.4 Motivation of the Study

Corporate social responsibility has been identified to be the organisation practices which benefit the communities, external societies, environment, and individuals. CSR practices have been identified to be important as they are implied in the corporate governance principles and the UK Companies Act (2016) have also made it mandatory for organisations to engage in CSR practices (Tran, 2014). Many studies have been conducted on identifying the relationship

between CSR practices of an organisation and its employees' engagement and it has been identified that the employees of an organisation tend to be positively influenced by CSR practices. Many sectors, including the financial sector, have been engaging in CSR practices. The study of Khan, Aslam and Lodhi (2011) highlighted that the banking sector tends to face the issue of increasing employee turnover and hence due to this reason the studies are being conducted to highlight CSR practices' impact on the turnover intentions of employees. Therefore, it is one of the motivations to conduct this current study on identifying the impact of CSR on the employees. Furthermore, the motivation for the topic of CSR and employees' engagement also comes from the interest of exploring corporate social responsibilities and the fundamentals of CSR. The researcher has developed different studies on CSR in regard to the consumers' perspective and the researcher now further extends the knowledge of the domain by interpreting the CSR from the employees' perspective. The financial sector has been selected as the industry of the research owing to the researcher's working experience in this sector. The researcher has been involved in the banking sector for a long time and hence due to this reason is motivated to identify the impact of CSR practices on the employees of the banking sector.

A number of researches have denoted that the employee satisfaction is lower in the banking sector than other sectors (Bhardwaj, Mishra and Jain 2021). Hence due to this reason, the employees in the banking sector are being studied in this research to identify the ways in which the employees' CSR practices tend to be influential on their behaviour and attitude to their job. The main motivation of the researcher is to identify in what way CSR can help grow employees' performance which can lead to the increasing performance of the organisation. Furthermore, the researcher is also motivated to study the issue of employees' retention in the banking sector. As identified in the study of Kurdi and Alshurideh (2020), employee turnover tends to incur significant cost for the organisation, and it also decreases organisation's performance. Therefore, due to this reason the researcher aims to identify how CSR practices can improve the performance of individuals in the organisation so that it can perform better over time. The researcher has also been motivated to identify the different ways in which CSR can help organisations to grow in the long term and to provide recommendations to the banking sectors to be involved in the practices of CSR. It has been identified from the different studies that there are different dimensions and fundamentals of CSR and different organisations have been identified that focus on CSR practices in number of ways (Etter et al. 2019). Therefore, the researcher also aims to provide the recommendation to the banks on how they can engage in the CSR practices efficiently in order to influence on the individual behaviour. The motivation

of the researcher has been explored in different ways in this study so that the anticipated findings to the research can be identified significantly. Therefore, the research in this domain has been conducted which is significant and contributes to the present research in a number of ways.

It has been observed that many of the financial institutions have recognised the use of CSR and these observations have led to several issues being identified. CSR causes the rate of scandals in the companies to decrease as it promotes sustainability and ensures that legal requirements are met in an effective and efficient manner. With more consumers interested in banking services, the role of banks has increased in recent years which means it is essential for them to ensure customer satisfaction and has caused the services to increase and improve. Moreover, CSR has caused the transparency of banks to increase, and it has led stakeholders' interest to increase (Paulik et al., 2015). Therefore, this study has been developed to determine the factors that cause CSR activities to impact on employees' engagement and how services are being improved to increase the rate of EE. Furthermore, with the correct implementation of corporate social responsibility and its designed policies, there exists a possibility that businesses can enhance the potential of gaining personnel that are considered to possess the prerequisite skills required by the banking sector. The main motivation of the study is to determine how CSR has an effect on employees' engagement.

1.5 Research Gap

There has been a number of studies conducted on CSR and how it influences on the engagement and behaviour of employees. The studies of Ali et al (2020) and Glavas (2016) have recorded the relationship between CSR practices and employees' engagement and explained that CSR tends to impact significantly on the engagement of employees. However, the current research is aimed at extending the range of research by concentrating on an industry that has not been investigated in depth by the previous studies. The banking sector in the UK has not previously been investigated and hence due to this reason the current research aims to identify the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement in the UK banking sector; hence this is the first research gap identified. The researcher aims to contribute to the extent of the researches on CSR and employees' engagement and also to fill the gap in the literature by incorporating an untouched sector. The studies on CSR and employees' planned behaviour have also been

identified to be limited and hence, due to this reason, the researcher aims to fill the gap in the present literature by highlighting the relationship between CSR practices and employees' planned behaviour. For this current study, research on CSR and employees' planned behaviour has been conducted with the purpose of filling the gap in the present literature due to the reason that employees' planned behaviour is identified to be an important dimension of the organisation which tends to increase its performance.

The third identified gap in the literature is the relationship between CSR and employees' retention, which this study aims to fill. Employees' retention has been identified to be a significant issue in the organisation and hence due to this reason the researcher has been exploring this dimension. The researcher has also incorporated a unique combination in the framework by incorporating three different employee behaviour dimensions that impact on the organisation's performance. This provides a significant contribution to the previous studies and hence it is important to conduct this research so that the gaps in the literature as identified above can be filled. Therefore, the research is contributing to the present studies on this aspect by identifying these gaps.

1.6 Research Problem

The research problem is based on the fact that, although there have been many studies regarding the relationship between corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement, however as pointed out by Tahir et al. (2021), there is a lack of clarity in terms of the CSR factors. The importance of conducting the research can be reflected from the study conducted by Bhardwaj, Mishra and Jain (2021) where the study has demonstrated that the employee satisfaction level is lower in the banking sector. Furthermore, employee's engagement has been reported low in organisations in many countries and UK has specifically recorded a big drop in the engagement levels of employees. According to the AON (2018) reports the UK's EE score in 2017 is below the universal average of 65%. The following figure, according to Gallup (2003) report, illustrates the breakdown of employees' engagement levels within the British labour force.

Figure 1: Engagement levels within the British workforce (Gallup, 2003)

According to the above illustration, it is clear that the majority of the Britain's workforce are either unengaged or actively disengaged. The actively disengaged proportion of the workforce on its own costs the British economy over £37 billion a year (Gallup, 2003). Hence, it is critical to evaluate the strategies that can support the banking sector in improving the employee satisfaction and engagement that can overall contribute to the productivity of the bank. Moreover, the research of Gangi et al. (2018) has exemplified that the bursting of the banking bubble in the year 2008 along with growth of the non-performing loans (NPL) has led to the reduction of trust among the customers. This indicates the importance for involving in CSR for the banking sector where it can support in developing a relationship with the customers while also contributing to the social well-being. In addition, it can be further stated through the study conducted by Galant and Cadez (2017), there has been sparse contribution in the preceding decade that serves the objective of investigating the capability of corporate social responsibility of developing a pertinent amount of competitive advantage for an organisation. The authors further highlight the fact that the research within the banking sector considering the role of corporate social responsibility has been found to be even sparser and fails to bridge the academic gap effectively.

In accordance with the views of John et al. (2019), there have been few studies that have served the objective of developing a fundamental understanding regarding the effectiveness of corporate social responsibility and its subsequent impact on employees to prolong their association with their respective organisation. Based on these views, it is further elaborated by Wang and Sarkis (2017), that another problem is the lack of research on the impact on the productivity of the personnel. Since there has been a lack of studies regarding the interrelationship between employees' productivity and the success of an organisation, this current study suffers from a distinct disadvantage in terms of the findings that it will obtain during its research in terms of validation. Another problem that is associated with the study is that there are limited variables that have been identified in different studies, therefore, it has caused the research of the study to be limited and has further affected the scope of the study in a negative manner. Many CSR projects have been undertaken by the banks in the UK but they are limited in numbers. As discussed previously, there has been limited research conducted to identify the importance of CSR in bridging the employees' engagement gap, although employees' engagement has been identified as a critical issue faced by companies. This leads to the development of the first Research question - *How does corporate social responsibility influence employees' engagement in the UK banking sector?* Additionally, derived from the first research question, this research will address the first research objective *To evaluate the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement in the UK Banking sector.*

While discussing the first research objective and research question, it is important to identify the mediator that influences CSR to play a role in the engagement of employees. According to the research conducted by Slack, Corlett and Morris (2015), CSR activities helps employees experience an increased feeling of participation, optimistic vision, and self-esteem which influences positive behavioural changes within the employees. Gao and He (2017) stated that planned behaviour is an important motivational model for describing specific engagement of employees within voluntary behavioural conducts since such conducts are neither mandatory, nor recognised by any rewards system within the organisation. Therefore, the research aims to address the second research question - *What role does employees' planned behaviour play in employees' participation in a company's CSR activities?*. Furthermore, the need to understand the interrelationship between the CSR and employees' planned behaviour led to the development of the second research objective *To examine the impact of employees' planned behaviour on CSR.* Finally, the research further extends its scope to answer the third research question, *How does CSR influence employees' retention in an organisation?*. The PWC

Saratoga benchmarking study reveals that compared to 2020 and 2021, the UK employee turnover rates in 2022 have gone up, making it challenging for companies to retain their talents (PWC, 2023). This condition is despite the economic recession and high inflation rates. According to De Silva and Lokuwaduge (2020), proper application of CSR strategies ensures a business that its employees are retained for a long period of time which helps avoid repeated hiring and training costs which would otherwise damage the business' financial performance. Hence, the research will *investigate how CSR influences employees' retention in an organisation* as its' final research objective. Therefore, this study has been developed to discuss the impact of corporate social responsibility of employees' engagement, Employee' planned behaviour and employees' retention.

1.7 Research Aim

As per the background that has been provided in this chapter, it can be stated that the main aim and purpose of this study is to evaluate the relationship that exists between the notion of corporate social responsibility, employees' engagement and employees' retention within the UK banking sector. Moreover, the research's subliminal aim is to realise the objective of developing a better understanding regarding the effectiveness of corporate social responsibility on the employees and the level of engagement they share with their respective organisation, which in this case is the banking sector in the UK.

1.8 Research Questions

As per the research objectives and the ability to achieve the aim of the study, three questions have been developed to facilitate the study to be carried out in an effective manner. These questions led to identification of different aspects on the effects of CSR activities in the context of employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention. The research questions of the study are as follows:

1. How does corporate social responsibility influence employees' engagement in the UK banking sector?
2. What role does employees' planned behaviour play in employees' participation in a company's CSR activities?
3. How does CSR influence employees' retention in an organisation?

1.9 Research Objectives

Based on the study's aim and purpose, research objectives have been formulated and are as follows:

- To evaluate the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement in the UK Banking sector
- To examine the impact of employees' planned behaviour on CSR
- To investigate how CSR influences employees' retention in an organisation

1.10 Significance of the Research

It can be stated that there is a lack of previous literature regarding the relationship between corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement in the banking sector in the UK but, at the completion of this study, the knowledge gap will have narrowed substantially. This is substantiated by the views of Činčalová and Hedija (2020) who confirm there is a significant requirement for the academic gap to be filled within this context based on the fact that there has been lack of investigation regarding the role of corporate social responsibility within the banking sector and the ways it can contribute to an organisation's success.

Along similar lines, the author further states the reason this study is considered to be of significance and will be subject to major academic interest is based on the economic recession that occurred in 2008, causing a substantial loss of reputational capital for the banking sector. Moreover, there have been a considerable number of studies that have focused on the notion of corporate social responsibility, the perceived benefits accorded through its accurate implementation and the amount of reputational capital it provides to the respective institution. In accordance with the views of Mahrani and Soewarno (2018), there are studies in regards to CSR, however limited studies have been conducted in the context of employees' engagement. Therefore, this study has been conducted to fill the gap in previous research.

In light of the points presented above, it is deemed a prerequisite to reiterate the views of He and Harris (2020), who stated another reason that contributes to the significance of this study, namely its capability to focus on the impact of corporate social responsibility on the notion of employees' engagement. The author further infers that with the implementation of this study, there will be a clearer understanding regarding corporate social responsibility and its impact on organisational success, as this study intends to allocate its focus on the impact on employees'

engagement and the possibility to retain employees' association with the respective organisation. Moreover, it is stated that since this research will also consist of theoretical framework. The study will serve the objective of developing more clarity regarding the role of corporate social responsibility since the theoretical framework will incorporate certain theories that will be directed towards addressing this concern.

Furthermore, as dictated by Agyemang and Ansong (2017), it can be stated that with deeper understanding regarding corporate social responsibility, there is a greater possibility of the banking sector designing policies that can be directed towards motivating employees and to further their engagement with the respective organisation.

In addition, the significance can be further elaborated through the views provided by Orazalin (2019), who claimed that the notion of corporate social responsibility holds the potential of providing potent amount of solutions to the banking sector that can be directed towards fostering a better policy that is designed towards employees' engagement. Furthermore, with the implementation of this study, it can be inferred that with the correct implementation of corporate social responsibility and its designed policies, there exists a possibility that the business can enhance the potential of gaining personnel who possess the prerequisite skills required by the banking sector.

The study also exudes significance since it is concerned with the converse impact that is levied by the organisation through their corporate social responsibility's principles on their respective employees. For this purpose, the study focuses on assessing the relationship that exists between CSR's respective variables that will be considered to be integral in terms of the organisation and hold the potential of developing a wider understanding regarding the applicability of corporate social responsibility in terms of facilitating employees' engagement as well as creating a conducive environment for the workforce.

According to the research study proposed by Tilt (2016), corporate social responsibilities practices have helped in motivating employees to perform well. It was mentioned that employees face many issues during their jobs due to a lack of confidence and expertise. Tilt highlighted that the implementation of CSR practices in developing countries could bring development and growth (Shah et al., 2016). On the other hand, developed countries like Australia, the UK and the US are trying to build their organisational environment on the basis of CSR practices. Another research study, by Mayer et al., (2021) has highlighted the idea that the banking sectors are linked with numerous other departments and have to deal with the

internal and external organisational consequences daily. Moreover, managers and the HR department pay major attention towards the implementation of effective strategies so that the organisational environment may be maintained peacefully (Olson et al., 2018). Globally, the business strategies have been changed now as organisations are paying more attention to the market-based orientation. A research study by Tian and Robertson (2019) outlined the positive impact of CSR strategies on the employees' behaviour. It has been discussed further that the workplace environment and employees' behaviour are interlinked with each other. Moreover, employees' behaviour and attitudes are reflections of the circumstances they face during their working life.

In addition, the research study conducted by Buallay (2019) has discussed the situation of the banking sectors in the UK. Researchers have highlighted a focal point that the banking sectors are aiming to spread their business and looking forward to globalisation. These aims have changed their working patterns and framework. Managers and their departments have started collaborating with foreign countries and have introduced many policies and services for foreign customers (Healey, 2016). The sustainability of the organisations and the consistency in their performances help in reaching the leading positions in the global marketplace. It has been mentioned that there are two major financial markets in the UK, banking industries and manufacturing sectors. Banking sectors contribute hugely in stabilising the national economy. It has been stated in a research study by Siddiqui (2020) that the COVID-19 pandemic has adversely impacted the global economy. Many organisations worldwide have faced huge economic losses and downfalls in the marketplace. It was mentioned by Siddiqui (2020) that the strategies that were opted by the UK based organisations have helped in retaining their positions. Moreover, Gumbrell-McCormick and Hyman (2017) explained that the managers and the management department have made changes in their workflow and working strategies in order to reduce the economic consequences. Frequent changes in working patterns have the potential in disturbing growth (Rayna et al., 2016). The banking sectors in the UK have strengthened themselves by giving priority to the CSR policies and strategies that have resulted in rapid growth since the implementation of these strategies.

1.11 Dissertation structure

In terms of the dissertation structure, it is considered to be a methodological mapping of the chapters that will be used in this research and each chapter holds a specific feature that will be elucidated subsequently:

Chapter One: Introduction: The foremost chapter of any research, this chapter serves the objective of providing the prerequisite information with the objective of setting the tone of the study. The chapter will consist of the research aim, objectives, and questions which will be addressed in this study.

Chapter Two: Literature Review: This focuses on the academic articles that have accorded insights similar to this research's topic. The main intent of this chapter is to gauge pertinent themes and patterns that can serve the objectives of the research study. In this chapter, the study will also consist of a theoretical framework that will hold relevant theories and concepts that have the potential of addressing the research questions of this study.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology: This is the area of the study where the research design will be selected i.e. either qualitative or quantitative, which will allow the user of the research to gain clarity in terms of carrying out data collection for this research. Based on the chosen research design, the user of this research will determine the following aspects i.e. research philosophy, research approach, data collection methods, and data analysis techniques. In terms of data collection methods, the chapter will provide clarity regarding the sources used for data collection i.e. either primary or secondary. Based on the data collection, data analysis techniques will be determined and will be used in the subsequent chapter.

Chapter Four: Analysis and Discussion: After determining the data analysis technique in the preceding chapter, the main focus and purpose of this chapter is to subject the data to the chosen data analysis techniques. After the results are obtained from the data analysis, the findings will be subjected to analysis and by extension will also be interpreted and discussed in the same chapter. The main objective that is realised in this chapter is to evaluate the findings in terms of addressing the research hypothesis and objectives of the study.

Chapter Five: Conclusion and Recommendations: This final chapter of the research is concerned with according a comprehensive summary of the study in its entirety based on the choice of research design, and to provide summary of findings. Based on the findings of this

research, this chapter will also provide a credible set of recommendations as well as highlight the future implications of this study.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is defined as the process or model of promoting the element of social accountability in a business organisation. The consideration towards the maintenance of CSR in the company leads to the development of effective and interactive relationships with the stakeholders and service users as well as other relative businesses operating within the industry (Baldini, Bronzetti and Sicoli, 2018). Similarly, the study of Marek (2018) stated that CSR is considered as one of the leading processes, which is required in the banking industry and other organisations to run and maintain their functions of business operations and to promote the standards of the business in every industry or targeted market. CSR is a process by which an organisation expects to create a relationship with their stakeholders for the betterment of the business processes and strategies. The most important factor of CSR which makes it so efficient is the ethical structure of CSR, which in turn plays an important role within organisations and many businesses sectors. According to the World Bank Annual report (2015), the appropriate implication of the CSR helps in enabling the banking sector to promote positive terms of engagement with the employees as well as the service users, which proportionally helps the banks to utilise their strength in providing subsequent benefits to the service users as well as the staff members and the stakeholders (Baldini, Bronzetti and Sicoli, 2018).

The current study shows that CSR activities are not only important for investors and stakeholders, but also important for the regulations' goodwill and customer risk assessment within the financial system. In the crucial process of providing benefits to the public and different businesses, the banking sector encounters several challenges which restricts the pace of its growth. The critical evaluation of the prevailing research studies have ensured that the use and implication of CSR standards helps the banks to promote a safe business environment and prosper in a manner of achieving the ethical goals of business (Tran, 2014). To understand the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and employees' engagement in the UK banking sector, the present study will illustrate the types of CSR, its importance along with the dimensions of CSR, the impact of employees' planned behaviour on CSR, the importance of CSR on employees' retention and finally, the theoretical and conceptual frameworks for understanding the purpose of CSR in the banking sector.

2.2 Concept of Corporate Social Responsibility and Employees' Engagement

2.2.1 Concept of CSR

Corporate social responsibility is defined as the role of the company in terms of its community-based setting. CSR is adopted by corporations to cater to different problems faced by society and to apply better solutions to them. It is the responsibility of organisations towards a broader set of stakeholders and the society beyond its primary shareholders (Sharma, 2019). According to Linag and Renneboog (2017), it is the corporate social responsibility that obliges companies to cater further activities in their corporation rather than simply profit maximisation. These activities can include employee benefits, investing in environment-friendly projects and avoiding relations with businesses that use child labour. According to Liczmańska-Kopcewicz, Mizera and Pypłacz (2019), in CSR, an action programme is implemented to maximise profits for the company while also contributing towards the improvement of the society's wellbeing. The definitions and perceptions of CSR has changed through the years, countries and situations. The following table demonstrates a few definitions of CSR that has evolved over the years.

Author	Year	Definition
Bowen	1953	The duties of an organisation to follow policies, make decisions and follow actions which are essential for the values and goals of the society
Friedman	1971	The key obligation of a company to the community is to maximise profit towards the shareholders and investors, as long as it is done in an ethical manner and the laws are obeyed.
Davis	1973	A company's attention and response to issues that are not limited to legal and economic requirements but also to achieve social benefits along with financial gains which the business pursues.
Carroll	1979	CSR incorporates philanthropic, legal, ethical and economic anticipations a society has of a business
Chandler	2001	Transparent business operations which are legally compliant, has ethical values, and respects the environment, individuals and society are referred to as CSR

Frederick	2008	CSR is the procedure of assimilating the social and environmental factors, as well as the concerns of a company's operations, while guaranteeing that the stakeholders of the organisation play a key role in philanthropic actions towards the society in which it functions
ISO	2010	Obligation of an organisation to consider the impacts of its operations and decisions on the community and the environment, through transparent and ethical conduct that leads to sustainable improvements, considers stakeholders expectations, compliant with the law and international standards, and has CSR incorporated in its operations and associations within the organisation.

Table 1: Definitions of CSR (Author's own compilation)

The concept of CSR is different based on different situations. The major function of defining CSR by organisations comes from the institutional environment of the firm. Each organisation recognises corporate social responsibility in different ways and applies them differently in their organisation (Alas et al., 2018). According to Ali, Frynas and Mahmood (2017), CSR is practiced differently between developing and developed countries. In developing countries, organisations are forced by international buyers, international media, regulatory bodies, and foreign investors to implement CSR activities and there is little pressure from the public. Meanwhile, in developed countries, corporations are influenced by the public to incorporate CSR activities. Other forces such as shareholders, media, creditors, and environmentalists also demand that organisations in developed countries implement CSR in their organisations. Therefore, it is evident that the concept of CSR could be different geographically which is primarily due to the different perceptions around the world about CSR. Nevertheless, it is apparent that CSR is of great significance for any organisation.

Stage	Decade	Guiding CSR Principle	Main CSR action	CSR Drivers	CSR Policy Instruments
CSR1: Corporate Social Stewardship	1950's - 1960's	Corporate managers are public trustees and social stewards	Corporate philanthropy	Executive conscience and company reputation	Philanthropy and public relations
CSR2: Corporate Social Responsiveness	1960's - 1970's	Corporations should respond to legitimate social demands	Interact with stakeholders and comply with public policies	Stakeholder pressure and government regulations	Stakeholder negotiations and regulatory compliance
CSR3: Corporate/ Business Ethics	1970's - 1980's	Create and maintain an ethical corporate culture	Treat all stakeholders with respect and dignity	Human rights and religion-ethnic values	Mission statements, ethics codes, social contracts
CSR4: Corporate Global Citizenship	1980's - 2000's	Accept responsibility for corporate global impacts	Adopt and implement global sustainability programs	Globalization disruptions of economy and environment	International code compliance, sustainability policy

Table 2: Stages of CSR (Adopted from Fredrick, 2008)

According to Fredrick (2008), as demonstrated in table 2, CSR has evolved through 4 stages and the principles and drivers of CSR has transformed alongside. The author also confirms that not every business evolves through all 4 stages. While some companies are positioned in one stage at one point in time, other companies evolve through all stages at the same time (Frederick, 2008). There are five key components in CSR, namely business-based social purpose, clear theory of change, quality and depth of information, concentrated effort, and collaborating with experts (Chen, 2011). CSR can potentially improve the perception of customers related to the brand or a product of a company. Different activities conducted on CSR assist consumers in viewing the organisations as a positive force within the society. In addition to this, CSR works as an effective platform to market and earn the attention of an audience within that market (Salazar, Husted, and Biehl, 2012). The clear theory of change in CSR highlights the mainstream theories identified as corporate social performance (CSP) and shareholder value theory.

Corporate social performance (CSP) refers to the values, principles, and consequences of the relationship of businesses with individuals, groups, associations, and societies as a result of the

thoughtful actions undertaken by businesses towards the stakeholders (Baron, Harjoto and Jo, 2011). The quality and depth of information in corporate social responsibility refers to shared values and beliefs between the management and employees in the organisation (Tai and Chuang, 2014). The collaboration and concentrated effort between the experts in CSR suggest that individuals involved in the activities can pool financial and human resources between multiple organisations. Furthermore, the CSR collaboration addresses the prevailing opportunities and threats within an industry. Not only does it help increase sales and loyalty of consumers and motivates the employees, but it also assists companies in attracting new talent within the industry.

2.2.2 Concept of Employees' Engagement

Employees' engagement can be regarded as the behaviour of an employee to perform their best in their everyday tasks. An increase in employees' engagement also increases productivity, avoids conflict, and maintains a professional decorum. Employees' engagement can be practiced by effective cooperation between the company administration and employees to increase production and provide high quality service to customers (Patro, 2013). Human relations and behavioural experts suggest that the productivity of a firm depends on the sound engagement of its employees. An engaged employee can perform well and is fully motivated to work for the betterment of the company. The company is dependent on the role of these employees; thus, they are in direct relation with the company's progress (Lapoint & LiprieSpence, 2017). Every organisation requires to incorporate the concept of employees' engagement for its successful operation and to provide a better work environment for its employees. Efficient employee management can help in building enthusiasm, satisfaction and commitment in employees and helps increase the overall employees' engagement for better outcomes for organisations. (De Waal & Van Der Heijden, 2015). Following table presents different perceptions and definitions of employees' engagement.

Source	Definitions
The Caterpillar Company Retrieved from (Vance, 2006)	Employees' commitment, work effort and aspiration to stay in a company

The Corporate Leadership Council Retrieved from (Vance, 2006)	Employees dedication towards something or someone in their workplace, the extent of their hard work and retention as a result of that dedication
CIPD (2007) Retrieved from (Storey, et al., 2009)	Passion towards the job and the enthusiasm to go the additional mile
Seijts & Crim (2006)	An employee who is wholly involved and is passionate about their job.
Shaw (2005)	Converting employee potential into employee performance and organisation's success
International Survey Research (Storey, et al., 2009)	The process of a company to enhance commitment and retention of its employees to accomplish organizational goals

Table 3: Definitions of EE (Author's own compilation)

Employees' engagement is defined by Jamali and Karam (2018) as the extent of commitment that employees have towards a company, which is evidenced by their hard work and length of service. Employees' engagement and empowerment is one of the most significant sources of competitive advantage for businesses, as it leads to improved performance, productivity, and lower levels of attrition and absenteeism. Employees' engagement is also achieved by effectively applying performance management techniques. Performance management is the process of creating motivation and commitment in employees to achieve the objectives of a business (Gruman & Saks, 2011). Companies pay attention to their CSR policies because they may boost profits by enhancing employees' engagement, loyalty, and risk management. Employees' engagement directly affects the productivity of a firm. Productivity is considered an invaluable asset both in the manufacturing and the service sectors, since they follow productive practices to ensure the objectives of the company are met in a timely manner. Productivity is also considered to be an attribute that leads to favourable economic growth, better social progress, and enhanced profitability (Hanaysha, 2016).

Out of the several assets a company owns, one asset that cannot be replicated or stolen when managed well are the employees. Hence, several studies such as the research conducted by DDI identifies employees as the most valuable asset and the main form of competitive advantage for an organisation without which it is impossible for a business to achieve its goals and objectives (Wellins, et al., 2015). Paying attention to Employees' engagement primarily drives performance and contributes to the satisfaction of employees. Employees' engagement and employee satisfaction leads to increased revenue for the company. The activities of CSR and employees' engagement are closely linked together, the more the organisation engages in the practices of corporate social responsibility, the more engaged the employees will be (Mirvis, 2012). For instance, the sustainability programme of CSR assures a high level of employee morale and loyalty. Therefore, organisations make efforts to involve the employees in CSR programmes, operations and business practices. The element of social accountability developed through the implication of the CSR helps business organisations, belonging to any sector, to evaluate the social and environmental aspects of their organisation. This process potentially serves in addressing the challenges and risks associated to the organisation. Moreover, the evidence obtained from literature has also highlighted that the sense of accountability signifies the ability of the organisation to promote the employees' satisfaction and work engagement, with the aim of increasing the effective participation of employees in the assigned tasks (Roza, 2016).

When organisations include CSR in business strategies, it helps in building brand reputation along with making improvements in the local and international communities (Kucukusta, Mak, and Chan, 2013). Companies which consider themselves as an enterprise that is socially responsible in creating a positive impact, empower employees to leverage the corporate resources at their disposal to do well. Furthermore, the programmes of corporate social responsibility also boost the morale of employees which leads to greater productivity within the workforce (Sun, and Yu, 2015). The prevailing concept related to employees' engagement deduces that when organisations implement best practices of corporate social responsibility, the workers or employees are more likely to engage in cooperative behaviours or attitudes towards their co-workers within the organisation, for instance, teamwork. Moreover, corporate social responsibility also promotes high quality and robust relationships among the employees in an organisation (Jizi et al., 2014).

2.3 Contemporary Researches on CSR and Employee Behaviour

Current researches confirm that CSR functions enhances an organisation's activities in a way that any other organisational elements cannot do. Moreover, it also gives competitive advantage to businesses over others. This indicates that the organisations are not just a profit oriented entity yet it also considers the concerns of every stakeholder (Shen and Benson 2016). Financial compensations alone cannot ensure that employees are engaged with an organisation on an emotional level. Therefore, organisations undertake different methods in order to achieve a sense of belonging within its workforce.

Different authors have explained the link between the four CSR dimensions and employees' planned behaviour. According to Kitzmueller and Shimshack (2012), economic CSR helps keep employees engaged within their field of work as they perceive that the company is performing well in the market to provide them with a balanced and stable work quality. Legal expectations of CSR activities help minimise the adverse effects on employees concerning insecurity, anxiety and stress that may ultimately lead to the disengagement of the employees from the organisation. Therefore, employees' engagement procedures are improved and reinforced as a result of the company's involvement in corporate social responsibility. A study found that firms that make a positive contribution to society and provide benefits to society had higher employees' engagement levels and hence higher productivity (Mirvis, 2012).

Ethical CSR activities encourage employees within an organisation to be positive towards their duties, responsibilities, and the organisation itself, which helps achieve greater employees' engagement levels. Gao and He (2017) also stated that discretionary CSR is enhanced through employees' planned behaviour, that leads to improved organisational efficiency. Therefore, when employees identify that their organisation maintains a good CSR image within the country and its citizens, it develops a feeling of determination towards community engagement and corporate philanthropy (Kim et al., 2018). CSR practices are also oriented at the organisation's workers, resulting in enhanced employees' engagement. As a result, it is established that CSR plays a vital role in enhancing employees' engagement, which leads to increased staff productivity.

According to Kitzmueller and Shimshack, (2012) social interactions are controlled by the benefit analysis and the subject cost. The cost benefit analysis is the term that refers to the process of evaluating and comparing the estimated or projected cost of the task or project. This process crucially serves in addressing the risks and benefits associated with the project and

helps the organisation to analyse whether the task or project will be beneficial in terms of contributing towards the progress of the organisation. Moreover, it is dependent on the contrast of alternatives. Azim (2016) also explains that the coordination between the employees and the organisation is usually grounded and symbolic. The communication process is mostly controlled by reciprocity norms. Many types of research are in line with the norms related to reciprocity. These norms are dependent on the inopportune alignment of the employees on which employees must support people who have assisted them in the past. The employees are engaged enough that they reciprocate the incentives which they receive for the company related to their fulfilment and betterment of the agreements or contracts with the company or the stakeholders (Gao and He, 2017). Due to a lack of awareness of the impact of CSR practices on employee behaviour and attitudes, erroneous conclusions about the impact or value of CSR may be drawn.

Several theoretical models have been used in different dimensions of work related to employees' engagement such as psychological contract, trust within the management, turnover rates and organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB). According to Gao and He (2017), planned behaviour is an important motivational model for describing particular engagement of employees within discretionary behavioural conducts since such conducts are neither mandatory, nor identified by any rewards system within the organisation. In such behavioural situations, employee interactions are similar and can link to the typical relationship which is constantly changing with no time-constraints and are dependent on employee benefits (Archimi et al, 2018).

Kim et al. (2018) highlighted that the internal CSR dimension deals with the employees in an entirely socially responsible manner, which will then help decide the practices which employees will adopt to maintain their behaviour within the company. When the employees recognise that the company and its leaders treat the workforce positively, they will reciprocate this behaviour and return a positive attitude towards the company. Steinmetz et al. (2016) added that employees have become more concerned about what their company objectives are and that they are motivated to work towards achieving those objectives. According to Gao and He (2017), employees are naturally flexible and adaptive. Therefore, they interpret and understand the reasons within the work-settings and intended attitudes. When organisations have high CSR standards and ethical policies, this can be taken as a strong partner as well as a respectable component of the overall organisational community.

Similarly, Sarfo et al. (2020) contended in their study that, when organisations integrate environmental and social concerns within their operations and while interacting with their important stakeholders, they are able to influence and motivate their employees to demonstrate higher ethical behaviours. The authors stated that this is commonly noted when employees become more responsible about the work they do and act in the best interest of their company and customers by avoiding unethical behaviour. Employees refraining from providing false information about products and services to its customers can be considered as an example of this.

Therefore, it can be stated that CSR acts as a positive stimulator that demonstrates to employees the compassion of their place of work and thereby encourages ethical behaviour. According to the research conducted by Slack, Corlett and Morris (2015), internal CSR activities of an organisation helps employees experience an increased feeling of participation, optimistic vision, and self-esteem which influences positive behavioural changes within the employees. This in return, enhances the employees' engagement levels within the organisational context. Furthermore, organisations are investing in their internal CSR activities in different ways to achieve employee satisfaction, which ultimately leads to deeper employees' engagement towards their jobs and towards the organisation (Ong et al, 2018).

2.4. Impact of CSR on Employee Retention

The concept of CSR has gained unprecedented importance since the financial crash in 2008 and it is now assessed directly in connection with reducing employee turnover rate (Kim et al., 2020). Furthermore, as stated by De Silva and Lokuwaduge (2020), with the proper application of CSR strategies, a business can ensure that its employees are retained for a long period of time thus avoiding repeated hiring and training costs which would otherwise damage the business' financial performance. Moreover, it is also stated that the concept of CSR holds the potential of enhancing the reputational capital of its entity, which is in consonance with maintaining loyalty with its consumer base (Krémer, 2019).

In addition, as per the study conducted by Fernando and Sutha (2022), it is inferred the reason CSR is attested with much importance is that not only is its implication restricted towards financial performance and company's brand equity, but it is also found to share a proportional relationship with the company's internal stakeholders i.e. employees. According to Bharadwaj and Yameen (2020), CSR is connected with employees' extrinsic and intrinsic motivation and

thus it is important for the business to develop a cohesive internal CSR strategy that can ensure continued association of its employees with the company.

Not employing such policies, will lead to an increase in a business' turnover rate. A lack of CSR policies has also been found to impact brand equity and subsequent effects of this will be evidenced by the business' unsustainability in its industry (Kim et al., 2018). By developing a good CSR strategy, a business can ensure not only employee retention, but also attracting such employees that have the required set of skills and expertise that can accomplish company goals and objectives (Gharleghi et al., 2018). The authors further explain that if a business is successful in its CSR strategy, it is indicative that it will be in a position to develop its competitive advantage and thus able to counter any difficulties posed by its external environment, for example fluctuations in supply and demand, market volatility. Therefore, as agreed by Sarfraz et al. (2018), CSR strategies entail an operational organisational structure that is deemed conducive for the employees' wellbeing and motivation.

In such an environment, Lee and Chen (2018) mention that the business can also ensure that it can increase the operational performance of its employees which will be evident from the level of engagement they show towards the company and partaking in the company's decision-making processes. One such inference that can be drawn from the preceding statement in relation to decision making is that, since the employees are encouraged to provide their opinions on critical business matters, in line with its CSR strategy, it is found to serve the purpose of bridging the gap between the management and its employees (Nie et al., 2018).

Several studies such as the study by Glavas (2016) discussed that CSR leads to employees' motivation. Employers integrate different methods such as recognitions, rewards, training and development to motivate employees. Samuel and Chipunza (2008) identified that motivational factors are commonly used as an employee retention strategy leading to reduced turnover rates. Organisations depend on their employees and their skills to achieve competitive advantage in the market and retaining top talent is challenging due to risks of job poaching. Job poaching is a common practice between competitive firms, which wants to attract talent and achieve advantage over its competitors. When an organisation approaches a person who is already employed at a different company, it is referred to as job poaching (Nandini, et al., 2020). Holland et al. (2007) further stated that companies are required to align its retention strategies with CSR in order to retain talent. Hence, it is determined from the above researches that employee motivation instigated by CSR lead to employee retention.

2.5 Significance and Role of CSR in the Banking Sector

CSR within the banking sector has been conducted with the objective that the banking sectors play an important role in engaging employees and increasing their participation through CSR. Different studies have also shown that many companies were involved in CSR activities during the Covid-19 pandemic by providing awareness about combatting the pandemic situation. The study of Huang and Liu (2020) has also mentioned in their research that after the outbreak of Covid-19, many firms including financial institutions like banks, were observed to engage in various CSR activities.

However, the study of Zhang, Morse and Kambhampati (2017), suggests that many business sectors use multiple techniques and strategies to improve the position of the organisation. In this manner, CSR plays an important role as it improves the business reputation and helps businesses in improving their reputation, which makes the business more efficient by bringing constructive changes within the business sector. Past studies show that CSR is important for increasing the business value of the firm in the banking sector. . In this way, CSR supports many businesses start-ups by providing effective financing sources. The study of Nareeman and Hasan (2013) also suggests that CSR improves customer behaviour and enhances the customer interactions throughout the customer lifecycle. CSR develops customer service relationships and leads to customer retention, hence CSR activities play an important role in influencing a business's customer behaviour and in maintaining a good relationship with the customers, including in the banking sector. Furthermore, the application of CSR activities helps a company to introduce an initiative that could benefit the wider society and the environment as a whole. The corporate sector today is highly criticised for damaging the culture of society and the environment. However, the study of Štreimikienė, and Ahmed (2021) states that CSR can influence employees' retention in an organisation which also improves the employees' planned behaviour by making necessary investments into their growth and development.

Corporate social responsibility helps to promote the business. For instance, the implications of well-managed programmes of corporate social responsibility can help to create a strong brand value, and awareness about the resilient values of the business. In the context of the banking sector, corporate social responsibility also encourages banks to do exceedingly well in their proceedings and revenue generation. As generating stakeholder consciousness and handling stakeholder acknowledgements towards an organisation's CSR actions are key fundamentals in gaining corporate social responsibility's strategic profits, it is crucial for executives to have a more profound understanding of important issues related to corporate social responsibility

and communication. This comprises questions such as what to interconnect (for instance, content of the message), where to interconnect (for instance, channels for message), as well as an acceptance of the business and shareholder specific aspects that influences the efficiency of corporate social responsibility's communication aspect which consequently favour most of the outcomes and helps communal and social benefit (Romani, Grappi and Bagozzi 2013). The corporate social responsibility concept helps raise the customers' confidence in banks. It also encourages businesses to take part in different communities' welfare and makes efforts in directing corporate social responsibility reserves on local infrastructures, development efforts, and determinations based on environmental aspects (Park et al, 2014). However, there is a promising need to build an understanding and highlight the need and importance of corporate social responsibility amongst public and governing organisational bodies. Several organisations including the banking sector have recognised the long-term benefits of corporate social responsibility's resourcefulness and its exposures and have subsequently made use of corporate social responsibility strategies as a step towards performing their commercial procedures (Akram, Tang, and Tariq, 2020). In the area of corporate social responsibility activities, banks are entitled to construct short-term development programmes in order to enhance the performance, appearance and revenue of the bank (MacGregor Pelikánová, 2019). In the report of Wingwon (2012), the term "capability" has been defined as a unique bundle or combination of processes, skills, and knowledge that is generated from tacit knowledge, spans levels of the firm, and helps the implementation of important activities under a given process. Whereas CSR capabilities have been defined as the processes, skills, and knowledge of the organisation related to evaluating, planning, and implementing the activities of the CSR campaigns. Bocean et al. (2014) have stated that capabilities often comprise the complex patterns of coordination which are observed between the planned behaviour of employees and other important resources of the company such as consumers and society.

Similarly, the research of Malik (2015) has also indicated that the capabilities of an organisation can help in increasing the motivation levels of its employees towards higher commitment in accomplishing the important objectives of the company. Likewise, the findings of Sinthupundaja et al. (2019) have shown that the quantity of a resource, as well as the capability of evaluating, executing, and planning activities related to CSR initiatives tend to have a positive correlation with the financial performance of the organisation. Therefore, CSR capabilities play a vital role for organisations to achieve strategic competitiveness in their industries.

2.6 Types of CSR

The study of Kucharska and Kowalczyk (2019), described that CSR improves the corporate image and reputation, depending on the ability of the CSR. In this regard, companies spend their resources on CSR in a way that provide benefits to the external society and also to stakeholders such as employees, investors, government, based on the type of CSR activities and the people engaged in the CSR activity. Additionally, to understand corporate social responsibility (CSR), it is important to understand the two types of CSR activities, which further describe the relationship of CSR with employees' engagement in the banking sector (Ferreira and de Oliveria, 2014).

2.6.1 Organisational Efforts – Internal CSR

Internal CSR practices are those that focus on a company's internal stakeholders such as employees and shareholders. Milton Friedman (1971), one of the Nobel Memorial Prize-winning economists was in the opinion that CSR of a company should be towards making profit for its shareholders. Internal CSR activities towards employees focuses on providing them with good working conditions, having policies and practices in place that protects employees' wellbeing, fairness, and equality (Ferreira and de Oliveria, 2014). Employees' health and safety, job security, career development opportunities, training and development are other forms of internal CSR activities. Furthermore, business leaders within the banking sector understand that workforce and cultural diversity in the workplace is also an important tool for gratifying employees who are from different cultures and backgrounds (Rajeswari & Menon, 2015).

Cultural divergence in the banking has increased over the years and equal opportunities are being provided to the employees. Organisations along with those in the banking sector should make good efforts and ensuring that each employee is treated equally irrespective of the difference in their cultural background.

The goal of organisational efforts is to achieve employee satisfaction which eventually leads to employee loyalty (Zhu, et al., 2014). It has been observed that internal CSR organisational efforts are important for employees' retention which can be achieved thorough incentives that leads to employees' engagement to increase. According to the study of Anwar and Abdullah (2021) incentives are important as they are considered to be based on organisational efforts and lead to the employees' retention to increase. In addition to this it is important that employees believe that there is an organisational justice when the companies execute CSR programmes.

CSR activities have a direct effect on the perceptions of employees on management justice and equality.

The relationship between internal CSR and employees' engagement can be discussed through the employee motivation theory whereby companies that meet employees' psychological needs through internal CSR attain a motivated workforce. Employees' motivation is vital in achieving employees' engagement (Riyanto et al., 2021). Alternatively, the impact of internal CSR on employees' engagement can also be supported by the Social Exchange Theory (SET). This theory suggests that employees reciprocate what they receive from the company. When the organisation offers employees with good working conditions, fairness amongst the employees and development opportunities, then the employees will display more engagement towards their jobs and reciprocate the corporate actions through dedication and commitment towards the company and its goals (Jia, et al., 2019).

2.6.2 Corporate Philanthropy – External CSR

External CSR activities refer to the different actions a company takes to benefit the external stakeholders of a company. The external stakeholders can be *customers* whereby the company focuses on providing value to the customers through the products and services, the *natural environment* through green, sustainability and environmental projects, or the *society* by participating in humanitarian projects, donations, and community development projects (Jia, et al., 2019). Many businesses in the banking sector align their business strategies with corporate philanthropic efforts. Philanthropic efforts refer to the CSR strategies which help in determining the wellbeing of society that is not a requirement from the law. For this purpose, the banking sector mainly uses the corporation's contributions towards charitable and socially responsible projects. Additionally, philanthropic efforts also help the corporate communities to uphold peace and wellbeing within the social environment. The study of Park, Lee and Kim (2014) also shows that the banking sector mostly use the philanthropy efforts for the goodwill and betterment of society and for this purpose, they practice CSR activities for attaining several advantages in society. The study of Haynes, Murray & Dillard (2013), pointed out that when their local communities need help, the banking sector must provide opportunities to benefit them and offer financial benefits and moral support.

The impact of External CSR activities on the employees' engagement is commonly described using the Social Identity theory (SIT), which is further discussed under the theoretical

framework section. According to the SIT, employees' go through a psychological procedure in order to classify themselves into different social groups. When an organisations reputation amongst the society is good, employees' they identify themselves as a part of that organisation to achieve self-worth and self-improvement. By participating in external CSR activities, organisations attract a good brand image and reputation. This helps the employees to develop a sense of pride for being a part of the organisation and fulfils their social-identity needs (Jia, et al., 2019). Once the employee develops a positive identity with the organisation, it results in high engagement levels and retention rates of the employees.

2.7 Dimensions of Corporate Social Responsibility

The expression "corporate social responsibility" was designed to label commercial self-regulation incorporated into a corporate model which comprises various dimensions of corporate actions (Etter et al. 2019). To benefit different corporate sectors, corporate social responsibility professionally incorporates business principles, practices, ethics, norms, and policies combined into the commercial culture. The dimensions of corporate social responsibility comprise nine mechanisms in the banking sector, manufacturing, and different other sectors, which are typically conveyed in company's annual reports and accounts. These dimensions/categories are shareholder, employee, manager/governance, customer, supplier, competitor, community and society, environment, and corporate social responsibility management (Szegedi, Khan, and Lentner, 2020). The primary stakeholders recognised in a firm include the shareholders, supervisory team, consumers, contractors, communities, and natural surroundings. It is concluded that to achieve sustainability in business, companies must determine primary stakeholders influencing the firm, determine their requirements and formulate organisational policies and practices to satisfy them (Dzeawuni, 2020).

- Shareholders
- Employees
- Governance
- Customers
- Suppliers
- Environment
- Competitors
- Community
- CSR Management

Figure 2: Dimensions of CSR (Adopted from Szegedi, Khan, and Lentner, 2020)

The stakeholders' items are measured as appreciating shareholders, identification of the relationship of investor and management, common mediums for dialogues, evidence disclosure for shareholders and bonus interest and long-term progress (Venturelli, Cosma, and Leopizzi, 2018). Employee items dimension identifies gender diversity, employee security and hygienic issues, covers employee benefits, provision of equal opportunity, employee health and welfare, facilities to employees' families such as medical assistance and education, female employees' policies without discrimination, employee motivation, satisfaction, training, and education aspect as well, and rewards along with minorities' anti-discrimination policy (Soni, and Mehta, 2020). In addition to that, manager/governance perform in corporate social responsibility through a board of directors and independent directors, board effectiveness with a proper governor structure, identification of the relationship between all stakeholders, management, and staff (Khan, and Szegedi, 2020).

Corporate social responsibility contributes in the customer items through customer relationship management, marketing practices which are responsibly ethical and legal, customer satisfaction and awareness, socially accountable investment, socially in charge of saving, micro financing and credits, funding initiatives to not-for-profit organisations (Moisescu, 2017).

Supplier items also serves corporate social responsibility with equal opportunity to suppliers, facility of information to suppliers, feedback system and complaint management system, supplier rational negotiation, long-term association with suppliers, provision of care, and improvements to the systems (Fandos-Roig et al., 2021). Furthermore, corporate social responsibility also implies in terms of competitor items in the aspect of association with competitors, competitors' collaboration, ethical selling arrangements which should be free from misleading advertisements (Bukhari, Hashim, and Amran, 2020). In addition to that, community and society items of corporate social responsibility covers charitable investments, scholarship and internships, education and health, poverty eradication, employment opportunities, sponsorships in the context of culture and sports, natural disasters aid, programmes for community support (Nugraheni, and Khasanah, 2019). Finally, the last dimension of corporate social responsibility also measured the environment aspects in the banking sector which includes planting and green initiatives, pollution controlling aspects, environmental guidelines, and awards for environmental security, future strategies for ecofriendly products (Tulcanaza-Prieto et al., 2020).

2.8 CSR from the Employee Perspective

From the perspective of the employee, there is a certain belief and attitude towards the Human Resource Management (HRM) policies of the company. This belief of the employees varies from one to another based on how information is communicated to them. According to the study conducted by Ong et al. (2018), employees frequently take external information but their behavioural and attitudinal reactions to that information might vary. Every employee has their own opinion and perception and based on their opinion they tend to react to the situation in different ways.

CSR activities of a company indicate how much the company is dedicated to giving back to the country and the society in which they are operating. The employees view their company's social responsibility behaviour with the belief that, if the company is concerned about its surroundings, that means the company will also be responsible for their employees and the employees' needs. Positive CSR activities bring positive outcomes in the case of company employees. Therefore, the concept of CSR is a catalyst that impacts employee behaviour towards CSR (Lu et al., 2020). Similarly, while highlighting the importance of CSR activities in assisting companies to become more socially responsible, Lee and Chen (2018) under their

article stated that if companies fail to recognise the efforts and voluntary work of their employees under the CSR campaigns, they become demotivated to participate in such activities in the future and develop a negative perception about their firms. The authors also stated that praising the efforts of employees under CSR initiatives not only increases their satisfaction with the company but also motivates them to stay in the organisation in the long run. The reason behind this is that upon receiving recognition from the employers or management, employees are able to perceive that their work is valued in their organisations.

Past literature confirms that based on discretionary, economic, ethical, and legal corporate social responsibility, the concept of various stakeholders might be organised and planned in an advanced manner. A cross-culture study performed by Shen and Benson (2016) indicates the perspective of upper-level managers through a stakeholder framework. The CSR perspective is dependent on the concept of organisational justice: different activities of corporate social responsibility for the social benefit, namely procedural corporate social responsibility, an outcome of the CSR functions (distributive nature of CSR) and the communication among the people as a consequence of the CSR function (interactional nature of CSR). A study conducted by He et al. (2019), explained a structure that describes how the organisational performance, environment setting, and society impacted in the behavioural response and attitude facilitated in the employees due to their change in perspective about CSR.

According to Hemingway (2005), there are 4 types of employees whose idea and perception of CSR varies based on their morals and intents around the concept demonstrated in Figure 3 below. These employees' values play a key role on their perspective of CSR. In order to overcome the reluctance of frustrated corporate social entrepreneurs, conformists and the apathetic, it's important that companies undertake different strategies and approaches and maintain a corporate culture to ensure employee inclination towards CSR.

Figure 3: Categories of Employees in CSR (adopted from Hemingway, 2005)

Hur et al. (2018) gave the concluding remarks in his study that as CSR impacts the employee behaviour, CSR also impacts the overall outcomes of the organisation by impacting the employee behaviour. The perspective of CSR is seen to move as a standard parameter to guide the decisions and attitudes of the employees related to their association with the company. The perceived justice impacts the behavioural conduct and the attitudes of the employees. Corporate social responsibility not only impacts on commitment but also on other behaviours and attitudes of the employees, for example, citizenship behaviour towards the organisation (Steinmetz et al, 2016). Glavas (2016) in this regard, also stated that CSR activities can help employees bring more of their whole selves to work. This helps them to enhance their work quality since they feel more engaged with their jobs. Likewise, Murmura et al. (2017) also stated that when firms conduct CSR activities, they become more encouraged to implement and use high-quality working standards (such as SA 8000 standard) to apply, maintain, and develop socially acceptable working practices. This also positively influences employees' behaviour by giving them a sense of pride to work for their companies.

Many organisations are focused on achieving higher engagements among employees through corporate social responsibility programmes to compete with the external demands of the market

(Lu et al., 2020). Moreover, to attain the real-time advantages that CSR gives to the overall position of the organisation. Effective CSR activities and programmes help in building a positive image and benefits in company branding since they impact the current employee commitment. Additionally, it also increases the value of the company for prospective employees (He et al, 2019).

The study conducted by Azim (2016), which assessed the attitudes and perceptions of employees towards sustainable growth and CSR, followed three concepts. These concepts are; the impact of stakeholders of the organisation on their CSR functions, insights of CSR, and an action plan to implement CSR. Azim indicated that CSR was only used to resolve the issues related to social responsibility that are linked with the company's economic gains.

Another study was performed by Tuan (2018) related to the expectations and perceptions of employees towards the CSR activities of their companies. The author explained the differences between the perception level, expectations, and individual factors of employees. The study indicated that the perception of employees was interlinked with their possible expectations for CSR activities (Hur et al, 2018). Nevertheless, it is also important to understand the impact of external factors that tend to influence the employees' perspective about corporate social responsibility. An example of such an external factor can be taken from the recent outbreak of Covid-19. In this regard, the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on the employees' engagement was investigated by Chanana (2020) under which various sectors such as the telecoms sector, banking sector and IT sector were studied by the author and the findings of this study indicated that during Covid-19, employees' engagement was highly influenced in some cases because organisations were laying off their employees. Additionally, the study also indicated that there are some companies who were involved in CSR activities during the pandemic by providing awareness about combatting the pandemic situation. Huang and Liu (2020) mentioned in their article that after the outbreak of Covid-19, many firms, including financial institutions such as banks, were observed to engage with various CSR activities.

These activities included creating awareness amongst people (e.g., to maintain social distancing), and on reducing the spread of the virus (by providing free masks or hand sanitisers). According to Vinerean et al. (2013), when organisations contribute to the wellbeing of the customers and the society at large by undertaking different CSR activities (similar to the actions mentioned above), employees feel more pride and satisfaction for working for such

companies. This, in turn, motivates the employees to stay with these companies in the long term.

However, by considering these postulations, it can be inferred that more research is required to determine whether or not similar initiatives that have been undertaken by banking institutions to protect people from Covid-19 are encouraging employees to stay with these banks in the long-run. Following are some of the dimensions that form employees' perception regarding CSR.

2.8.1 CSR Motivation of Employees

Employees require some motivational and directional flows that have to be encompassed to survive in the business environment (Hur et al, 2018). In the article by Sarfraz et al. (2018) it has also been stated that CSR activities help in generating a positive impact on employees' behaviour by inciting pleasant feelings in them. This, in turn, helps in fostering corporate citizenship behaviour among the employees. Thus, from this finding, it can be inferred that the higher the familiarity with CSR initiatives among the employees, the more motivated they will become to display engagement towards CSR. It is implied that the motivation of the employees to engage in such activities would help an organisation bring new and creative ideas for CSR and hence it will also increase employees' engagement.

CSR's impact on motivation of employees can be further discussed based on intrinsic and extrinsic motivation factors. When employees participate in an activity to achieve or receive an external expectation, it is considered as extrinsic motivation. Monetary rewards are a common form of extrinsic motivation. Long & Shields (2010) suggested that employees are motivated by extrinsic factors for reasons that has a *symbolic significance* for them such as appreciation for their support, *informational significance* whereby they consider monetary rewards as a response to their contribution, or as an *instrumental significance* itself since monetary rewards have a value for them.

In contrast, intrinsic motivation are tasks that gives employees an internal satisfaction for doing an activity. When employees participate in tasks that they are interested in or ignites satisfaction, joy, growth, creativity or expression, these influence their intrinsic motivation. Two key characteristics of intrinsic motivation is that it differs from one person to another as what gives an employee internal satisfaction is different to what makes another employee satisfied, and that the intrinsic motivator within one person also tends to change from time-to time (Tampubolon, 2016). Motivation of employees to complete specific tasks are derived from

intrinsic and extrinsic motivation factors. This is evidenced through research of Skudiene & Auruskeviciene (2012) that studied the positive relationship between CSR activities dedicated on employees and employees' motivation. Furthermore, relating to the service industry, Glavas (2016) substantiated that CSR activities motivate employees both intrinsically and extrinsically and that CSR activities eventually result in competitive advantage for the organisation.

Several researchers have studied how employees' engagement can be enhanced through employees' motivation. Motivation on itself is not sufficient to achieve organisation's success. It is crucial that companies achieve the engagement of its employees in the current competitive market. According to a study conducted by Habte (2016), it was established that leaders believe extrinsic motivation plays a smaller role compared to intrinsic motivation when it comes to employees' engagement as intrinsic factors have an effect on the psychological characteristics of an employee. The importance of intrinsic motivation for employees' engagement was also researched by Khan and Iqbal (2013), who further identified work stress, appreciation, satisfaction and interesting job as the key intrinsic factors that instigated employees' engagement. The extrinsic motivation factors the study identified to be the drivers of employee engagement are salary, career development, job security and recognition. It was further confirmed by the research of Christian, et al. (2011) that there is a relationship between the motivational factors and employee's engagement.

The study of Riyanto, Endri and Herlisha (2021) further stated that motivation is an important factor that leads to employees' engagement and productivity to increase, hence leading to incentives to be developed. Motivation enables new ideas to be generated and it further leads to values of organisations to increase. In addition to this, the innovation process of the company improves and it enhances the reputation of the company. Furthermore, the motivation-hygiene theory also highlights the hygiene factors and motivation factors that affect and influence employee motivation levels, which is further discussed under the theoretical framework section.

2.8.2 CSR and Organisational Justice

The concepts of organisational justice and corporate social responsibility are dependent on the ethical principles of regulated treatment. According to Nazir and Islam (2020), the organisations that are CSR-driven treat their employees and the overall community ethically. The concepts are dependent on the research related to organisational justice. As highlighted by Sarfraz et al. (2016), CSR programmes highly impact the observations of the stakeholders

about the justice and fairness of the organisation. According to Shen and Benson (2016), social justice can be described as the company's engagement with respect to CSR initiatives.

Employees tend to believe that there is an organisational justice when the companies execute CSR programmes. CSR activities have a direct effect on the perceptions of employees on management justice and equality. Organisational justice is considered as a parameter taken by the employees to assess the company's efforts (Farid et al, 2019). The past literature indicates that there is a direct correlation between organisational justice and employee perspective on CSR. The insights about CSR directly impact the employees' opinions about organisational fairness and justice. Moreover, it is also concluded in the previous researches that employee perspective is positively linked with organisational justice as well as with their job satisfaction level (Azim, 2016).

2.8.3 CSR and Organisational Commitment

In the study performed by Steinmetz et al. (2016) on organisational citizenship behaviour, employees' engagement has various components of organisational citizenship behaviour and commitment. Organisational commitment links to the sense of belonging and personal attitude towards the firm. Tuan (2018) believes that engagement is not a behaviour, but the extent to which a person is involved and incorporated in their roles and responsibilities. These features and nature of the correlation between employee-employer relationships can be classified into two behaviours: extra-role behaviour and in-role behaviour (Hur et al, 2018). In their study, Lin and Liu (2017) mentioned that when firms carry out different socially responsible practices by engaging in different CSR activities such as reducing carbon emission, conducting philanthropic activities, etc., the turnover intentions among the workers are reduced substantially. This is because workers often feel proud while working for such companies/firms that engage in different CSR activities, which as a result, increases their job satisfaction and reduces attrition in the company.

Previous literatures indicates that the employees do not just respond to the way they have been treated by the organisation, but they also react to the way others are treated by the organisation. The authors from the past researches explain that different programmes of corporate social responsibility support increasing psychological health under the subjective context since this boosts self-esteem, and overall confidence level and employee satisfaction. Thus, CSR is considered an evident practice that creates a positive effect on employee behaviour and commitment, service-driven citizenship, and thus, on employee loyalty (Conner, 2020).

2.9 Impact of CSR on Organisation Citizenship Behaviour

It has been observed that when employees increase their identification with the company, the interests and values of that company becomes an important part of the employees' self-concept (Supriyanto, 2013). This is usually demonstrated under the behaviours of the employees when they consider the collective interest of the company as their self-interest. Moreover, they also become more motivated to accomplish the goals of their organisations by acting in the best interest of their companies. Fatima et al. (2015) stated that by conducting different CSR campaigns to enhance the well-being of the society, top management of the company can increase the organisation's identification of their employees, which in turn, can cause employees to experience the success or failure of their companies as their own.

This, in turn, can encourage employees to engage under those organisational citizenship behaviours that can assist their companies to accomplish their objectives because demonstrating such positive attitudes or behaviours will reflect positively on their organisations and by association, on the employees themselves (Abdullah and Rashid, 2012). This, as a result, can again help organisations to increase both the motivation and productivity of their employees successfully.

Past researches show that CSR is an important factor, which describes employee behaviour and also encourages the employees to engage with those organisational citizenship behaviours. The relationship between CSR and OCB are discussed and described in different studies such as Farid et al. (2011). The results of these studies show that CSR has a positive influence on organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB). The social identity theory (SIT) shows a theoretical linkage between CSR and OCB. Mory, Wirtz, and Göttel (2017) postulated that in SIT the employees can accomplish positive self-esteem, if they can experience an in-group identity, which in turn, assists them to differentiate themselves from out-group members. Thus, it can be stated that with its underlying procedures associated with self-enhancement, SIT can be considered as an effective framework for describing the effect of CSR initiatives in planned attitude of employees in OCB.

In a recent study by Beal (2013), many banks are interested in bringing positive change to society, through authentic leadership, organisational justice, and organisational perceived support that positively affects the OCB among employees. For this purpose, they create a connection with different companies which are engaged in CSR (Beal, 2013). Many scholars such as Utami et al. (2021) have found that OCB has a positive association with employee

loyalty to an organisation, and the operationalisation of organisations also assists the OCB in achieving goals in CSR. These studies show that CSR has positive impacts on organisational citizenship behaviour.

2.10 Role of Human Resource in Influencing Planned Behaviours

Gond et al. (2011) in their study, have argued that companies (under their operational frameworks) should always try to make their human resource department as a steward of human assets. For this, they should try to strengthen the capacity of their human resources in order to support employees to become more active while performing their work and accept the culture of responsible leadership. The authors further claimed that the decisions and actions of employees often play a crucial role in making organisational strategies come to life under CSR campaigns. Due to this reason, human resource professionals are often required to foster and nurture the performance of the CSR campaigns in their organisations (Inyang, Awa and Enuoh, 2011). This also includes the responsibility of making sure that the organisation, as well as its stakeholders, can gain the utmost benefits from the CSR initiatives that are undertaken by the company.

Jamali et al. (2015) stated that for any organisation, employees are usually considered as important assets, thus necessary efforts should always be made by the company to improve employees' planned behaviours by making necessary investments towards their growth and development. As employees are commonly perceived to participate under the CSR activities that are conducted by their organisations, HR professionals are often made responsible to guide the behaviour of the employees to ensure the successful execution/implementation of the CSR campaign.

In this regard, Garavan and McGuire (2010) recommended in their article that internal stakeholders of the organisations (i.e., employees) should always be repositioned in such a way that allows them to assume a leading position under the CSR activities of their companies. Whereas Voegtlin and Greenwood (2016) stated that making investments in the skills and behaviours of employees can also enable organisations to attain substantial benefits not just for their companies, but also for the employees, society, and environment. On the other hand, Rok and Mulej (2014) has perceived the strategic business partner role of HRM as a positive opportunity that can help in enhancing the process related to the policy formulation and implementation that is carried out under CSR campaigns. The author has considered this role

as highly significant in helping the organisation to enhance its image in the eyes of its important stakeholders.

Similarly, it has been asserted by Lam and Khare (2010) that HR can help organisations in managing the implementation process of the CSR plan and in monitoring its adoption by the employees proactively. This also includes celebrating or documenting the success of the CSR initiative throughout the organisation. Nevertheless, the performance of CSR initiatives can only be made possible by encouraging the involvement of employees. In this regard, Lam and Khare (2010) restated that HR managers can capitalise on different opportunities and use various tools to leverage the commitment of employees towards the organisation's CSR strategy. This can also help to increase employees' engagement levels with CSR initiatives.

Likewise, Sharma, Sharma and Devi (2011) in their article, asserted that organisations should always try to focus on the triple bottom line (i.e., social, economic, and environmental performance) while devising and implementing their CSR strategies. This also includes the task of placing great emphasis on the sustainability of their companies. Sustainable corporations have been defined by Haugh and Talwar (2010) as those companies that focus on achieving economic profits, maintain the quality of the environment, and contribute positively to increase social equity. Thus, the authors stated that the task related to devising, implementing, and monitoring all the activities related to ensuring the triple bottom line performance of CSR campaigns requires the crucial involvement of HR professionals. This can also increase the effectiveness of CSR programme under the leadership of HR.

Even though many studies have recognised the fact that CSR tends to impact the commitment of employees with their organisation, it is also important to realise that CSR can influence a wide range of organisational behaviours and attitudes of employees related to organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational justice (Shen and Benson, 2016). Due to this reason, Turner et al. (2019) reported that there are several important guiding principles related to CSR that directly involve participation from employees and HR professionals. For instance, these principles generally include the guidelines related to the efficient and effective utilisation of HR capital, as well as the creation of knowledge and intellectual capital that contributes to the sustainable development of the organisation. This also includes maintaining equity with distributive justice among employees and human resource rights assurance (Tuan, 2016).

As CSR initiatives generally require a radical change of behaviour and philosophy, HR professionals can also help organisations by acting as a change agent under the change management process of their companies. Almost every HR process and policy tends to generate CSR implications for the organisations since CSR sustainability often demands a more integrated and holistic approach towards managing people (Cohen, 2017). Moreover, since employees' planned behaviour is considered as critically important in making CSR initiatives a success for the organisation, the primary task of HR should always be based on managing the work of employees appropriately.

For this reason, HR's role is also considered as pivotal in driving and supporting CSR initiatives in the organisation. Although the actions of corporate CSR impacts the behaviour and attitudes of employees, the extent or degree of this impact usually depends on the perceptions of the employees, as well as their evaluations of these actions (Newman et al., 2016). Therefore, it can be stated that the perception and behaviours of employees towards CSR campaigns/initiatives influence the implementation and success of the CSR activities that are conducted by organisations.

The determinants of the Human Resource department are progressively becoming familiar as a crucial element in an organisation's success; as a result, a main emphasis of the Human Resource department's involvements is an exertion to encourage the attitudes and behaviour of the workers. It is significant to make evidence that providing the employees with the essential knowledge, skills and behaviour is able to make an organisational management to comprehend its objectives and purposes. Consequently, the Human Resource department plays a fundamental role in manipulating the actions and behaviour of the employees in a business. It is significant to note that it is a condition that the employees with the essential proficiency and behaviour is capable to make a company understand its purposes. Therefore, the Human Resource department plays an essential role in influencing the behaviour of the workforce in a business (Ren, Tang, and Jackson, 2018).

A conception about Human Resource Management is that it tends to increase productivity in the company and enables profit maximisation. A Human Resource department addresses the behaviours of employees' expertise working in the entire organisation. A Human Resource department in the context of the management is best positioned to declare the significance of efforts and employment direction in a corporation's performance and the part of such structures, rooted as they are in sectorial and socially related resources and official regimes. In captivating

this opinion, it is realised that employee perception and their outcomes are important fundamentals that determine their planned behaviour. The anticipation and the fair play theories have been projected to explain this. According to the study by Jing et al. (2019), which shed light on the relevance of planned behaviour, it is suggested that entities are to be expected to perform behaviours that they identify will bring appreciated results; therefore, not rewarding certain compulsions to workforces may create a change in their behaviour (NgoHenha, 2018).

2.11 Perceived Organisational Performance

For most companies (including their stakeholders), CSR campaigns and initiatives are often perceived as a significant consideration, but numerous studies have shown different results in terms of the relationship that exists between performance outcome and CSR campaigns (Petrenko et al., 2016). Some studies on CSR conducted in the past also examined its impact on the performance of the organisation by taking corporate financial performance (CFP) as an indicator/metric of organisational success. The exponential increment under the expenditures related to improving the social responsibility of organisations in the past few years highlight that most managers find CSR programmes highly beneficial in terms of attaining economic benefits (Ali et al., 2010). This is especially true with regard to achieving the financial objectives of the organisation that are highly important for maximising the wealth of shareholders. Another example of the positive impact of CSR on the organisation's performance can be taken from the article of Sun and Yu (2015), who stated that CSR activities impacts the performance of employees by motivating them to improve the operational performance of their companies in comparison to those employees who work for less socially responsible organisations. Nevertheless, this again is made possible by the corporate citizenship behaviours that are demonstrated by the employees whenever they participate in such activities (Sarfraz et al., 2018). The study of impact of CSR on organisational performance in terms of employee commitment and financial performance was entirely conducted in developed markets, particularly in western economies. However, the financial sector and other financial institutions were left out of the study of Sarfraz et al. (2018), and the United Kingdom was not a part of the research either. Therefore, the current paper provides an inquiry that intends to first analyse the adoption of CSR practices in the banking industry in the United Kingdom. Second, to investigate the impact of CSR on employees' engagement in the banking sector in the United Kingdom.

Likewise, under the research of Al-Shuaibi (2016), the use of CSR practices was supported under those firms that are operating in developing countries because the adoption of CSR practices by firms and multinational enterprises within the developing countries can help in improving both their productivity and ability to innovate. This, in turn, can help them to enhance their financial performance. Furthermore, CSR has been seen as a significant factor for enterprises since it is believed that the application of CSR practices in the company changes the image of the firm. CSR has been proven to have a positive impact on the society and citizens, as well as benefiting the organisations. Organisations that have a high degree of CSR activities have positive employee behaviour, and this has been investigated to determine the impact on employees' engagement practices (Azim, 2016).

Prior findings of these studies have not provided any appropriate conclusion about the relationships between performance outcomes, CSR initiatives, as well as reporting neutral, positive, and negative associations (Tang, Hull and Rothenberg, 2012). The inconsistency of the results that describe the relationship between corporate performance and CSR practices have been noted to occur for various reasons. For instance, one such reason is related to the presence of mediated variables like employees' citizen behaviour and organisational commitment under the relationship between the organisation's performance and CSR campaigns. Despite these inconsistent results, CSR is often considered to be positively linked with the organisation's financial performance and thus, supports the case of CSR implementation by the companies (Cavaco and Crifo, 2014).

2.12 CSR Activities for Banks

Banks are considered financial intermediaries for society, and they have the role of managing the finances of society. Banks are considered essential for economic development as their activities revolve around monitoring, screening and enforcement in the matters of finances of society. As the CSR model describes the economic, social and environmental benefits for society, banks in particular have a high focus on the economic development aspect (Bongini et al., 2017). It is evident through recent studies that banks have applied CSR attributes in their operations and are becoming more socially responsible. There are multiple ways the banks have demonstrated social responsibility in their actions and operations. Some banks have considered

supporting charitable events as their corporate social responsibility (Sigurthorsson, 2012), while others have managed to incorporate social responsibility by increasing the professionalism of people working in the financial sector and observing ethical codes in their operations. Banks also implement transparency, protection of rights of customers and cooperate with societal institutions by providing them support in funding and charity (Paulik et al., 2015). These business practices not only benefit the stakeholders of the bank but strengthen the relationship with its customers. Customer satisfaction plays a key role in the assessment of banks for the financial market as customer satisfaction is in direct relation with the success of the banking business model (Senthikumar, Ananth & Arulraj 2011).

According to Loureiro Sardinha and Reijnders (2012), the increase in productivity and customer satisfaction can increase financial performance and result in the reduction of cost directly or indirectly. Thus, it is evident that banks must adhere to CSR practices as this can also benefit them and support their business in different ways. Commercial banks must adhere to their social responsibility because they are directly monitored by regulating authorities and are observed the public. Commercial banks are responsible for contributing to the economy by providing services to a diverse population of society, so it is important for them to take part in CSR to enhance their image in the eye of the public. The contribution of banks in their social responsibility is essential for any society to progress towards a sustainable future (Gangi Mustilli & Varrone, 2018).

Banks play a key role in maintaining the economic stability in a country; hence it is important for the financial sector to be stable for a country's economy to be stable. Environmental issues such as climate change carries major risks to the financial sector (Bank of England, 2022). Banks need to focus on tackling climate change in order to avoid any diverse effects on the country's economy. Fighting climate change should not only be incorporated in the bank's operations but should also be a part of the company mission and policies to ensure financial, economic and monetary stability. According to Bank of England's climate change pledge, the bank has launched a Climate Biennial Exploratory Scenario (CBES) system to identify the flexibility of the UK banks and other financial institutions in diverse climate change consequences (Bank of England, 2022). This system will focus on controlling the financial exposure, recognising challenges on organisational models and risk management to minimise the impact of climate change on the financial sector.

2.13 Barriers for banks to undertake CSR

According to Jack Welch, the CEO of General Electric between 1981-2001, the success of a company is determined by three factors: one of which is employees' engagement, which leads to customer satisfaction, and profitability (David et al. 2021). Any institution, according to Welch, cannot succeed without a motivated, empowered, and engaged staff, which then develops organisational citizenship behaviour and aligns employees' allegiance with the firm's objective and vision. As a result, many organisations throughout the world spend time and resources in building policies and practices to foster employees' engagement and dedication to the company. Since prior researches focused mostly on corporate organisations, and the banking sector was the most underserved sector in the current literature, employees' engagement in the UK banking industry was investigated. Furthermore, an assessment made by David et al. (2021) on how banks in the United Kingdom might use CSR as a tool and approach to close the employees' engagement gap in the financial services sector. External and internal CSR have been identified as two distinct aspects of CSR. Given this, the primary goal of this study is to investigate the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement in the UK banking industry, as past research has mostly focused on corporate organisations, and the banking sector has been underrepresented in the current literature.

The organisations that are socially responsible have senior corporate representatives who ensure the responsible conduct of the organisation. The commitment of the top management would also affect the strategic intentions of the businesses towards their social responsibility. The desire of the senior management might encourage others in ensuring that the CSR practices are effectively implemented in the organisations (Kumar, Goyal and Kumar, 2019). Top management is also responsible for improving the CSR orientations of the organisation. As compared to this, the lack of commitment towards the CSR from the management and employees has been found to be a critical barrier in implementing activities of CSR. When they are not highly committed to these practices, it may lead to the poor engagement of employees towards CSR (Zaman et al. 2020). Many organisations do not have a clear understanding and vision on the CSR practices and this creates issues about its effective implementation (Mahmood et al., 2021). Hence it is vital that the company have appropriate CSR strategies and policies in place that encourage leaders' and employees' commitment to CSR, increases CSR knowledge and training, and build a CSR positive perception and culture within the organisation.

Furthermore, there are economic barriers that limits banks from participating in CSR activities. CSR activities could be costly, and it requires banks to invest financial and human resources in CSR projects. Moreover, a study conducted by Gross and Roberts (2009) identified that CSR has a negative impact on the bank loans. It is crucial that banks understand the economic gains of CSR activities by conducting a cost-benefit analysis. CSR helps attract consumer loyalty and improves brand image that attracts customers, which eventually leads to higher profitability for the bank (Goh and Heng, 2013). Similarly, when a bank invests in its workforce, the employees' motivation goes up and hence, the productivity of the company goes up.

Lack of regulatory requirements in a country to encourage CSR is another barrier faced by banks. This barrier is more common in developing countries than developed countries. Countries such as UK and USA are legally required to practice and disclose their CSR and sustainability information in their company reports (Tran, 2014). In the UK, the Companies Act (2006) requires all businesses to promote the business in a way that benefits its stakeholders, which includes the shareholders, employees, suppliers, the environment, and the community.

2.14 Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and Employees' Engagement

There have been several studies conducted to explore the association between corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement. With the help of corporate social responsibility, the banking sector can gain higher employees' engagement which will further lead to greater gain not only for the society but for organisations as well (Chaudhary, 2017). Corporate social responsibility makes efforts for organisations and banks to take the employee's success/failure as their own personal success/failure (Tsourvakas, and Yfantidou, 2018). Furthermore, corporate social responsibility helps to differentiate an organisation from others in the same sector. People make effort for affirmative social individuality and promote CSR. Being a fellow of a community-responsible business can deliver the workforces with psychological individualism with regards to organisational standards and performance (Duthler, and Dhanesh, 2018).

Additionally, this is reinforced by Gashema, (2021) who indicated that employees as well as job candidates are on a mission to find corporations that make assurances about corporate social responsibility as these businesses make necessary plans to involve employees, to attract fresh talent, retain clients, and improve the corporation brand. It is also observed that the more

socially responsible the firm is, the more they will work to enhance the economic state of affairs, higher employee contentment, and respectable reputation (Rettab and Mellahi, 2019). Moreover, the relationship between corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement has also verified that it is not merely beneficial for appealing to talented employees in an organisation but also provides a pronounced way to keep up the involvement of its existing employees (Obeidat, et.al, 2019). It has also been identified that the occurrence of corporate social responsibility creates amongst employees a sense of job safety, self-worth, loyalty, and determination at work, which in turn enhances their contentment (Chaudhary, 2019).

Corporate social responsibility has a vast impact on employees' engagement that has now become a highest priority aspect for trades and industries as well as in banking sectors around the world. Commercial managers identify that a highly involved workforce prove to increase innovation, productivity, and efficiency, while reducing expenses of employing and retaining workforces in a highly uncertain talent marketplace (Nazir and Islam, 2020). Additionally, it is also observed that a corporate social responsibility strategy assists firms to support their workforces as where a company's activities are interconnected to corporate social responsibility it creates favourable sensations for the employees in terms of superiority, desire, gratification, and pleasure that improve their contentment (Rupp, et.al, 2018).

Corporate social responsibility can relate to the employees' engagement to some extent. Specifically, it is observed that the relationship between corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement is qualified by supplementary-role participation in corporate social responsibility such as volunteering (Zhou, Luo, and Tang, 2018). Even though supplementary roles like volunteering support involvement in corporate social responsibility which could positively impact emotionally on employees, excessively involving in supplementary role participation in corporate social responsibility does not serve as a useful mechanism. Nevertheless, a voluntary role within corporate social responsibility resulted in embracing the responsibility of various activities that develops a positive impact on the organisation's functions relevant to the employees, consumers, communities, environment and other shareholders. Apart from this, researchers also instigate a multidimensional communication of CSR in the context of project significance, social provision, and obtainability of properties on employee arrangement (Soni, and Mehta, 2018). Additionally, corporate social responsibility permits the corporations to do far better and encourage them to recognise their values' declarations which have been written down but in reality, companies are often not living up to these standards. This in turn gives directions to the employees of an organisation about the

implementation of principles and regulations of the corporation, which is linked with the investigation that has originated an affirmative connection between corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement (Sobhani, Haque, and Rahman, 2021).

In addition to that, corporate social responsibility demonstrates a developed purpose which indicates that employees will discover efforts which are meaningful for both the employees and the organisation. In the work of Tahir, et al (2021) it was found that social individuality will decide the association between corporate social responsibility and affecting organisational practices. The scholars put forward an accelerative approach for those workforces for whom doing well is important for their own satisfaction and productivity, and corporate social responsibility will be a technique which allows workers to embrace parts of their identity not usually connected to their workplace. These authors stated that corporate social responsibility indicates that banks ought to incorporate corporate social responsibility activities which, when successfully generated, result in better engagement of employees. Besides this, the banks' management play a significant role in creating a positive administrative culture and socially accountable attitude among the staff. Employees' Engagement also provides significance of operational and efficient corporate social responsibility in reducing the risk and enhancing the quality of banking procedures which ultimately results in increasing productivity (Al Amri, Das, and Ben-Ayed, 2019).

2.15 Factors affecting Employees' engagement in the UK Banking Sector

Corporate social responsibility programmes operate as a self-regulating tool where a corporation monitors and makes certain agreements in-line with the law, ethical values and local or international standards. The main goal of organisations is towards achieving profit maximization. However, it is vital for companies to fulfil the social responsibilities towards the stakeholders. Companies that are implementing the CSR activities are able to achieve intangible assets which includes the improvement of brand image, corporate image along with enhancing financial performance (Jiang, 2021).

Factors that affect employees' engagement in the United Kingdom banking sector consist of two major categories, for instance, internal factors and external factors. The internal factors comprise those factors that are located inside the business and influence the method and accomplishment of actions. The external environment comprises a collection of aspects from outside a business that characteristically the business does not have control over and are

difficult to address. Managing the strong points of an organisation's internal factors and identifying potential chances and intimidations outside of its processes are key to the professional banking sector's success. (Kholis and Lubis, 2021). The internal factors in a bank comprise the quality of assets, capital adequacy, operational efficiency cost, diversification of income and liquidity. The internal factors of the organisation such as capital adequacy helps the organisation in arranging the resources for CSR activities. The external factors comprise socio-economic, legal or moral and ethical, political and technological factors. Socioeconomic factors narrate to the standards, confidence and hesitations of the target consumers and their financial abilities to come up with the money for the products that banks are offering. Furthermore, to encounter the moral or social accountability ideals of the consumers and the public, generally there are certain commercial laws, ethical, legal, and political factors that transmit the need to come up with the solutions (Nguyen, et al. 2021).

There are various factors that affect the employees' engagement in the banking sectors as discussed below.

2.15.1 Leadership

This factor was found to be a significant in employees' engagement in the banking sector, namely engagement through leadership behaviour in the study of Kertiriasih et al. (2018) which also suggests that the leaders in today's organisations are having an impact on their employees' engagement which also helps employees to develop. Similarly, Daniëls, Hondeghem and Heystek (2020) suggest that true leadership increases the productivity of work by the employees and also in organisations, while the leaders' behaviour clarifies the objective and goal for the achievement-focused employee. The study of Visuvalingam, Perera and Siaw (2018) shows that there are three factors that increase employees' engagement towards work, both in the private and the public sectors, namely trust, teamwork and true leadership. These factors increase employees' engagement and performance in any organisation.

The study of Al Mehrzi and Singh, (2016) pointed out that leadership behaviour in organisations increases employees' engagement, so having a good leadership strategy increases the performance of the employee and their engagement towards their job in banking or any other organisations. For instance, a leader who communicates with their employees politely and professionally creates a good environment within the organisation. The study of Tims et al. (2011) also shows a positive relationship between transformational leaders and the

employees' engagement levels. The leadership style promotes the opportunities for employees which increases the interest of employees towards their jobs. The study of Ariyani and Hidayati (2018) has also emphasised on the employees' engagement and transformational leadership styles by elaborating that transformational leadership style tends to be impacting positively on employees' engagement. Therefore, it is evident that leadership style positively affects the employees' engagement in the banking sector.

2.15.2 Organisational Culture

The organisational culture is an important factor in employees' engagement towards organisations as it incorporates the values, and standards of a person. A leader's performance and enhanced trust and job satisfaction is also crucial for employees' engagement (Paais, and Pattiruhu, 2020). Soemaryani and Rakhmadini (2013) expressed that "organisational culture" is the aspect that the workers notice, and that this perception produces a blueprint of feelings, value and expectations. The organisational culture includes the working environment of the organisation within the teams. Consequently, workplaces, groups and friendly relations can be seen to be the fundamental influencers of employees' engagement, which highly affects employee performance. Past studies have shown that the organisational culture increases the employee motivation. The study conducted by Gautama et al (2018) also elaborated that employee performance and motivation is influenced by the organisational culture. It has been proved that an organisation culture which is more friendly and cohesive leads to better employee performance and the employees are also more motivated to work in these organisations.

2.15.3 Financial and Non-Financial Rewards

Financial rewards are a key factor for motivating employees to work efficiently towards achieving organisational goals. Financial rewards such as salaries and bonuses, pensions, health benefits and insurance increase the employees' engagement towards their jobs and for that purpose they try to work hard to increase the rewards given to them. Therefore, financial rewards are a key factor for influencing employees' motivation and hence their engagement, in the banking and other sectors (Zaraket and Saber, 2017). According to the study of Uddin and Wijidi (2014), managers suggested that pay is the most influencing factor for employee performance, but the employees argued that pay is not the main motive because if the payment/rewards process is inappropriate, it will demotivate the employees.

Financial rewards are considered to be an important factor for employee behaviour, nevertheless non-financial rewards also play a critical role in motivating employees. The study of Afolabi et al. in 2018 described that career development, working environment and job design along with performance management systems are the non-financial rewards which affect the employees' engagement in the banking sector.

2.15.4 Teamwork and Trust

Trust is also a significant factor that affects employees' engagement in the banking sector. Raheja (2020) describe that trust is the integrity and morality whilst Iddagoda (2020) states that morality is the key factor for the betterment of society. In term of organisations, trust defines the relationship between two or more people, and it comprises three categories within the organisation such as inter-organisational trust, intra-organisational and inter-personal trust. Inter-organisational trust defines how organisations depend on each other, intra-organisational trust describes the relationship between leaders and the employees, and lastly inter-personal trust describes the relationship between employees/teams in an organisation (Khvatova et al., 2016).

Additionally, teamwork is a key component in an organisation which influences employees' engagement. The study of Farr-Wharton et al. (2021), shows that true leadership strategies increase the quality of teamwork, which engage the employees more actively towards achieving organisational goals, and that teamwork has a positive impact on employee behaviour. Therefore, teamwork and trust significantly affect employees' engagement through employee motivation.

2.16 Strategies for Employees' engagement and CSR in the Banking Sector

2.16.1 Training and Development

The banking sector is improving the productivity and performance of its employees by providing the appropriate training for employees' engagement in the banking sector, and it is also an important function of human resource management (HRM). The study of Sitzmann and Weinhardt (2018), shows that the UK banking sector in 2012 spent 164.2 billion dollars in training and development programmes. The study of Sendawula et al. (2018) highlights the role of employees' engagement through training and development in the banking sectors. The results show that not only does training and development programmes significantly increase the employees' engagement in the banking sectors, also that proper training and development programmes engage the employee to improve their abilities and performance within the

banking sector, so the findings were positive. The study of Sendawula et al. (2018) also states that training and development programmes in banks positively increase the employees' performance. The study by Afroz (2018) also supports that these training programmes increase employees' engagement within the banking sector. The study shows that the training and development programmes increase employees' engagement and their motivation and job satisfaction level in the banking sectors. Therefore, training and development programmes in the banking sector increase the employee performance and engagement, which then lead them to achieve organisational goals.

2.16.2 Perception of Fairness

According to Rupp et al. (2018), the perception of fairness affects employees' mental and physical health. While the concept of fairness builds loyalty and a sense of wellbeing in the work, fairness is essential for developing trust since it is a powerful signal for employees to engage more in their work. The study of Gapor and Doctor (2020), also shows that the perception of fairness is critical for the development of psychological safety in employees because fair treatment enhances the employees' engagement.

2.16.3 Rewards Programme and Teamwork

Rewards programmes in the banking sectors are one of the most important strategies for motivating employees towards their work and achieving organisational goals. Rewards programmes engage the employees more actively towards work through motivation. In banking sectors, financial rewards such as salaries and bonuses, pensions, health benefits and insurance increase employees' engagement towards their job and for that purpose the employees tend to work hard to increase their productivity (Levesque et al., 2018).

Teamwork is also a key component in any organisation which helps boost the employees' engagement in any organisations. Teamwork within a fair environment engages the employees more actively for better outcomes. Amongst the many strategies that the banking sectors use to engage their employees, teamwork increases employee productivity and also improves the business performance by minimising the employee workload (Rosa and Hastings, 2018).

2.16.4 Philanthropic strategy

The CSR strategies in banking refer to the approaches that corporations or firms employ to conduct their businesses in a way that is ethical, environmental, philanthropic, and beneficial to community. Development of strategies for CSR is very important since lack of strategic

planning has been identified to be one of the main barriers of CSR implementation. Strategies helps an organisation in identifying their position and planning for the future. The CSR strategies of a business can be described with the help of philanthropic philosophy of the organisation since most banks use the concept of philanthropic efforts in their CSR strategies. It is important that banks of all sizes run their business strategies through philanthropic efforts. This includes charitable and humanitarian efforts which are undertaken by the banking sector to help those in need and to bring peace and wellbeing in the social environment. Similarly, philanthropic efforts play an important part in the banking sector for increasing employees' engagement by including a more humanitarian approach and showing the stakeholders that the organisation has humanitarian values (Taylor and Goodman, 2020). The study of Vekariya (2019), also suggested that philanthropic effort is a major aspect of CSR in the banking sectors to attain competitive advantages.

2.17 Empirical Review

According to the study evaluated by Albdour and Altarawneh (2012) regarding corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement in the banking sector of Jordan, it was stated that there exists a significant relationship between corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement. Employees' engagement is considered essential for corporate social responsibility, and it was analysed in the results of the study that Jordan's banks are less involved in CSR practices and this requires further improvement. It can be stated that if an organisation supports its employees through fulfilling the economic and socio-emotional responsibility, then employees help the organisation through their involvement, which is considered as gratitude on the part of the employees. A study of Glavas (2016) stated that employees' engagement is considered as one of the essential elements in the success of an organisation. It was also mentioned in the study that an increase in corporate social responsibility would help in increasing the engagement of the employees, which means that the employees would be more involved in the activities of the organisation. It further analysed from the results of the study that the organisations that fulfil their CSR are responsible for increasing engagement of the employees because employees participate actively when organisations fulfil their CSRs. A study by Chaudhary (2017) examined the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement and it was stated by the author that corporate social responsibility plays an essential role in employees' engagement. It was also explained by the author that employees in

the organisation pay more attention only when the organisation fulfils its CSR. This can be explained by saying that the organisations are responsible for improving the engagement of the employees.

According to the study evaluated by Gross and Holland (2011) regarding corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement, it was further evident that corporate social responsibility is related to employees' engagement. The author conducted the study by using quantitative research design and the results of the study stated that corporate social responsibility has a significant relationship with employees' engagement. This shows that CSR has an impact on employees' engagement, which can be explained by saying that if the employees are supported by the organisation, then they will engage themselves in the activities of the organisation. It was also analysed in the study that employees will be able to engage more if they have been given importance by the organisation. It can be stated from the literature review of the study that CSR acts as a pathway for the employees in order to find meaning in their work (Rupp et al., 2018). This can be explained by saying that employees feel good when they see that their contribution is for the sake of society, and they are contributing to the greater good. However, it can be stated that when employees feel good about their work then they start participating actively which helps in their engagement and when employees engage themselves in the activities then they help the organisation in achieving its goal.

It is explained by Farrukh et al., 2020 in their study that employees' engagement in the organisation is considered essential which means that it is the responsibility of the organisation to engage its employees by providing different platforms and opportunities for this to occur. It was also stated in the study that CSR leads to the engagement of the employees, which can be elaborated by saying that if the employees consider themselves as a part of the organisation and involve themselves productively, then it can be beneficial for the organisation. Moreover, it was analysed in the study that sharing common goals with the employees such as communicating the CSR to the employees can help in the engagement of employees. It was also stated by the authors that sharing common goals helps in explaining the perception of employees, their feelings and behaviours that is considered beneficial for their organisations. Lu et al. (2020) have demonstrated that CSR acts as a catalyst towards the employee's behaviour and attitudes. Kim et al. (2018) highlighted that CSR impacts employees decide the practices that they will adopt to maintain their behaviour within the company. A research conducted by Tan & Ann (2023) found that subjective norms, attitudes and perceived

behavioural control have a significant impact on the engagement of CSR activities, which eventually affected the behaviour of employees. Hence, the development of the first hypothesis;

H1: CSR has positive and significant effect on employees' planned behaviour

According to the study by Aracil (2019), it was stated that involvement of banks in social causes is responsible for directing the organisations towards social and non-social stakeholders namely society, future generations, protection of the environment and non-governmental organisations. It was also analysed in the study that corporate social responsibility is something that motivates the employees of the organisation so that they participate in the activities of the organisation. Moreover, it was observed by the author in his study that employees in those organisations where corporate social responsibility is the preference are more engaged as compared to the organisations that do not fulfil their CSR. A study by Slack, Corlett and Morris (2015) stated that employees who work in organisations which are concerned more about the environment and run their operations with sustainability in mind are more satisfied in comparison to the employees from organisations that do not support such factors. It has been stated that employees are more interested in organisations that think about the future of the next generations and run their operations accordingly. However, it can be stated that CSR activities of the organisations are considered essential because employees' engagement depends upon it and it can also be stated that CSR activities give directions to organisations.

A study by Nazir and Islam (2020) stated that CSR activities of the organisation affects employees' engagement which means that if the organisation does not fulfil its responsibility, then there are chances that its employees will disengage. It was stated in the study that an organisation created employee friendly policies in order to fulfil its responsibility towards employees so that employees can play their part and contribute to the goals of the organisation productively. It can be stated that the support of the organisation to the employees possesses significance because employees can be engaged through friendly policies. In their study Potdar et al. (2018) stated that organisations that fulfil their CSR have high employees' engagement, which means that employees' retention will also be enhanced. This shows that CSR is directly or indirectly related to the performance and retention of employees. According to Gharleghi et al. (2018) developing a good CSR strategy not only ensures employee retention, but also helps attract employees that have the required set of skills and expertise that can accomplish company goals and objectives (Gharleghi et al., 2018). Hence the development of the second hypothesis;

H2: CSR has positive and significant effect on employees' retention

It was stated by Esmaeelinezhad, Singaravelloo and Boerhannoeddin (2015) that employees' engagement possesses great significance because it is related to the activities of the organisation, which is related to the performance of the organisation. In this study, authors have linked the engagement of employees with the corporate social responsibility of the organisation. Esmaeelinezhad, Singaravelloo and Boerhannoeddin (2015) further stated that CSR could also lead towards customer satisfaction, which can lead towards engagement of the employees. It was stated that employees' engagement could lead towards positive business outcomes, so it is necessary to fulfil the CSR. According to the study by Al Amri, Das and BenAyed (2019) it can be stated that CSR and employees' engagement are found to have relationship with one another because both of these variables have an impact on one another. It can be analysed from the studies that CSR is the approach of an organisation in order to meet the expectations of the stakeholders, which are regarding the social, ethical and environmental concerns. It can be stated that employees' engagement is the emotional connection of the employee with their organisation, which is somehow related to the support the employee received from the organisation. It was analysed from the results of the study that employees' engagement is related to the promotion of the interests of the organisations which means that if the organisations want to improve their performance, then they will have to focus on CSR. CSR is indirectly related to the overall performance of the organisation, which is a result of the engagement of the employees.

A study by Gupta (2017) analysed CSR and employees' engagement within Information Technology Enabled Service (ITES) companies in India. It was stated in the study that the ITES companies are not much engaged in corporate social responsibility, which means that the engagement of the employees is low. This means that the IT sector needs to focus more on its CSR so that the employees can become engaged, because engagement of the employees is related to the overall performance of the sector. However, it can be stated that the employees in the IT sector are not satisfied as compared to the other sectors which focus more on CSR. Moreover, the overall study showed that the relationship of employees' engagement with CSR is of great importance because employees are considered as the significant elements of an organisation and their role plays an essential part in achieving the organisational goals. It is analysed from the results of the study that the IT sector should pay more attention to fulfilling their corporate social responsibility in order to achieve the engagement of the employees. Employees should be a part of CSR so that they can contribute productively towards the

sustainability of the organisations (Yousaf et al., 2016). Therefore, it can be stated that the initiatives related to CSR by the banks is considered beneficial for their success.

In the light of the study conducted by Obeidat (2016) to explore the link between corporate social responsibility, employees' engagement and its impact on organisational performance, the data was collected by using a questionnaire from 350 respondents to understand the relationship between the independent variable corporate social responsibility, mediating variable employees' engagement and dependent variable organisational performance. The data was analysed and evaluated using multiple and regression tables to test the hypotheses. The study found out that employees' engagement in terms of dynamism, dedication and absorption, and both internal and external corporate social responsibility contains a substantial positive link with organisational performance. This finding revealed that in order to improve organisational performance, the management, leaders and decision-makers must endeavour to develop and sustain an effective corporate social responsibility agenda, which will promote employees' engagement in their work, resulting in improved performance and organisational growth.

The above findings were supported by the research study of Alrowwad et al. (2017) that employees are more likely to engage in cooperative behaviours with their colleagues, customers and the organisation when organisations apply best practices in CSR. As a result, CSR encourages communication and employee interactions within the organisation (Zameer et al., 2018). On the other hand, leaders are well aware of the numerous obstacles that affect employees' engagement and organisational performance (Ahmad et al., 2017). Organisations that are able to overcome these obstacles have significant prospects, particularly in terms of business performance (Szegedi, Khan and Lentner, 2020). Dis-engaged employees had shown a negative impact on productivity, growth and organisational revenues (Sinthupundaja et al., 2019). Therefore, it is critical for businesses to cultivate a culture and environment that encourages employees' engagement along with maximum participation, and that they implement strategies in order to achieve maximum organisational performance and productive culture (Slack, Corlett and Morris, 2015).

The academic research on employees' engagement levels in corporate social responsibility is expanding fast and has proved beneficial for organisations. However, researchers and past literature are unable to fully grasp why and how CSR affects individuals or employees. The research conducted by Glavas (2016) fills that gap by examining the link between CSR and employees' engagement. Furthermore, corporate social responsibility is presented as a

mechanism for engaging the workforce in order to tackle the low levels of employees' engagement within the workplace, using engagement theory as a model in which CSR allows employees to contribute more to work, resulting in higher employees' engagement. Structural equation modelling was used to examine data collected from 15,184 employees affiliated with senior professional backgrounds in the United States. The findings revealed that authenticity is the key that mediates the association between CSR and employees' engagement in a positive and meaningful way. The other mediator in this study perceived organisational support through direct or indirect benefits did not mediate the link between the variables. Furthermore, moderated relationships imply that when CSR is not connected with job duties and roles, for instance, corporate volunteering, the association between CSR and employees' engagement is insignificant.

In conclusion, the findings indicate that the more employees engaged in CSR, the more engaged and productive they will be at work. The findings are supported by Soni and Mehta (2020) that employees discover better purpose and values at work is the sole reason for the favourable association between CSR and individual engagement. Although these studies imply that volunteering has a good impact on employees, it has not been thoroughly investigated whether excessive extra-role behaviour can have an unfavourable impact (Mann–Whitney, 2020). Employees are more positively associated with CSR when it is incorporated in their job as supported by the research of Kim et al. (2020). Consequently, when CSR is extracurricular, i.e. extra-role or additional duty, it might have an unfavourable impact over employees' engagement (Soni and Mehta, 2020). Furthermore, extra-role CSR may impose additional effort or pressure on employees having excessive workloads and high expectations placed on them (Mann–Whitney, 2020). Gallardo-Vázquez et al. (2020) discovered that putting excessive pressure on employees to volunteer for external or internal CSR would have negative consequences on organisational performance.

Due to its evolving behaviour and dynamic interaction within the society and stakeholders, corporate social responsibility is considered a very complex topic within the industry of banking (Aras, Aybars and Kutlu, 2010). It is a widely debated phenomenon, although most studies have focused on its relationship and association to financial performance, organisational growth, consumer behaviour, and organisational strategy, and marketing tactics while ignoring the aspect and importance of human resource management (Rupp et al., 2018). Therefore, the research conducted by Gupta and Sharma (2016) aims to highlight the employee's feelings and emotions with regard to engagement towards organisational corporate responsibility. Their

study focuses on the different aspects of CSR and how they relate to employees' engagement and corporate performance. The study concentrates on corporate social responsibility as a significant contributor towards employees' engagement, which has emerged as a viable business strategy. In this research for demonstrating the influence of CSR on employees' engagement and overall performance, a secondary data collection method is used to provide a critical analysis of the literature. The study discovered two types of CSR practices: internal CSR and external CSR. The researchers Gupta and Sharma (2016) argued that the internal CSR component has a greater impact on employees' engagement than the external CSR activities. Engagement is also discovered to be a complex technique for organisational effectiveness (Gallardo-Vázquez et al., 2020). In conclusion the paper developed a positive association and strong link between CSR practices and engagement, as well as CSR and organisational performance. From an academic perspective, the study makes a significant contribution to the understanding of CSR strategy and using it as a business strategy through opening up additional channels of CSR aspects in moulding employees' attitudes and behaviour (Gupta and Sharma, 2016). Furthermore, this research includes a number of mediators that are addressed at the individual level in CSR but are important to investigate in order to understand different mechanisms that influence employees' performance and engagement (Jones et al., 2014). This also has relevant theoretical consequences since both positive and negative impacts on employees are discussed at the macro level.

Another research, conducted by Bravo, Buil, De Chernatony, and Martínez (2017) in the United Kingdom, to investigate the internal corporate social responsibility and its impact on employees' perspective within the banking industry, looks at the effects of five internal CSR practices, including human rights, training and education, work-life balance, health and safety and workplace diversity, on two perspectives of employees' engagement, Job Engagement (JE) and Organisational Engagement (OE). It employs quota and convenience sampling, both of which are non-probability sampling methods. A sample of 336 frontline personnel in the UK banking sector was used to evaluate the suggested approach. The testing of numerous potential internal CSR-employees' engagement relationships found that all of them were meaningful and strongly associated. Furthermore, it demonstrates that CSR techniques are not widely used in the UK banking sector. Out of five dimensions, only one internal CSR factor, work-life balance, was shown to be less adopted than the other four internal CSR dimensions. However, when compared to employee job engagement, the impact of internal CSR practices on organisational engagement was larger. The findings of the research revealed that internal CSR practices might

be a better predictor of employees' organisational engagement than their job engagement. Furthermore, by broadening understanding about the influence of CSR, particularly internal CSR, on employee attitude and behaviour, the study has made major additions to the body of knowledge at both the academic and practical levels. The findings concluded that CSR activities help improve customer trust and employees' engagement within the banking sector. Consumer trust is critical for establishing long-term relationships; however, employee's participation in CSR plays a huge role in enhancing that relationship. Hence, improved productivity and organisational growth.

A research was conducted by Ali, Nasruddin, and Lin (2010) with the aim of exploring the role of leadership in improving employees' trust and participation in the CSR practices within the organisation. The findings of confirmatory factor analysis back up the hypothesis that corporate social responsibility has a direct impact on employees' engagement. In the relationship between internal corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement, the data also show that trust plays a positive mediating effect. The moderator leader-member exchange, on the other hand, had no effect on employees' engagement and participation. The study advises leaders to concentrate on increasing employee trust in order to promote participation in the firm's activities and escalate organisational growth, as well as to experiment with novel ways of communicating issues to employees and tackling them through human resource interventions and leader-member exchange channels (Aras, Aybars and Kutlu, 2010). The study contributes to developing strong participation and a level of trust within the employees to promote CSR practices and organisational growth. Finally, CSR will boost employees' attitudes toward working in the organisation, resulting in higher levels of involvement in their everyday tasks.

Increase in employee satisfaction and loyalty will ultimately boost employee motivation (Slack, Corlett and Morris, 2015).

This leads to the development of the third hypothesis;

H3: There is a significant effect of CSR on employees' engagement

2.18 Hypothesis summary

H0: CSR has a positive and insignificant effect on employees' planned behaviour

H1: CSR has positive and significant effect on employees' planned behaviour

H0: CSR has positive and insignificant effect on employees' retention

H2: CSR has positive and significant effect on employees' retention

H0: There is no significant effect of CSR on employees' engagement

H3: There is a significant effect of CSR on employees' engagement

Three hypotheses were generated in this literature review which shows the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement. The first hypothesis of this study is that CSR has a positive and significant impact on employees' planned behaviour, similarly, the null hypothesis for this statement is that CSR has a positive and insignificant impact on employees' planned behaviour. The results of this study imply that the CSR strategies increase the plans of the employees' planned behaviour towards the job performance, and hence the organisation has to shape the positive behaviour of the employees by using strong practices of CSR.

The second hypothesis in this study shows that CSR has a positive and significant impact on employees' retention while the null hypothesis is that CSR has a positive and insignificant impact on employees' retention. The third hypothesis in this study shows that CSR has a significant impact on employees' engagement. Similarly, the null hypothesis shows that CSR has no significant impact on employees' engagement. Therefore, the majority of the past research papers in this study showed that CSR has positive impact on employees' planned behaviour and also on employees' retention and employees' engagement.

2.19 Conceptual Framework

This study elaborates the relationship between corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement in the banking sector. Figure 4 demonstrated the conceptual framework of this study. Here, the independent variable is corporate social responsibility whilst employees' engagement, employees' retention and employees' planned behaviour are the dependent variables. The notion of corporate social responsibility (CSR) is not an innovative concept which can be used in the banking industry, but in the present economic state of affairs it has turned out to be the paramount way out for incorporating moral ideologies in activities taking place within the banking sector (Ionescu et al., 2018). With the implementation of corporate social responsibility, the current experiences and moral/ethical values in the banking sector

indicates to the view that the corporate social responsibility in respect of bank's morals and beliefs seem a suitable promotion tool for community statements and are not combined into strategies of different banks (Gangi, Mustilli, and Varrone, 2018).

Figure 4: Conceptual Framework (Author's own)

It is detected in several studies that corporate social responsibility affects the performance in banks. It is indicated that CSR actions have recorded improvement in the better-quality of products connected to the requirements of the social order and take appropriate actions in appealing to new talents and retaining current employees. Moreover, it identifies employees' capability and their motivation which indicates to better inventiveness and modernisation. Furthermore, it highlights the different campaigns, and corporate social responsibility helps in providing better promoting opportunity to the banks among competitions. Apart from this, it helps to build a virtuous association with the stakeholders (such as the public)

2.20 Theoretical Framework

2.20.1 Stakeholder Theory of CSR

In organisations, corporate social responsibility (CSR) is integrated, which involves social and environmental concerns in the business operation with stakeholders (Gazzola, and Colombo, 2014). The stakeholder theory of CSR refers to the essence of business, which primarily lies in establishing relationships or creating value for stakeholders (Brown, and Forster, 2013). This theory presents the view of capitalism, which focuses on the interconnected relationships between an organisation and its prospective consumers, traders, workers, stockholders, groups, and others who have a stake in the company. The theory claims that a business should generate value for all investors, not just shareholders (Asante Boadi et al., 2020).

Edward Freeman initially described the stakeholder theory in 1984 in his book, *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*, which groups the stakeholders of a company and discusses how businesses can give due regard to their stakeholders (stakeholdertheory.org, 2018). The theory suggests that for a business to succeed, it must create value for its stakeholders such as, the employees, customers, shareholders, suppliers, community, and anyone who is linked to the business. When it comes to CSR and the stakeholder theory, some scholars believe that one theory is a part of the other theory, while some believe that the two theories share competing views (Freeman & Dmytriiev, 2017). According to Freeman and several other scholars, the stakeholder theory represents everything that CSR does since both these concepts emphasise the importance of conducting business operations considering the benefits of the larger society (Gaonkar & Chetty , 2020). Whilst the stakeholder theory focuses on creating value and relationship between an organisation and its stakeholders, CSR highlights the importance of benefitting the wider society through these business operations (Freeman & Dmytriiev, 2017).

Employees are one of the key stakeholders of a company and are vital for company CSR initiatives. Without the employees' involvement and their expertise, it would not be possible for businesses to achieve their CSR goals (Gaonkar & Chetty , 2020). There exists an interrelationship between an organisation and its employees', and the responsibilities of the company and employees are multi-directional (Freeman & Dmytriiev, 2017). The stakeholder theory focuses on the responsibilities of the company towards the employees as well as the responsibility of the employees towards the company. When it comes to CSR practices towards employees, businesses mostly emphasise on ethical working practices and environmental

efforts. The stakeholder theory assists the company and its employees' by means of employee satisfaction, enhanced retention rates and improved productivity since according to the theory, the role of a business is to create value to its stakeholder which includes employees (stakeholdertheory.org, 2018). Therefore, the stakeholder theory of CSR is a framework that is able to create an association between CSR and the employees' and help identify their CSR needs and expectations.

Furthermore, the theory interprets that the leaders in the banks should comprehend and account for all the stakeholders of the organisation (Mainardes, Alves and Raposo, 2011). The constituencies, which affect the activities of corporate social responsibility, are impacted by the operational activities in an organisation. In addition to this, according to the theory corporate social responsibility (CSR) potentially affects stakeholders such as employees in an organisation (Gross, and Holland, 2011). For instance, the organisation actively engaging in CSR practices would make the employees also take part in the activities. Hence, the organisations with sustainability plans have higher levels of employee morale and loyalty. Moreover, the stakeholder theory of CSR demonstrates that the employees or individuals working in the bank are required to rethink their standardised approaches to management (Asante Boadi et al., 2020). It advocates the leaders shifting the prime concentration of their work away from the short-term profits to long-term profits or financial success.

2.20.2 Triple Bottom Line Theory

The triple bottom line theory suggests that businesses should be committed to measuring their contribution or social and environmental influence along with their monetary or financial performance rather than merely concentrating on generating profits or revenues (Žak, 2015). As per the theory, this scenario demonstrates that organisational goals or the objectives of the bank are essential for making the business low risk for investors, hence increasing the longevity and sustainability of the bank. It eventually enhances the reputation or brand image of the bank in the market (Uwuigbe et al., 2018). The elements of the theory include the social, environmental, and financial bottom lines along with the measures, which are people, resources, and profit (Tate and Bals, 2018). According to this theory, there is a robust relationship between corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement. This theory indicates that the social and environment bottom lines helps the organisation in developing their reputation in the community and hence their employees are more engaged too. The engagement of employees in the organisation or banking industry fully mediates the relationship between CSR and organisational performance in a substantial way.

Therefore, the perception of corporate social responsibility shapes the attitudes and behaviours of employees or workers within the company (Kim et al., 2017). Moreover, in the banks that are implementing the best practices in corporate social responsibility, the workers or leaders in the business are more likely to engage in cooperative attitudes and behaviours to their coworkers and the organisation. Additionally, it takes employees' engagement to the next level. For instance, an employee would go the extra mile to assist a member of the team regarding any complex task (Kim et al., 2017). In the same way, corporate social responsibility encourages higher-quality and closer relationships amongst employees in the organisation.

2.20.3 Social Exchange Theory

Within the study of Cook et al. (2013), it has been stated that social exchange theory (SET) helps in highlighting the planned social behaviour that usually results from the exchange process. The authors further stated that while working for an organisation, if employees feel a high level of satisfaction (or happiness), they become more motivated to provide support to their organisations as a mutual exchange. Shiau and Luo (2012) also contended that employees can even display voluntary behaviour in order to respond towards the positive treatment received from their companies. An example of this can be taken from the research of Hansen et al. (2016), who stated that when companies engage in CSR activities, they are able to develop and foster an ethical climate. The authors further argued that in such ethical climates, workers often become motivated to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviours. These behaviours are generally displayed by the employees when they are faced with questionable moral behaviours of their higher-ups. Cropanzano et al. (2017) have mentioned in their article that SET typically provides a more robust theoretical rationale in comparison to SIT in order to describe the concept of employees' engagement.

Under any given organisation, employees' engagement can be referred to as a two-way relationship between the employees and employers of the company. In other words, it can also be stated that employees usually repay their companies through their engagement level. This engagement level can be described as the amount of physical, emotional, and cognitive resources that employees are ready to devote while performing their job duties. However, this devotion is usually dependent on the socio-emotional, as well as economic resources that employees attain from their organisations (Li, 2015).

In the research of Drollinger (2010), it has been postulated that philanthropic donations often impact the dynamics of social exchange for both the recipients of the donations, as well as for

the donor's own social group. The author further argued that people usually make charitable donations not to attain their recipients' gratitude, but to earn their peers' approval who take part under the philanthropic campaign. Drollinger (2010) also stated that even though for social approval, donations can be exchanged by suppliers and recipients, it is not necessary that the donations' recipients and suppliers of the approval would have high similarity.

Nevertheless, the clarification of the relationship that suppliers and recipients have still requires an in-depth analysis of the complex structure which is observed under indirect exchange (Barman, 2017). By considering these findings on SET, it can be stated that when CSR initiatives adequately meet employees' expectations, they are likely to experience positive behaviour and attitude. This, in turn, encourages employees to demonstrate more enthusiastic behaviour in the form of employees' engagement, organisation citizenship behaviour, as well as other desirable behaviours of the company.

2.20.4 Motivation-Hygiene Theory

Employees engagement is an important aspect for business success as it leads to higher productivity. As employees' needs and preferences are different from one to another, organisations need to customise their strategies in accordance with the needs of their workforce. To do so, businesses need to identify what satisfies, dissatisfies motivates and engages their employees. Also known as the two-factor motivation theory, the motivation-hygiene theory by Fredrick Herzberg highlights the different, mutually exclusive factors that either causes an employee to be satisfied or dissatisfied (Tan, and Waheed, 2011). According to Herzberg and his tested hypothesis, the factors that motivated employees were different from factors that caused them to be dissatisfied. The theory identified two types of factors; motivators – which are necessary to accelerate employee satisfaction and motivation such as career development, growth, recognition, responsibilities, and a job that is meaningful to them; Hygiene factors – that includes salary, security, policies & leadership and working conditions which if not met, could lead to employee dissatisfaction. Motivators are important as they fulfil the employee needs and expectations which then encourages employees to put in increased effort towards achieving business goals (Tan, and Waheed, 2011). Chiat and Panatik (2019) states that, Hygiene factors determine the level of satisfaction of employees related to their job, which strongly influences the retention of employees at the workplace. However, according to Herzberg, Hygiene factors do not lead to satisfaction but are fundamental to avoid dissatisfaction within an employee (Tan, and Waheed, 2011). The implementation of these activities increases the satisfaction of employees, the loyalty of customers, and the creativity

within the organisational boundaries; therefore, it eventually enhances the public image (Diers-Lawson et al., 2020).

According to the Herzberg's theory, both motivators and hygiene factors influence employee's engagement. While the motivators impact the employees' values, intellectual and creative capabilities that helps them feel more connected and engaged to their roles, the hygiene factors influence the psychological and emotional welfare of the employees (Tan, and Waheed, 2011). Hygiene factors such as a salary and benefits are foundation for employees' engagement, which would ensure that employees are not dissatisfied at work. However, motivators are crucial for employees' engagement as these factors fulfil the employees' intrinsic needs and values (LinkedIn, 2023). This relationship also helps explain the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement. When employees' values match with CSR, when employees are involved with CSR where they are given autonomy and opportunities, and when employees are recognised for their CSR efforts, it improves their sense of belongingness to the organisation and find meaning in their roles as it align with their value and intrinsic needs. These motivators eventually lead to employee satisfaction and employees' engagement. The activities of corporate social responsibility also contribute to the productivity, creativity, and commitment of employees (Hossen et al., 2020). Research also suggests that CSR is bivalent in nature which not only impacts as a motivator, but also as a hygiene factor (Lacey, et al., 2015). Therefore, it is suggested that lack of CSR initiatives within an organisation, could lead to employee dissatisfaction.

2.20.5 Kahn's Engagement Theory

Kahn's engagement theory concerns individuals or employees who make decisions related to their real and personal selves, which they express and reveal while performing their work or task (Fletcher, and Robinson, 2013). According to this theory, the engagement of employees involves continuous dialogues and procedures related to the designing and altering of their roles, tasks, and working relationships. As per the theory, there are three principle dimensions in employees' engagement; physical, cognitive, and emotional (Pham-Thai et al., 2018). The leaders or the employees working at a senior leadership position in the banking sector specifically in the United Kingdom ensure that all the members in a team are completely engaged in the activities related to corporate social responsibility. The theory demonstrates that the banks in the banking industry of the UK are required to make sure that all the employees and team members of the company understand the importance of their specific role in the

organisation. It works as an appreciation for fulfilling a prime purpose of making a contribution, which motivates the employees or individuals in an organisation to commit themselves completely to their specialised role (Chaudhary, 2019). The activities of corporate social responsibility may also include charitable and sustainability activities. The organisation conducts programmes and carries out the practices and operations in order to ensure employees' engagement.

2.20.6 Theory of Planned Behaviour

Evolving from the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), the Theory of Planned behaviour (TPB) was proposed by Ajzen, which predicts an individual's intention to undertake a specific behaviour amongst two predictors that are the subjective norms and the behavioural conduct towards the behaviour. The basis of both models is that individuals, based on the information available to them, make logical and reasoned decisions that align with their values. However, the reasoned actioned theory does not consider the factors in which the individual's behaviour is not fully under the person's control (Steinmetz et al, 2016). Therefore, perceived behavioural control was added as characteristic to the model, which led to the model to be renamed as the Theory of Planned behaviour. The theory states that the intention of an individual to practice behaviour is affected by and individual attitude towards the intentions related to behaviour as well as by the behavioural control and subjective norm.

According to the study conducted by Truong et al. (2022), the theory believes that not only is the behaviour of an individual predicted by his intentions, which is the direct behaviour antecedent; but also that the stronger the individual's intentions are, the more clearly that they will express that behaviour. Moreover, an individual's intention is a practice that decides the behaviour that is shown (Archimi et al, 2018). According to Gao and He (2017), an individual's behavioural intention is tightly linked with its predictors, that is the individual attitude towards the intentions related to behaviour, as well as by the behavioural control and subjective norms that are related with the constructs of a belief, known as control beliefs, normative beliefs and behavioural beliefs. Archimi et al. (2018) highlight that the antecedent beliefs show that the capabilities, perception, and thoughts of a person in order to carry out a specific behaviour as well as the importance of the provided result, before getting engaged with the behaviour. Thus, to analyse the perceived behavioural control, subjective norms, and attitude of a person, is significant to create the antecedent of such constructs. This theory also suggests that rational choices control the behaviours and choices of people. Therefore, as a person is capable of evaluating his beliefs, he tends to explore a specific result (Chowdhury et al., 2021). Every

result is assessed to determine whether the individual's behaviour will lead to the result in question. Lu et al. (2020) state that before a person determines to practice a certain type of behaviour, s/he tends to assess the costs and advantages that is going to be a result of the said behaviour.

Therefore, it is important to highlight that in this current research which investigates the CSR activities' impact on employees' engagement, it can be said that employees' engagement could also be affected by the individual's attitudes, perceived behavioural control, and subjective norms depending on employees' main beliefs (Ong et al., 2020). The behavioural constructs will be applied to employees which will help identify the interrelationship between employees' planned behaviour and CSR that will eventually lead the engagement of the employees.

2.20.7 Social Identity Theory

Social identity theory (SIT) can be considered as an integrative theory that helps in explaining the perception of psychological basis related to intergroup discrimination (Farooq et al., 2014). In other words, this theory assesses both the sociological, as well as psychological aspects of behaviours that are observed in the members of a given workgroup. Albasu and Nyameh (2017) stated in their article that SIT typically studies the effect of group distinctiveness, social categorisation, and perceptions of employees, including their behaviours and attitudes towards CSR campaigns.

Social identification, according to SIT, usually corresponds to the psychological procedures that individuals use in order to categorise themselves into different social groups of references. Examples of these categorisations can include organisation, nation, religious or political affiliations, etc. These categorisations are made by individuals to reinforce their overall concept of self and self-esteem (Park and Levy, 2014).

In their article, Mory, Wirtz and Göttel (2017) postulated that employees can accomplish positive self-esteem if they are able to experience an in-group identity, which in turn, assists them to differentiate themselves from out-group members. Thus, it can be stated that with its underlying procedures associated with self-enhancement, SIT can be considered as an effective framework for describing the impact of CSR initiatives on the planned attitudes and behaviours of employees. This can also be validated from the article by Kim et al. (2010) who also acknowledged that when employees see that their companies are working to provide benefit to

society (in the form of any CSR initiative), which as a result also enhances the image of their companies in the external society, it significantly improves the satisfaction of the employees with their organisations. This also increases the commitment of the employees with their companies since it enables them to enhance their pride and self-esteem.

Therefore, it can be inferred that SIT offers a rational explanation related to describing the relationship that exists between positive attitude and planned behaviour of employees with CSR initiatives that are conducted by their companies. Nevertheless, D'Aprile and Mannarini (2012) argued in their study that SIT does not integrate the concepts of mutual obligations, expectations, and reciprocity that are often required to comprehend how behaviours and attitudes are improved by the identification of employees with their companies (including their CSR activities) that helps organisations in attaining desirable behavioural outcomes from their employees. For this purpose, social exchange theory (SET) can help in providing a better theoretical comprehension of this relationship.

2.21 Chapter Summary

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is understood as the method or paradigm of encouraging social obligation in business activities. The consideration of CSR in the organisation contributes to the creation of successful and dynamic relationships with stakeholders, employees, service users, and other related businesses operating within the industry. This current study provided a detailed literature on the different kinds of CSR and its significance, the concept of employees' engagement along with the influence of CSR employees' planned behaviour patterns, as well as the impact of CSR on employees' retention. Theoretical and conceptual frameworks for explaining the importance of CSR in the banking sector is provided in order to better understand the association between CSR and employee engagement in the UK banking sector. Corporate social responsibility obliges businesses to respond to additional activities within their firm rather than just profit maximisation. Corporate social responsibility refers to the values, principles, and outcomes of corporations' relations between individuals, institutions, associations, and communities as a result of their conscious actions toward stakeholders. It also concluded that Employees' engagement has a direct impact on a company's productivity. Employee engagement and participation in their roles are core competencies for firms because they contribute to greater performance, productivity, and lower levels of turnover and absenteeism. Employee engagement can be achieved through effective collaboration between corporate and employees in order to boost output and offer high-quality services to

customers. An engaged employee perform well and is totally motivated to work for the benefits of the company.

It is recognised that corporate social responsibility helps to develop a sustainable progress which will result in trust amongst consumers and banks. According to the past studies, the literature review chapter concluded that CSR efforts also allows companies to make their policies and approaches to benefit of society in terms of job creation, reducing Greenhouse gas and ecological footprint on the environment as a sustainable performance initiative, and emphasising employee health and well-being over profit and benefits.

The chapter summarises that there is a significant impact of corporate social responsibility on employees' planned behaviour, employees' engagement and employees' retention. In the financial industry, corporate social responsibility motivates banks to perform exceptionally well in their operations, maintain transparency, promote active services and revenue generation. It can further be concluded that executives must have a more in-depth understanding of critical issues related to corporate social responsibility and consistent communication is vital for the success of CSR actions. The concept of corporate social responsibility aids in increasing client trust in banks. It also encourages corporations to participate in the well-being of various communities, local infrastructures, development initiatives, and environmental decisions. It has also been suggested that CSR initiatives have a favourable impact on employee behaviour by fostering positive wellbeing in them. As a result, CSR contributes to the development of corporate citizenship behaviour among stakeholders, especially employees. It can be argued that employees' involvement with CSR will improve their motivation, loyalty and participation towards the work which will eventually create opportunities and improve the organisations' image. It is believed that motivating employees to participate in such activities will help the bank in introducing new and creative ideas for CSR, hence, increasing employee engagement by involving them in decision-making and policy creation.

In the light of the literature, research has provided several ways for bank to participate in corporate social responsibility. It has indicated that banks need to practice openness, autonomy, transparency, protect client rights, and collaborate with social organisations by offering funds and charity to bring about positive impact to the community. Various measures and strategies should be followed by banks including training and development, improved rewards programme and promote teamwork. The study concludes that through training and development in the banking sector, it will not only increases employee engagement, but ensure

that their skills and abilities are improved in order to align individual goals with organisational objectives. In addition, in the financial sector, rewards programme and efficient compensation management is defined as one of the most essential tactics for motivating employees, improving teamwork and participation in attaining organisational goals. Research has proved that Employees are more likely to feel involved and recognised as a result of reward programmes. In a similar manner, charitable activities i.e. donation and environmental projects in the banking sector play an essential role in promoting employee retention by incorporating a more humanitarian approach. Hence, it can be stated that past research has demonstrated that there is positive relationship between employee retention and CSR activities.

The literature review chapter has further discussed factors that influence Employee engagement in the financial sector in the United Kingdom. It stated that internal and external factors influence business activities and operations. The chapter concludes that trust, teamwork, and authentic leadership are three qualities that promote employees' engagement at work in both public and private sectors. These elements boost employee engagement and performance while other factors such as organisational culture, financial and non-financial rewards, and organisational ethics also plays an important role in influencing CSR activities and employee retention in the banking sector.

This chapter evaluates the view that firms focus on their corporate social responsibility practices as they can increase profitability by improving employees' engagement, loyalty and risk management through corporate social responsibility policies. Consequently, this research study outlines an investigation that aims, primarily, to examine the adoption of practices of corporate social responsibility within the banking sector in the UK. The corporate social responsibility has been indicated to influence on the society and its citizens and also benefits the organisations as well. This research paper is also aimed to provide recommendations to the banks on how they can engage in corporate social responsibility practices efficiently so that CSR can influence on individual behaviour. Moreover, the dimensions of corporate social responsibility also covered in this study which are categorised into nine mechanisms in the banking sector and are typically conveyed in companies' annual reports and accounts. Employees in a bank or any firm can also be impacted by the corporate social responsibility initiatives or programmes that are conducted by their organisations which can affect their attitudes and behaviours differently. With regards to the relationship between corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement in the UK banking sector, it can be said that more research needs to be conducted in this topic area.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The following chapter presents the methodology of this study. The procedure of research methodology is used to design, process, identify, and examine information about a particular study topic. It pursues to inform why a research has been conducted, how the problems regarding research have been defined, how research information has been collected, which research method has been applied, and which technique of research has been implemented. Research methodology gives a structure about a research that a researcher performs by using appropriate design, procedures and the objectives of the research (Goddard and Melville 2004). This chapter is divided into eight parts comprising research philosophy, approach, design, investigation types, data collection, data analysis method, ethical guidelines and limitations of the study. Saunders et al. (2007) presented the research onion model in their book entitled *Research Methods for Business Students*. The aim of this model is to define the stages of writing a dissertation, which supports the researcher in further elaborating and defining the methodology in terms of tools, techniques and approaches. The onion framework in research provides the relevant approaches which contain experimental research, action research, surveys, interviews, or a systematic literature review, or case study research (Sahay, 2016).

The research in general can be defined as a systematic method or process that aims to gain knowledge about a phenomenon through collection and analysis of data and information. Within the context of business research, the purpose is to analyse a business phenomenon and gain useful knowledge to aid business decision making and managerial problem solving (Bryman and Bell, 2011). In the current study, the aim of research is to investigate the phenomenon of how CSR impacts employees' engagement. In social research, there is the research onion framework and there is also the honeycomb framework to design and execute research systematically. The honeycomb framework has six components (Haydam and Steenkamp, 2020). To make sure that this research is conducted systematically, the researcher has chosen to use the honeycomb methodological framework (see figure below). The honeycomb framework is composed of six stages of business research process that can be used to conduct an examination of a business phenomenon systematically to gain knowledge that can aid decision making. The main components in honeycomb methodology are summarised

in the following diagram. Each of these stages are then discussed separately in following sections:

Figure 5: Honeycomb methodological framework

Source: Wilson (2014, p.8)

According to Wilson (2014), the honeycomb provides two important benefits as compared to the top layered model, a) it is a non-linear method to explain research design and b) it indicates links between various elements of research.

3.2 Section A: Methodology Theory

3.2.1 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy is a belief about the development of knowledge. It deals with the assumption about problems and how the research problem is viewed by the researcher. According to Saunders et al. (2015), the research philosophy demonstrates the concept that supports the researcher in terms of gathering, analysing and interpreting the data. Research philosophy is very significant to recognise the methods that are used to conduct the considerate investigation of the research. There are several types of philosophies that are involved in the research; positivism, realism, interpretivism and pragmatism.

The main purpose of any research project is to gain knowledge about the researched phenomenon. In research community the epistemological philosophical position refers to the beliefs of researchers regarding the acceptability of knowledge based on choice of whether to use methods and ethos of natural sciences or not. In this aspect, two opposite positions exist in social sciences. The first is the positivism epistemological school, the proponents of which posit that acceptability of knowledge gained can only be established if methods and ethos of natural sciences have been applied in the research project and examined the phenomenon under consideration objectively. The underlying value in positivism epistemology is that the social phenomenon can be quantified and analysed independently from social factors.

As a result, researchers following positivist philosophy typically adopt a deductive approach and use quantitative methods in the research process (Wilson, 2014). In contrast, there is the interpretivism school of thought in research epistemology. According to interpretivists, methods and ethos of natural sciences should be avoided because the subject matter in a social phenomenon differs from its counterpart in natural phenomenon. Therefore, interpretivist posit that acceptable knowledge is acquired by having a separate research strategy without quantifying the social phenomenon. The research process is entirely subjective and is based on qualitative methods (Myers, 2013). Figure 6 below provides a brief description of different types of epistemologies and compares positivism with interpretivism:

Figure 6: Types of Epistemologies and comparison of Positivism and Interpretivism Source: Wilson (2014)

Moreover, there is an additional philosophy that leads to the combination of positivism and interpretivism which is referred to as pragmatism. Similarly, Simpson (2018) indicated that

pragmatism can combine both positivist and interpretivism in a single research as per the nature of the study. It can lead to the adoption of mixed or multiple methods such as the integration of both qualitative and quantitative data. The philosophy involves the critical assessment of the findings that are obtained from one research method and further comparing the results with another research method for improving the reliability and validity of the results.

It is to be noted that research philosophy provides a way of thinking and evaluation of the collected data to the researchers through which they produce results and construct conclusions. For instance, the use of interpretivism philosophy enables the researchers to evaluate the collected data, more specifically the qualitative data in subjective manners (Wilson, 2014). It allows the researchers to use their intellect and personal understanding of the topic and comprehend the results as per their own understanding. Interpretivism is effective for the secondary and qualitative data evaluation. However, the philosophy of positivism is effective for the evaluation and comprehension of the quantitative data because it supports the objective evaluation of the data for the statistical and logical explanation of the results (Myers, 2013).

3.2.2 Research Approach

The research approach is a process that covers the wide-ranging steps to complete processes of collection, analysis, and then interpretation of data. Research approach is distributed into two different types: data collection and data analysis approach. Data collection approach is subdivided into quantitative and qualitative approach. Quantitative approach is known as a systematic examination of phenomena through collecting numerical data and performing mathematical, statistical or computational methods. Data collected for quantitative research is from online polls, questionnaires, and surveys. Qualitative approach is related with social constructivist pattern. Qualitative approach is about exposing, or analysing deeper significance of human behaviour, for example, conflicting behaviours, practice and feelings. Data could be collected for qualitative research or study with the help of literature, in-depth interviews, and diary entries (Alase 2017).

Research approach is broadly described as the way in which the researcher presents arguments while examining phenomenon. There is a range of social research approaches developed and applied in social research community of which the most commonly used and basic approaches are inductive approach and deductive approach (Reason and Bradbury, 2013). The presentation

of argument in inductive approach starts with collecting and recording information from specific circumstances. The researchers then move on to developing patterns and commonalities in the observations.

Once the patterns are identified the researcher goes on to develop a theory that can be used to explain and elaborate the same phenomenon in all circumstances and settings. In other words, the general purpose of inductive approach is conceptualisation of general theories (Wilson, 2014). There is sharp contrast in deductive approach with respect to inductive reasoning-based research process. The researchers using deductive reasoning aim to test already developed and established theories and then test them to explain the research phenomenon focusing on specific target settings. The researchers first identify a theory and then develop tentative hypotheses assuming that the theory is applicable. The next step is to test the hypotheses and conclude whether the target settings follow the general theory or not (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

3.2.3 Research Strategy

Research strategy can be broadly defined as the choice of type and nature of data to be utilised in the research process. There are three main types of research strategies (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2008). The first is the quantitative research strategy, of which the distinguishing feature is the requirement to execute research process using quantitative data only. Quantitative data typically exists as numbers, digits, and ratings, among others. In any type of research, research design define the research outline that is chosen by the researcher to carry out the research in the way of adopted research design. Research designs are characterised into three different types; i.e. qualitative, quantitative and a mixed study research design. Quantitative research is known as a study in which data or information is represented numerically. Quantitative research is used to examine causal relationships, make expectations, and simplify outcomes to wider populations. Qualitative Research is known as a study based on the collection and investigation of non-numeric data (Dannels, 2018).

The commonly acknowledged benefit of quantitative strategy is that it derives objective results and hence enhances reliability and validity in the results of investigation. However, quantitative research strategy is often critiqued because it lacks the ability to collect rich and detailed data and observations. Quantitative strategy cannot be used to explore feelings, perceptions, experiences, and other subjective aspects of social phenomena. In quantitative strategy the

essential requirement is to operationalise the research phenomenon (Ng and Coakes, 2013). On the other hand, there is qualitative strategy, the distinguishing feature of which is that the entire research process is completed using qualitative data only. Qualitative data can be collected in various forms which include text, speech, conversation, pictures, etc.

The qualitative strategy overcomes the weakness or inherent limitation in the quantitative strategy however, it is not free of inherent limitation. Since qualitative data is subjective, hence a common criticism of this strategy is the inherent vulnerability to personal bias of participants affecting research reliability and validity. Therefore, the qualitative strategy manifests low level of reliability and validity in comparison to quantitative strategy (Bell and Bryman 2011). In order to enhance reliability and validity of results, social researchers may choose to conduct a hybrid of quantitative and qualitative strategies called the mixed method or multimethod strategy. The essential requirement of mixed method is to collect both qualitative and quantitative data and obtain research results through triangulation. Although the mixed method eliminates individual limitations weaknesses in both mono-methods as it uses multi-method, but the time, cost and resources requirements of mixed strategy are high and it is not feasible for small scale researchers (Bryman, 2012).

3.2.4 Research Design

Research design in broad view is described as the choice of the researcher regarding the time horizon. There are various types of designs, for example case study, cross-sectional design, longitudinal design, archival, etc. Cross-sectional design is the one in which the research process identifies a sample of target population and data collection process is based on a specific point in time. The primary benefit of cross-sectional design is that it is simpler and cost and time efficient as compared to other designs (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). Longitudinal design is where the data collection process spans over a longer time period and may involve multiple data collection processes. The researcher must collect larger amount of data multiple times over the selected period. Longitudinal design as compared to cross sectional requires more time but it provides higher reliability and validity in the results of the project (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010).

3.2.5 Sampling Strategy

Sampling can be defined as the process in which the researcher recruits a sub-set of target population. The sample is then used in the research process and the results achieved from the sample can be applied and generalised to the entire target population (Reason and Bradbury, 2013). The sample is a population subset through which researchers choose the participants in their research. Sampling is said to handpick a selection of the population in a specific study area, which will represent the entire population. A strategy is a plan that researchers set up to make sure that the sample they use in their research study represents the populace from which they drew their sample (Landreneau and Creek, 2009). As an introduction, terms related with sampling are sampling frame, population, inclusion criteria, eligibility criteria, exclusion criteria, sampling designs, representativeness, sampling bias, sampling error, and effect size. There are various types of sampling methods such as accidental, convenience, snowball, purposive sampling, simple random sampling, cluster sampling, and quota sample. The terms of sampling which used by the researchers sometimes overlap and it will help any researcher to become familiar with the above terms of sampling. Sampling strategies can be categorised as probability and non-probability sampling. In probability sampling processes, the researcher must make sure that there are equal probability/chances for all members of the target population to participate in the research and be recruited in the sample. However, the researcher must have access to all members or the entire target population. In contrast, there are non-probability sampling processes in which the equal probability condition is relieved, however, the nonprobability sampling techniques are considered to be biased and compromise the overall validity and reliability of research results (Hennink et al., 2010). There are four different main methods of probability sampling; simple random, stratified random, cluster, and systematic (Sharma, 2017). *Non-probability sampling*- In this type of sampling, the elements are selected by non-random methods to make up the sample. There are three different main methods of nonprobability sampling; convenience, quota, and purposive (Etikan and Bala, 2017).

3.2.6 Data Collection

Data collection refers to the tools or instruments using which a researcher accesses the sample members and collects data and information from the target population. The choice of data collection methods must be taken in accordance with the research strategy decision because

there are different methods of data collection for different strategies. In addition, data collection is also categorised based on secondary and primary sources of data (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011).

The secondary data is defined as those data and information that are obtained from past studies and literature. Typical sources of secondary data include academic publications (journal articles, books, university theses/dissertations, etc.), business publications (annual reports, special reports etc.), government publications (public statistics, economic data), and publications from international and non-governmental organisations (such IMF, World Bank, etc.) (Pickard, 2013). The comparative advantage of secondary data over primary data is that the former provides better efficiency in terms of time consumption. Using the internet and digital sources of information researchers accumulate large amount of secondary data in a faster and cost-efficient manner. However, secondary data does not provide fresh and new insights into the research phenomenon and is also vulnerable to sources' bias (Wilson, 2014).

Primary data is defined as the data and information that is directly collected from the target population or sample. The comparative advantage of primary data over secondary data is that it provides new and fresh insights into the relevant research phenomenon. Therefore, the researchers are able to gain creative and new ideas from primary data and add to the literature (Levy and Lemeshow, 2013). Therefore, primary data-based research process is highly valuable for research literature but the comparative disadvantage of primary data as compared to secondary data is that the former is more time consuming and expensive than the latter (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015).

One of the main aspects of questionnaire-based studies is the design of a questionnaire survey. There are two types of questionnaire designs. The first is the standard questionnaires and the second is the self-administered questionnaire. Standard questionnaires (such as SERVQUAL questionnaires) offer high reliability because they are well-tested in past studies. However, they cannot be used in every study due to differences in scope and target settings (Wilson, 2014). The self-administered questionnaires are those that are developed by researchers specifically for their study and accommodate all unique needs of the research process and integrate into the research scope and objectives (Myers, 2013).

3.2.7 Data Analysis

Data analysis refers to processing and manipulating raw data to derive meaningful results that are the bases of conclusions for the research. The selection of techniques for data analysis is based on data collection instrument as the analyses of quantitative data are different from qualitative data. There are several types of techniques used in investigating the qualitative data analysis where the techniques are dependent upon the approach from which the data is gathered. For instance, the qualitative primary data collected through interviews are commonly examined through thematic analysis or NVivo which supports in identifying the relevant themes that supports in addressing the objective and research questions. The secondary qualitative data on the other hand is examined through the content analysis where themes are developed through critically reviewing the journals, articles, news and other secondary sources. As for quantitative approach, it is mainly conducted through statistical techniques for achieving the relevant findings. The primary benefit of statistical techniques as data collection process is that they provide results using graphs and tables that are easy to read and interpret (Levy and Lemeshow, 2013).

3.2.8 Reliability and Validity

The definition of reliability is that it is the degree to which the methods and techniques adopted in the project can be replicated by others at different points of time. On the other hand, the definition of validity is that it is the degree to which research methods and process are able to provide similar results when replicated (Lakshmi and Mohideen, 2013). Reliability and validity are the concepts that are used to estimate the research quality. Reliability and validity indicate how suitable is the technique, method, or test that are used to measure something. Validity is about measuring accuracy, and reliability is about measuring consistency. When a researcher is creating a research design, planning the method for the research and writing the outcomes of research, it is significant to consider the reliability and validity. Reliability can be assessed through comparing the diverse versions of similar measurement. Validity is difficult to estimate, but the outcomes can be estimated by comparing them to other relevant theory or data. Reliability and validity of the research is linked to the evaluation of the quality of the conducted research. Through the evaluation of the reliability and validity the suitability of the technique, methodology and the approach of the research is indicated and analysed in the context of suitability and feasibility of the topic. It is to be noted that the validity of the research process is used to measure accuracy of the methodology meanwhile, the reliability is to evaluate and analyse the consistency of the methodology (Viladrich et al., 2017).

3.3 Section B: Methodology Practiced

This research adopted the Wilson's Honeycomb methodological framework which enabled the researcher to conduct the research in a systematic manner. There are different methodological frameworks available such as the Research onion that highlight the fundamentals of a research methodology. However, the honeycomb model offers a step-by-step guide to the research methodology which enables the researcher to adopt the right research element in a logical manner. The first step of the honeycomb model was to determine the Research philosophy.

3.3.1 Research Philosophy

In this study, positivism has been selected as the research epistemology. The researcher believes that the phenomenon under consideration, i.e. relationship between CSR and employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention can be quantified and an objective process is more likely to provide acceptable knowledge as compared to conducting a subjective process of research. Therefore, using the literature review, this study has operationalised study variables and presented them in a conceptual framework. Furthermore, another important reason for choosing positivism is to provide objective insights and analysis in order to aid business decision making and problem solving which is the main purpose of this study. The positivism philosophy is effective for the evaluation and comprehension of the quantitative data because it supports the objective evaluation of the data for the statistical and logical explanation of the results (Myers, 2013). The positivism philosophy has provided the conducted study in a logical and objective approach of finding out the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention through extracting the primary information and interpreting the results in a statistical manner. In addition, by means of using the positivism research philosophy researchers manage to attain the objective data results and the relations of the variables along with their impacts upon each other through using different tools.

Interpretivism philosophy enables the researchers to evaluate the collected data, more specifically the qualitative data in a subjective manner and is specifically effective for the secondary and qualitative data evaluation (Wilson, 2014). Additionally, according to Myers (2013), an interpretivist research is highly subjective and could be influenced by personal bias. However, By means of positivism philosophy of data analysis and evaluation, the research has effectively handled the quantitative data and has drawn factual knowledge through utilising statistical measurement techniques. Also, the philosophy of positivism has made the result

highly objective so that their authenticity can be increased to the maximum extent and the chances of lacking in the credibility of the results and findings along with the profoundness of the conclusion can be eradicated.

3.3.2 Research Approach

The purpose of investigation of the current study is to explore the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement in the banking sector of the UK. Based on the research purpose, the researcher adopted the suitable research approach for the study which is deductive reasoning. The researcher first identified generally applicable and established theories related to CSR, employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention and then developed tentative hypotheses. The hypotheses were then tested using data specifically from banking sector employees. Another rationale that supports the choice of deductive reasoning in this study is that the researcher has posited with positivism epistemology due to which it is essential that quantitative and objective data is utilised for the completion of the research process. Hence, the deductive approach has been chosen. The results of hypotheses are provided in next chapter.

In the contrary, an inductive approach starts with collecting and recording information from specific circumstances and then move on to developing patterns and commonalities in the observations (Wilson, 2014). In other words, inductive approach contributes to making observations about the research and then developing a theory based on the observations made and is commonly used in qualitative research. As this is not in-line with the research objectives, by means of implementing the deductive approach of analysing and evaluation of the collected data to cultivate the results, the researcher has conducted the whole process of data analysis and hypothesis testing so that profound and effective results could be generated (Myers, 2013). The deductive approach has helped the researcher in investigating the impact of CSR on employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention in the banking sector of the UK and to acquire the statistical data from primary resources so that the results can be constructed accordingly.

3.3.3 Research Strategy

The current study has adapted a quantitative strategy. The foremost justification for this choice is that the researcher has already made positivism as epistemology and deductive reasoning as research approach. Both of these choices essentially require accumulation and examination of quantitative data. Furthermore, another factor that justifies quantitative strategy as the choice for this study is that it aims to assess the impact of CSR on employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention in the banking sector of the UK, which in turn indicates that quantitative data is required for statistical analyses to gain insights about the correlation between the variables. Furthermore, Obeidat (2016) also used quantitative methods in their investigation regarding relationship between CSR and EE & organisational performance. Finally, this study chose to conduct quantitative strategy because it offers a higher level of reliability and validity as compared to qualitative research strategy. The quantitative strategy is based on objective investigation and is considered to be free of personal bias.

Through quantitative strategy the chances for lack of credibility and vagueness in the data is eradicated or reduced to minimal levels. Also, the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention in the banking sector of the UK which is observed and collected by the researcher in the quantitative data form, has helped the researcher to develop definite results without facing any complications and confusions (Creswell and Creswell, 2017).

3.3.4 Research Design

As previously discussed, the research design is observed as the choice of the researcher regarding time horizon and the selection of data and information accordingly to cultivate results. This study has chosen the cross-sectional design for the research process. The choice of cross-sectional design was made because of time and budget constraints involved as inhibitors to a large scale study. Gunawan and Putra, (2014) also used cross-sectional design to conduct a similar investigation within the context of the hotel industry. The researcher recruited a set of members of the target population as sample, employees in the banking sector of the UK, and then collected data using survey questionnaires at a specific point in time. The following sections provide details of these dimensions. The purpose of using the cross-sectional design is to identify a sample of target population and data collection for a specific point in time so that different entities can be recorded within a single time period. It is to be noted that the primary benefit of cross-sectional design for this research is that it is simpler and cost plus

time efficient as compared to other designs as expressed in the theoretical expressions of the methodology (Myers, 2013).

3.3.5 Sampling Strategy

The target population in this study is the workforce in the banking sector of the UK. This is because the phenomenon is relevant to employees' engagement and hence employees are considered to be most important target population.

This study chose to conduct a non-probability sampling process because the target population is banking sector employees which is large, and the researcher lacks access to the entire target population and could not fulfil the basic requirements of probability sampling technique. This strategy is in contrast with other studies where random sampling is often used to enhance reliability and validity such as Choongo (2017) who used random sampling technique to identify sample members. The researcher adopted a non-probability judgment sampling technique over a convenience sampling technique. In convenience sample, the participants are selected based on convenience and the accessibility to the respondent. Instead, a judgment sampling technique is a type of purposive sampling in which the members of the target population are selected and recruited who have similar characteristics (Reddy & Ramasamy, 2016). In judgement sampling, the respondents' specific characteristics plays a role, which in this research was that they are currently employed in the banking sector and the researcher had to ensure different demographic characteristics are represented in the sample. This study invited over 400 banking sector employees and ultimately managed to collect data from 250 employees working in different regions within the UK such as England, Scotland, and Wales. According to Statista (2021), an average of 1 million employees are employed in the UK banking sector. With a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error, the recommended sample size was approximately 385 respondents, due to which the researcher gave out approximately 400 questionnaires. However, since the data were collected during the covid-19 pandemic, there were some barriers and limitations to obtaining the responses. The reason why 250 employees were selected for this study is that this sample size assisted the researcher to reach the saturation process related to gaining all the relevant responses or answers for the questions that were proposed in this research. Moreover, this sample size was also selected by considering the resources, time, and cost of the researcher to reach the employees and collect the data for this

research. Since approaching 250 respondents was deemed possible considering the time and cost constraints, the sample size was created accordingly for gathering the data for this research.

3.3.6 Data Collection

This study collected secondary data majorly from academic textbooks and journal articles. These sources are considered to be less biased as they are published after considerable scrutiny and editorial process. The secondary data was used to elaborate on research variables as well as review of theories related to CSR and employees' engagement. Furthermore, secondary data was also used to develop a conceptual framework that is the basis of primary research component in this study. The previous literature review chapter has presented the results of secondary data analyses.

This study also collected primary data using survey questionnaires. Questionnaires were chosen as data collection instrument because of the decision made in research strategy stage. Questionnaires are commonly used and are popular among social researchers to be integrated in the quantitative strategy. Choongo (2017) conducted a longitudinal design-based study in which he conducted two surveys among 153 entrepreneurs with questionnaire as the data collection instrument. The primary benefit of using questionnaire is its ability to accumulate a large volume of data and information with better time efficiency and lower costs than other instruments such as observation and experiment. However, there is an inherent limitation in the questionnaire tool as it lacks the ability to collect in-depth and detailed data, particularly about perceptions and experiences of research participants (Ritchie et al., 2013).

The questionnaire used in this study was designed originally by the researcher for the purpose of this study and to achieve the research objectives. Therefore, the questions were developed with the support of the literature. The justification and the conclusion expected to derive from each question item is available in the appendices. The questionnaire was initially distributed amongst 3 professionals for a pilot test to ensure understanding and accuracy of the questionnaire, which also guarantee the validity of the questionnaire. Changes were made based on professional feedback to maintain the high standard of the research. The pilot study was conducted only amongst 3 professionals as it reached data saturation whereby the researcher was not receiving any different feedback on the questionnaire and sufficient and repetitive feedback were collected to make necessary changes to the questionnaire.

The questionnaire designed in this study was organised into different sections where the first section examined the demographic profile of the participants while the remaining questions examined the identified variables namely CSR, ER, EPB and EE. Each answer was assigned a pre-determined rating. Participants provided responses by choosing one of the answers and then the ratings assigned were used as quantitative data for the analytical part of research. In the first section of the questionnaire the focus is on accumulating demographic characteristics of participants such as gender, age, designation and education level of the respondents. The second section focused on perceptions of banking sector employees about the CSR variable and the next sections focused on making observations about the employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention variables of the study. It is important to note that these variables were operationalised using the Likert five-point scale.

Moreover, a total of 30 questions were asked from the respondents (justification of each question from existing studies or literature have also been provided in the Appendix of this thesis). The reason why 30 questions were asked from the respondents is that it helped the researcher to gain in-depth knowledge about how CSR activities (as per the opinions and views of the respondents) are impacting employees' engagement in the banking sector and what is the potential relationship between the employees' behaviour and the CSR activities that are undertaken by their companies. These questions have also benefitted the researcher in gaining useful information about the potential impact of CSR activities on the retention rate of the employees. In addition to this, some of the questions related to employees' engagement were also asked from the respondents by considering the impact of Covid-19 in order to determine how this pandemic has affected the planned behaviours (such as the confidence level about job security) of banking employees. However, the disadvantage that the researcher had to face while asking 30 questions from the respondents is that it consumed a lot of time in gathering the data for this study. This, as a result, also delayed the analyses that were conducted on the gathered data to provide appropriate inferences in this research.

3.3.7 Data Analysis

Three different types of statistical processes were used for investigation. The first was frequency analysis. This technique was used to analyse demographic trends of sample participants and to analyse their perceptions towards research variables. However, frequency analysis cannot be used to assess relationship between the research variables. Therefore, the

researcher also used correlation technique. The correlation analysis provided valuable results regarding the association of CSR with the EE, EPB and ER in the UK banking sector, however, the limitation in correlation is that it cannot assess the impact of CSR on employees' engagement and the results do not provide a predictive insight. Finally, in order to overcome limitations in correlation technique, this study developed a regression model (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). The regression model provided insights about the overall impact of CSR on employees' engagement employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention and the degree to which it can be used to explain variability in employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention. Furthermore, the regression model gauged the impact of CSR on employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention to demonstrate how much change can be predicted in EE, EPB and ER with the assumption that there is a unit improvement in CSR while all other factors remain the same. Moreover, these statistical analyses have been conducted by using the software tools SPSS (version 25) and GRETL. The results of the analysis have been presented in both tabular and graphical forms. The results that will be obtained from the quantitative analysis has helped in testing the hypotheses and providing resulting inferences to address the problems of the study (Liu et al., 2019).

3.3.8 Reliability and Validity

It is assumed that this study and the results provided in the next chapter possess a reasonable degree of reliability and validity. The reliability is established by two aspects. First, the researcher has provided complete detailed description of all methods and procedures adopted in the study. Therefore, future researchers are able to replicate the study completely.

Furthermore, Cronbach's alpha has been calculated and reported in the following chapter to demonstrate the internal reliability of the questionnaire. Reliability is important to be managed for the attainment of the value and accuracy of the results through using the most relevant and highly specific data sets. The reliability tests are usually conducted to evaluate the worth and value of the data extracted and the connection of the data with the constructed results. For managing the reliability of the research, the questions of the questionnaire, which is the research instrument for the data collection, are designed in a manner that reflect on the researched concepts and develop comprehension of the participants (Creswell and Creswell, 2017).

On other hand, the validity of the results is assumed to be comparably lower as this study is based on cross-sectional design and data has been collected at a specific point in time. It is assumed that if the study is replicated the respondents will change and therefore data is likely to change leading to difference in final results. In order to maintain the reliability and validity the researcher has recruited a set of participants from the targeted population as the research sample, employees in the banking sector of the UK, and then collected data using survey questionnaires at a specific point in time.

3.4 Ethical Considerations

A number of ethical principles and values were observed. First of all, the researcher made sure that plagiarism is prevented in the research process by using the Harvard referencing style. Proper credits and acknowledgements are given to all the past authors whose works have been used in this project. In addition, the researcher obtained consent from all participants in the study prior to data collection through consent forms. Finally, the researcher has maintained confidentiality and anonymity of all research participants. Since it is a primary and quantitative study that has taken the data from the involved participants by means of using the instrumental questionnaire thus the ethical considerations are more likely to be considered in the context of human safety and human rights preservations. The data is taken from the participants through the proper channel of consent application and the identities of the participants are kept confidential. Also, the respect factors while treating the participants is highly maintained throughout and their comfort is taken under consideration at every step. Similarly, the originality of the content of the research report is highly maintained and there is no chance of copied or plagiarised content or information being stolen from other resources; where information from other sources is used it is properly cited (Creswell and Creswell, 2017).

The primary data collection process of the conducted research is executed in the context of ethical considerations of the scientific research study strictly. For instance, the safety and security of the research participants is observed as a foremost consideration of the researcher and no participant is harmed or subjected to any kind of loss during this study. Also, the consent of the participants regarding participating in the research is attained through documented process. Privacy of the participants is also strictly maintained in the conducted research project. However, the individuality and independence of the participants is never compromised in the process overall.

As per the ethical standards of the scientific research evaluation it is observed that transparency and honesty are extremely important factors of the communication for the information exchange among the participants and the researchers. On ethical grounds the researcher believes that a participant must know and should be properly guided with honesty regarding their concerns related to the righteousness and credibility. Biasness is also strictly avoided in the course of executing the conducted research process by neutralising the environment and maintaining a broad point of view.

Chapter Four: Results and Discussion

4.1 Introduction

This section is aimed at providing the analysis of the study derived from the statistical analyses conducted. The previous sections have developed the background and context of the study. The research objectives have also been elaborated in Chapter One. The literature background was set along with the theoretical groundings of the research topic in Chapter Two. The third chapter further highlighted the method and techniques applied for deriving the analysis for this study. The methodology chapter also elaborated the techniques that would be used for the collection of data and also on techniques for analysing the data.

This section presents the results that have been derived from the statistical techniques as discussed in the previous chapter. The researcher sent out 400 questionnaires and gathered data from 273 respondents and, after the cleaning up of the irrelevant and incomplete data, the study used the data from 250 respondents. This chapter provides the interpretation of the results obtained from SPSS and GRETL software. It firstly describes the demographics of the respondents, namely the age, gender, education and their designation in the bank. Furthermore, the frequency analysis has been provided for elaborating the responses obtained for each question.

This section further provides the descriptive statistics highlighting the mean and the standard deviation of the variables used in the study. The correlation analysis has also been presented to elaborate the strength of relationship between the variables of the study. Regression analysis is also presented for identifying the influence of the independent variable (CSR) on the dependent variables (EE, EPB, ER). The discussion is presented based on the objectives of the study highlighting the findings of the previous studies. It indicates whether the study findings are consistent with the findings of previously conducted studies and if there are any implications of these findings in the study. The chapter also discusses the findings obtained in the Results and Discussion section with the literature review chapter to identify if the results are consistent with the theory and literature. It provides a critical discussion of the findings obtained in this section from the data collected previously with the literature and theories. It further provides a summary of the hypotheses of the data set as it indicates whether the hypotheses are supported or rejected based on the analysis conducted in this study. Finally, the summary section summarises the chapter and the findings.

4.2 Demographic Analysis

4.2.1 Age

Table 4 below shows the age groups of the respondents of the study. It reflects that 17.6% of the respondents are from the age group 18-25. 43.2% of the respondents are between the ages of 26-30. 24% of the respondents belong to the age group 31-39 and 15.2% of the respondents are aged 40 or above.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
18-25	44	17.6	17.6	17.6
26-30	108	43.2	43.2	60.8
31-39	60	24.0	24.0	84.8
40 or above	38	15.2	15.2	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Age Category

Age Category

Figure 7: Age Category of the Respondents

4.2.2 Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	178	71.2	71.2	71.2
Female	72	28.8	28.8	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 5: Gender

Table 5 shows the gender of the participants of the study. It shows that 71.2% of the respondents of the study are male and 28.8% of the respondents of study are female. This reflects that the majority of the respondents of the study are male.

Figure 8: Gender of the Respondents

4.2.3 Educational Background

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
High School	31	12.4	12.4	12.4
Bachelors	78	31.2	31.2	43.6
Masters	95	38.0	38.0	81.6
Doctorate	14	5.6	5.6	87.2
Other	32	12.8	12.8	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 6: Educational Background

Table 6 presents the educational background of the respondents. It elaborates that 12.4% of respondents finished their formal education at high school. 31.2% of the respondents hold a bachelor's degree. Furthermore, 38% hold a master's degree, 5.6% of the respondents are doctorate degree holders and finally, 12.8% respondents are from educational backgrounds not listed above.

Figure 9: Educational Background of the Respondents

4.2.4 Designation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Manager	28	11.2	11.2	11.2
Assistant Manager	24	9.6	9.6	20.8
Executive	11	4.4	4.4	25.2
Officer	89	35.6	35.6	60.8
Trainee	88	35.2	35.2	96.0
Other	10	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 7: Designation

The above Table 7 shows the designation of the respondents. It shows that 11.2% of the respondents are managers in a bank, 9.6% of the respondents are assistant managers in their respective banks, and 4.4% are executive level respondents. 35.6%, i.e. most of the respondents, hold the position of officers and 35.2% are trainees at a bank. 4% of the respondents are from designations other than those listed.

Figure 10: Designation

4.3 Frequency Analysis

The distribution of responses for a single variable is identified by the Frequency Analysis. A frequency table presents the number of responses and the percentage of responses under each Likert scale item for a single variable (Sage Publications, 2012). This is a useful method to identify the most common response for a questionnaire item. The following table summarises and presents the frequencies of the responses to the 30 questionnaire items. The questionnaire items have been categorised and allocated under corporate social responsibility (CSR), employees' engagement (EE), employees' planned behaviour (EPB) and employees' retention (ER) variables. The main categorisation has been conducted based on the outcome expected to be achieved for that question. Similarly, each question has been coded based on the variable under which it has been categorised.

Question No:	Code	Variable	Frequency of responses					Analysis
			Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	
1	CSR1	Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	20 (8%)	35 (14%)	74 (29.6%)	100 (40%)	21 (8.4%)	48.4% employees in the banking sector are in agreement that the employees in the sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility.
2	CSR2	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	20 (8%)	37 (14.8%)	69 (27.6%)	94 (37.6%)	30 (12%)	According to the responses, it can be identified that that 49.6% of banking employees believe that the CSR activities of

								the organisation have a positive impact on their job performances.
3	EE1	Employees' engagement is significantly impacted during the Covid-19 pandemic.	15 (6%)	26 (10.4%)	77 (30.8%)	100 (40%)	32 (12.8%)	Over 52% of the respondents feel that COVID-19 has impacted on banking employees' engagement levels. 30.8% of the respondents, however, neither agree nor disagree with the statement.

4	CSR3	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	19 (7.6%)	22 (8.8%)	65 (26%)	108 (43.2%)	36 (14.4%)	The majority of UK banking sector employee respondents agree that CSR improves the productivity of their organisation which is validated by 57.6% of respondents agreeing to the statement
5	CSR4	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	5 (2%)	27 (10.8%)	78 (31.2%)	105 (42%)	35 (14%)	It can be determined that 56% of the respondents believe that a company's working standards are enhanced through CSR initiatives. However, 12.8% disagree and 31.2% are neutral to the statement.
6	EE2	CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a work-life balance.	12 (4.8%)	11 (4.4%)	83 (33.2%)	117 (46.8%)	27 (10.8%)	A company's CSR activities that focus on flexible working arrangements that help employees to maintain work-life balance leads to increased employees' engagement

								which is evident by the 57.6% of the respondents who agreed with the statement
7	EE3	Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	10 (4%)	15 (6%)	65 (26%)	134 (53.6%)	26 (10.4%)	It can interpret that the majority (64%) of the respondents agree that Covid-19 and the subsequent unemployment levels have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.
8	EE4	Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID19 era.	10 (4%)	16 (6.4%)	73 (29.2%)	121 (48.4%)	30 (12%)	During the Covid-19 outbreak, many UK banking sector employees are losing trust in their company which is apparent by the fact that 60.4% of the responses agreed to the statement.
9	EE7	Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	5 (2%)	5 (2%)	55 (22%)	140 (56%)	45 (18%)	Only 4% of the respondents are in disagreement that employees' loss of confidence and trust in the company negatively impacts on their planned behaviour and the vast majority of the respondents (74%) are in agreement with the statement.

10	EE5	The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	3 (1.2%)	15 (6%)	42 (16.8%)	135 (54%)	55 (22%)	Over 75% of the respondents are in agreement that the Covid-19 pandemic has affected the job market and economic conditions.
11	EE6	The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	2 (0.8%)	8 (3.2%)	55 (22%)	138 (55.2%)	47 (18.8%)	74% of the respondents believe that the bank where they are employed has provided them with sufficient support and resources to help them through the Covid19 pandemic. A minority 4% of the employees disagrees that they have been provided with support and resources during the pandemic.
12	CSR5	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	8 (3.2%)	40 (16%)	91 (36.4%)	90 (36%)	21 (8.4%)	Although 36.4% of the employees are feeling neutral about this statement, 44.4% of the respondents believe that CSR activities encourage banking sector employees to demonstrate upward ethical behaviour. It is also important to highlight that 19.2% of the employees disagree with this statement.
13	EPB7	The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	6 (2.4%)	8 (3.2%)	64 (25.6%)	131 (52.4%)	41 (16.4%)	As a result of the Covid-19 outbreak, over 68% of the respondents from the UK banking sector believe that employees are encouraged to donate their own money to CSR activities that are focused on managing the virus and its effects.

14	CSR6	CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve work-related problems in their banking institutions.	18 (7.2%)	27 (10.8%)	85 (34%)	94 (37.6%)	26 (10.4%)	Although 18% of the respondents disagree with the statement, 48% of the respondents are certain that CSR activities instil encouragement in banking sector employees to actively and voluntarily solve work-related problems.
15	EPB8	CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	8 (3.2%)	5 (2%)	67 (26.8%)	132 (52.8%)	38 (15.2%)	The respondents from the banking sector most commonly (68%) believe that CSR activities reduce the turnover intentions of employees while just over 5% of the respondents think that CSR does not play a role in reducing turnover intentions of the employees.
16	EPB1	Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	4 (1.6%)	19 (7.6%)	67 (26.8%)	127 (50.8%)	33 (13.2%)	64% of the respondents are in agreement that employees are facing different challenges working remotely during the Covid-19 pandemic which has led companies to adapt to different working practices and new policies to be developed
17	CSR7	CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	14 (5.6%)	28 (11.2%)	82 (32.8%)	104 (41.6%)	22 (8.8%)	Over half of the respondents (50.4%) agree that CSR activities inspire employees to demonstrate ethical behaviour.

18	EPB2	CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	6 (2.4%)	24 (9.6%)	76 (30.4%)	116 (46.4%)	28 (11.2%)	57.6% of the respondents agreed with the statement that CSR practices encourage them (banking sector employees) to act in the best interest of their banks.
19	EPB3	The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	6 (2.4%)	16 (6.4%)	85 (34%)	114 (45.6%)	29 (11.6%)	Whereas 34% of the respondents remained neutral, 57.2% of the respondents agreed with the statement that the outbreak of Covid-19 has increased corporate citizenship behaviour amongst banking sector employees.
20	EPB4	The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	7 (2.8%)	11 (4.4%)	68 (27.2%)	126 (50.4%)	38 (15.2%)	50.4% agree and 15.2% strongly agree that their company's leaders have effectively managed the challenges and risks that were instigated by the Covid-19 pandemic
21	EPB5	The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	6 (2.4%)	8 (3.2%)	68 (27.2%)	124 (49.6%)	44 (17.6%)	Banking sector employees believe that their company has undertaken adequate planning to engage its employees during the Covid-19 pandemic and has effectively managed the crisis, which is evident by 67.2% of the respondents agreeing to the statement.

22	EPB6	Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	7 (2.8%)	9 (3.6%)	71 (28.4%)	119 (47.6%)	44 (17.6%)	65.2% of the respondents think that banking sector employees are worried about the changes in their company's policies and working conditions as a consequence of the Covid-19 pandemic, although 28.4% of the respondents remained neutral on this statement.
23	ER1	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	6 (2.4%)	13 (5.2%)	63 (25.2%)	133 (53.2%)	35 (14%)	Banks' involvement in CSR activities reduces the employees' intentions to leave the organisation which is apparent by the 53.2% of the respondents who agreed and 14% of the respondents who strongly agreed with the statement.
24	ER2	The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	6 (2.4%)	5 (2%)	69 (27.6%)	135 (54%)	35 (14%)	A small proportion of less than 5% of the respondents feel that the Covid-19 pandemic did not affect the job security of employees. However, the most common response (68%) is that the employees' job security has been affected by the Covid-19 pandemic.
25	ER3	CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employees' retention in the long-run.	7 (2.8%)	6 (2.4%)	66 (26.4%)	135 (54%)	36 (14.4%)	68.4% of the respondents are in agreement that CSR is a form of enhancing a company's branding strategy as an employer, which helps them retain their employees in the long-term.

26	ER4	Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	7 (2.8%)	10 (4%)	68 (27.2%)	131 (52.4%)	34 (13.6%)	66% of the respondents agreeing to the statement reflects that, when employees participate in voluntary CSR activities, it is important that the company recognises these efforts since it will lead to the retention of its employees.
27	ER8	CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	17 (6.8%)	47 (18.8%)	84 (33.6%)	87 (34.8%)	15 (6%)	40.8% of the respondents agree that CSR leads to an increased job retention rate by positively impacting on the job satisfaction of the employees. However, 25.6% of the respondents disagree with this statement.
28	ER5	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	7 (2.8%)	8 (3.2%)	72 (28.8%)	135 (54%)	28 (11.2%)	Although 28.8% of the respondents feel neutral about the statement, over 65% of them believe that the risks of job poaching is significantly reduced when organisations involve in CSR activities.
29	ER7	CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	4 (1.6%)	8 (3.2%)	68 (27.2%)	138 (55.2%)	32 (12.8%)	55.2% agree and 12.8% strongly agree that CSR activities focused on reducing the escalation of the virus has impacted positively on the employees' retention rates. A smaller proportion of 4.8% of the respondents disagree with this view.
30	ER6	The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee	5 (2%)	11 (4.4%)	62 (24.8%)	151 (60.4%)	21 (8.4%)	A larger proportion of the respondents trust that their company's leaders have

		retention strategies during the Covid-19 era.						implemented effective employee retention strategies during the Covid-19 pandemic.
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Table 8: Frequency Analysis (Author's own)

4.4 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
CSR	250	1.5	5	3.34	0.71
Employees' engagement	250	1	5	3.69	0.67
Employees' planned behaviour	250	1	5	3.69	0.68
Employees' retention	250	1	5	3.72	0.57

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics

The table 9 above shows the descriptive statistics of the variables. It shows that the variable CSR has the mean value of 3.34 which reflects that the average response for the questions relating to CSR is 'neutral'. The employees' engagement is indicated to have the mean value of 3.69 which reflects the average response for the employees' engagement questions are inclined towards 'agree'. Employees' planned behaviour has the mean value of 3.69 which suggests that the average response of questions related to employees' planned behaviour is also towards 'agree'. Finally, employees' retention has indicated a mean value of 3.72 which, too, shows that average respondents 'agreed' to the questions relating to employees' retention. Table 9, illustrating descriptive statistics, indicates that the minimum value of CSR is 1.5 whereas the maximum value recorded is 5 and this further shows the value of CSR depending on the policies of companies. The minimum value of employees' engagement is 1 and the maximum value recorded is 5 and this indicates that the value of engagement varies on the practices of CSR. The minimum value of employees' planned behaviour is 1 and the maximum value of employees' planned behaviour is 5. The minimum value of employees' retention is 1 and the maximum value of employees' retention is 5 and this indicates that employees' retention is associated with the practices of CSR.

4.5 Reliability Testing

Reliability analysis is defined as the measure of internal consistency of the measurement models used in the study (Sekeran and Bougie, 2016). It is associated with the fact that the scale has to be consistent in reflecting the construct being measured. It is the measurement technique which helps the researcher in evaluating the stability of certain measures or constructs. Cronbach's Alpha is used for the evaluation of the reliability of the questionnaire used for measuring certain variables. It is essentially the measure of the internal consistency which evaluates how closely an item is linked with the others in the group. The measure of the Cronbach's Alpha was developed by Lee Cronbach in 1951 to evaluate the internal consistency of a model. It is perceived that a Cronbach's alpha value of greater than 0.70 shows that the certain measure used for indicating the variable has higher internal consistency and is deemed reliable (Bougie and Sekeran, 2016). Therefore, this study uses Cronbach's alpha for evaluating the reliability of the questions that were used for measuring the variables CSR, employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention. There are 7 items representing each CSR and EE variables while 8 items are selected for representing each of the EPB and ER variables for which the reliability has been tested. The categorisation of the questionnaire items under each variable is discussed in table 8.

Cronbach's	
Alpha	N of Items
.837	7

Table 10: Reliability of CSR items

The table 10 above reflects the reliability test of the CSR variables. The reliability of the variables are reflected when the Cronbach's Alpha value is greater than 0.70, which show high consistency and reliability in the data. The Cronbach's Alpha of CSR has been obtained to be 0.837 which is greater than 0.70 and hence it reflects the higher internal consistency and reliability of the data.

Cronbach's	
Alpha	N of Items
.873	7

Table 11: Reliability of EE items

Furthermore, the Cronbach's Alpha of employees' engagement is found to be 0.873 demonstrated in Table 11 which also reflects the reliability of the items as it is higher than 0.70. This further indicates that the data of employees' engagement are reliable and maintains internal consistency. Employees' planned behaviour has obtained a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.906 as demonstrated in table 12 below, which is also greater than the threshold and hence it shows reliability of the data.

Cronbach's	
Alpha	N of Items
.906	8

Table 12: Reliability of EPB items

Employees' retention has identified to have the Cronbach's Alpha of 0.793 in table 13 and demonstrates high reliability of data since the value is greater than the threshold of 0.70. This indicates that the components of employees' retention are reliable and maintains internal consistency.

Cronbach's	
Alpha	N of Items
.793	8

Table 13: Reliability of ER items

In summary, the Cronbach's Alpha of all 4 variables are higher than 0.70 hence demonstrates that the instrument used in this study has higher internal consistency and confirms the reliability of the questionnaire as well. Henceforth, the data obtained through the questionnaire are verified to be reliable to conduct further analysis.

4.6 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is a statistical technique used to measure the strength of the association between the variables considered in the study and also to compute the significance of the relationship between the variables (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The higher correlation indicates a strong relationship whereas a lower correlation reflects weakly correlated variables.

Pearson's correlation coefficient is one of the widely used measure of the correlation between variables. It measures the strength of the relationship between variables. The value of the Pearson correlation ranges from +1 to -1. The value of the correlation coefficient which is closer

to +1 or -1 indicates a stronger relationship. However, the value below 0.38 is indicated to have a weak relationship among the variables. The value from 0.39 to 0.6 is indicated to reflect a moderate relationship among the variables (Bell, Brymann and Harley, 2018).

Table 14: Correlation Analysis

		CSR	EE	EPB	ER
Pearson					
CSR	Correlation	1	.608**	.406**	.366**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0	0	0
	N	250	250	250	250
Pearson					
EE	Correlation	.608**	1	.585**	.488**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0		0	0
	N	250	250	250	250
Pearson					
EPB	Correlation	.406**	.585**	1	.726**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0		0
	N	250	250	250	250
Pearson					
ER	Correlation	.366**	.488**	.726**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	
	N	250	250	250	250
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).					

The table above reflects the values of the Pearson correlation for indicating the strength of the correlation between the four variables in this study. Furthermore, it also indicates whether or not the relationship between the variables is significant. According to Table 14, CSR has a strong and significant correlation with employees' engagement since the correlation coefficient is identified to be 0.608. Furthermore, CSR and employees' planned behaviour has also been identified to have a moderate and significant correlation since the coefficient of correlation is 0.406. However, CSR and employees' retention has the correlation coefficient of 0.366 which indicates that the variables have a weak and significant correlation. Furthermore, employees' engagement and employees' planned behaviour has the correlation coefficient of 0.585 that reflects a moderate and significant correlation. Employees' retention and employees' engagement has reflected a correlation coefficient of 0.488 which also indicates the moderate and significant correlation. The correlation between employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention has been identified to be significant and strong with the correlation coefficient of 0.726.

The correlation analysis further indicates that there is a strong association between corporate social responsibility and employees' engagement with the significance value of 0.00 (less than 0.05). As identified in the literature, engagement of employees was interlinked with their possible expectation and participation of CSR activities. Furthermore, employees' engagement was highly influenced in some of the cases because organisations were laying off some of their employees especially during the Covid-19 pandemic. The Table of Correlation Analysis further indicates that CSR activities have moderate and significant association with employees' planned behaviour with the significance value of 0.00 and this indicates that CSR activities cause employee behaviour to be influenced. It was identified in the literature that employees are considered as one of the key stakeholders that have an impact on the decisions of organisations. Furthermore, employees can also be impacted by the CSR initiatives or programmes that are conducted by their organisations which can affect their attitudes and behaviours differently. The Table of Correlation Analysis above also indicates that there is a positive but weak and significant association between CSR and employees' retention, and this indicates that CSR activities can affect the motivation of employees and further causes retention of employees to be affected, but the strength of the relationship is weak between these 2 variables. The positive relationship demonstrates that, when firms carry out different socially responsible practices by engaging in different CSR activities such as reducing carbon emission,

conducting philanthropic activities, etc., the turnover intentions among the workers are reduced.

4.7 Factor Analysis

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) has been used for analysing the interrelationship among variables and for describing the variables related to the common underlying factors within them (Alavi et al., 2020). The factor analysis is mostly used by researchers for indicating the validity of the data analysis. There are various extraction techniques that are applied in factor analysis in which the Principal Component Analysis (PCA), has been opted to generate the initial EFA. In the current study, the factor analysis is performed for each variable to determine the inclusion items for measuring the effect of CSR on the employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention in the UK banking sector. This helps in excluding the items that are not relevant with the variables, as the main function of the factor loading is to reduce the larger number of variables into a number of fewer factors (Fan et al., 2018).

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) outcome retrieved from the factor analysis measures the suitability of data for the factor analysis. While the KMO measures the adequacy of the sample taken, Barlett's test of sphericity has also been used for achieving the applicable outcomes for the factor analysis. The KMO's measure of sampling adequacy has to be greater than 0.6 and the Barlett's test of sphericity has to be below 0.05. A significance in the Bartlett's test of sphericity reflects that the correlation matrix is not an identity matrix hence the variables are suitable for factor analysis. Total Variance Explained table shows the variance proportion of the variables that are caused through the use of the new factors. Furthermore, the main table of factor analysis pertains to the rotated component matrix where it represents the key output reflecting to the PCA which presents the estimation of the correlation between each of the variables along with the estimated components. For the current research, the researcher will be selecting 'proxy' variables to represent each of the independent (CSR) and dependant variables (EE, EPB, ER). The proxies will be selected on the basis of the 'rotated component matrix' with the items that have the highest values in the table.

4.7.1 Factor Analysis of CSR

A factor analysis was conducted for all items that were categorised under CSR. The table 15 shown below reflects that the KMO measure of sampling adequacy for CSR has a value of 0.771 which is greater than the set threshold of 0.6 and hence it is identified that the data are suitable for factor analysis. Furthermore, the Bartlett's sphericity test has been identified to

have the P-value of 0.00 and hence it is also shown to be significant and suitable for factor analysis.

Table 15: KMO- Bartlett's Test of CSR

KMO and Bartlett's Test			
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.			0.771
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	774.582	
	df	21.00	
	Sig.	0.000	

With the confirmation of the KMO and Bartlett's test of Sphericity, the next step involves the analysis of the 'Total Variance Explained' table which determines the percentage of the components extracted from variables. Table 16 represents the outcome of total variance explained for the variable CSR and as per the table; there are two factors/components that are extracted from the total variance. The cumulative percentage was computed as 69.53% for the two factors which indicates that the two factors/components explained the 69.53% of the variance.

Component	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared			Rotation Sums of Squared		
	Total	Loadings		Total	Loadings		Total	Loadings	
		% of Variance	Cumulative %		% of Variance	Cumulative %		% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.561	50.865	50.865	3.561	50.865	50.865	3.092	44.178	44.178
2	1.306	18.664	69.529	1.306	18.664	69.529	1.775	25.350	69.529
3	.763	10.900	80.429						
4	.483	6.906	87.334						
5	.333	4.756	92.090						
6	.318	4.541	96.631						
7	.236	3.369	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 16: Total Variance Explained of CSR components

The rotated component matrix of CSR examines the correlation value coefficient of each item that are involved in the variable of CSR. The results of rotated component matrix of CSR can be referred to in the table below where there is a particular score provided to each of the items. These scores will also be used for the selection of the ‘proxy’ item to represent the variables in the regression analysis. The proxy will have the highest score which would ultimately lead to the rejection of other items. Table 17 displays the rotated component matrix of CSR which indicates that there are mainly two components involved for the variable. Therefore, this leads to the selection of two proxies by examining the columns component 1 and component 2. Further reviewing the table, it was identified that the items with the highest scores under component 1 were CSR7 ‘CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour’, which had the score of 0.878 and the highest score under component 2 was CSR4 ‘CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company’, with a score of 0.886. Therefore, CSR7 and CSR4 will be considered as the proxies to represent CSR. A proxy is a variable to represent and can stand in for other variables. These two chosen proxies will be used to conduct the regression analysis where they is treated as the independent variable for representing CSR in the ordinal regression technique.

Table 17: Rotated Component Matrix of CSR

Rotated Component Matrix ^a		Component	
		1	2
CSR7	CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	.830	.028
CSR6	CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve work related problems in their banking institutions.	.824	.040
CSR2	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	.789	.210
CSR1	Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	.769	.263
CSR3	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	.677	.321
CSR4	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	.107	.886
CSR5	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	.204	.878

The scree plot of CSR is shown to be declining which shows the highest eigenvalues for the first two factors that has an eigenvalue is above 1. For the other factors forward however, the eigenvalues are below 1 and are further seen reducing as it attains a small value for the last few factors. Hence, it confirms the acceptance of the two components for CSR. Figure 11 below illustrates the clear declining eigenvalues for the factors showing the validity of data.

Figure 11: Scree Plot of CSR

4.7.2 Factor Analysis of Employees' Engagement

In this section, the factor analysis of employees' engagement is conducted through focusing mainly towards KMO and Bartlett's test, rotated component matrix and the scree plot. Table 18 below represents the KMO and Bartlett's test of sphericity for the variable employees' engagement, in which the KMO value is determined to be 0.815 and is greater than the 0.6 threshold. Moreover, the Bartlett's test significance value is 0.00 and is lower than the threshold of 0.05. Therefore, the results of the KMO and Bartlett's test indicate that it is appropriate to use the factor analysis for the dataset of employees' engagement.

Table 18: KMO- Bartlett's Test of Employees' Engagement

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.815
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1143.15
	df	21
	Sig.	0.000

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Extraction Sums of Squared						Rotation Sums of Squared		
	Initial Eigenvalues			Loadings			Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.037	57.673	57.673	4.037	57.673	57.673	2.904	41.488	41.488
2	1.378	19.682	77.355	1.378	19.682	77.355	2.511	35.867	77.355
3	.627	8.957	86.312						
4	.335	4.791	91.104						
5	.267	3.810	94.913						
6	.210	3.005	97.919						
7	.146	2.081	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 19: Total Variance Explained of EE components

Table 19 represents the total variance explained for the variable employees' engagement, where there are two factors/components that are extracted from the total variance. The cumulative percentage was computed as 77.36% for the two components which indicates that the two factors/components explained 77.36% of the variance in the employees' engagement variable.

Table 20: Rotated Component Matrix of Employees' Engagement

Rotated Component Matrix ^a			
		Component	
		1	2
EE3	Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	.897	.203
EE4	Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the Covid19 era.	.879	.192
EE2	CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a work-life balance.	.863	.231
EE1	Employees' engagement is significantly impacted during the Covid-19 pandemic.	.644	.238

EE6	The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of Covid-19.	.199	.922
EE5	The Covid-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	.219	.870
EE7	Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	.282	.846

Moving towards the rotated component matrix of the variable employees' engagement in table 20, it is determined that the item that has highest value in the matrix is EE3 '*Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities*' under component 1 scoring 0.897 and EE6 '*The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of Covid-19*' under component 2 with a score of 0.922. Therefore, these two items have been retained for representing employees' engagement for further conducting the ordinal regression technique where the effects of the selected CSR items are measured on these identified items of employees' engagement. Figure 12 below represents the scree plot of employees' engagement. As indicated from the graph, there are two components that have an eigenvalue above 1. Therefore, the plot suggests that the factors that should be retained are components 1 and 2.

Figure 12: Scree Plot of EE

4.7.3 Factor Analysis of Employees' Planned Behaviour

This section investigates the factor analysis of employees' planned behaviour where the procedure adopted above is similarly followed in conducting the factor analysis. The main techniques that are applied in the PCA are KMO and Bartlett's test, rotated component matrix and the scree plot. Table 21 represents the KMO and Bartlett's test of sphericity for the variable employees' planned behaviour in which the KMO value is determined to be 0.859 and is greater than the 0.6 threshold. Moreover, the Bartlett's test significance value is 0.00 and is lower than 0.05; therefore, the results of the KMO and Bartlett's test indicate that it is appropriate in using the factor analysis for the dataset of employees' planned behaviour.

Table 21: KMO- Bartlett's Test of Employees' Planned Behaviour

KMO and Bartlett's Test			
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin	Measure	of	Sampling
Adequacy.			0.859
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx.	Chi-	
	Square		1516.11
	df		28
	Sig.		0.000

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared			Rotation Sums of Squared		
	Total	Loadings		Total	Loadings		Total	Loadings	
		% of Variance	Cumulative %		% of Variance	Cumulative %		% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.898	61.231	61.231	4.898	61.231	61.231	3.898	48.723	48.723
2	1.417	17.717	78.948	1.417	17.717	78.948	2.418	30.225	78.948
3	.409	5.108	84.056						
4	.369	4.611	88.667						
5	.330	4.122	92.789						
6	.284	3.550	96.340						
7	.161	2.017	98.357						

8	.131	1.643	100.000						
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.									

Table 22: Total Variance Explained of EPB components

Table 22 represents the total variance explained for the variable Employees’ Planned Behaviour where there are two factors/components that are extracted from the total variance. The cumulative percentage was computed as 78.95% for the two components which demonstrates that the two factors/components explains the variance in the variable of EPB by 78.95%.

Table 23 represents the results of the rotated component matrix of employees’ planned behaviour where there are total of 7 items measuring the variables. Based on the results, it is observed that EPB7 ‘The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease’ has the highest score under component 1 due to the value being 0.892. Furthermore, EPB2 ‘CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks’ has the highest value under component 2 with a score of 0.860. In this regard, these two items are further utilised for conducting the ordinal regression and examining the effects on EPB by using the selected CSR items.

Table 23: Rotated Component Matrix of Employees’ Planned Behaviour

Rotated Component Matrix ^a		Component	
		1	2
EPB7	The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	.892	.219
EPB4	The company’s leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to Covid-19	.872	.211
EPB5	The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	.864	.230
EPB8	CSR activities help in reducing employees’ turnover intentions.	.848	.250

EPB6	Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	.843	.241
EPB2	CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	.168	.860
EPB1	Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	.237	.849
EPB3	The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	.284	.831

The scree plot in figure 13 represents the variable employees' planned behaviour in which it can be reflected from the plot that there are two items that have the eigenvalue above 1.

Therefore, this can indicate that two factors can be used in the EPB for conducting further analysis.

Figure 13: Scree Plot of EPB

4.7.4 Factor Analysis of Employees' Retention

The last PCA is conducted for the variable employees' retention which is demonstrated in Table 24. The results of KMO and Bartlett's test of sphericity for the variable employees' retention is shown in the table. The KMO value is computed as 0.797 which is above the threshold of 0.5;

therefore, this leads to acceptance of sampling adequacy. Furthermore, the Bartlett's test of sphericity has the significance value of 0.000 and is below the level of 0.05, hence is considered as significant. Therefore, the results further suggest incorporating the rotated component matrix for generating results for employees' retention.

Table 24: KMO- Bartlett's Test for Employees' Retention

KMO and Bartlett's Test			
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.797	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1139.48	
	df	28	
	Sig.	0.000	

Component	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared			Rotation Sums of Squared		
	Total	Loadings		Total	Loadings		Total	Loadings	
		% of Variance	Cumulative %		% of Variance	Cumulative %		% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.522	44.030	44.030	3.522	44.030	44.030	3.209	40.114	40.114
2	2.122	26.519	70.549	2.122	26.519	70.549	2.435	30.434	70.549
3	.930	11.622	82.171						
4	.430	5.371	87.542						
5	.369	4.617	92.159						
6	.251	3.141	95.300						
7	.211	2.641	97.941						
8	.165	2.059	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 25: Total Variance Explained of ER components

Table 25 represents the total variance explained for the variable Employees' Retention where there are two factors/components that are extracted from the total variance. The cumulative

percentage was computed as 70.55% within the two components which demonstrates that the two factors/components explain the variance in the variable of employee retention by 70.55%.

Similarly, Table 26 reflects to the rotated component matrix for the variable Employees' Retention. It is observed from the table, that the item ER4 '*Recognising voluntary participation of employees in CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run*' has the highest value in rotated component matrix due to having a score of 0.906 under component 1. Meanwhile under component 2, ER6 '*The leadership of the company is implementing effective employees' retention strategies during the Covid-19 era*' has the highest score of 0.925. This leads to the selection of the items ER4 and ER6 as the variables to represent employees' retention. However, further decision can be made through the screen plot to ensure both components have an eigenvalue above 1 to be considered as a proxy.

Table 26: Rotated Component Matrix of Employees' Retention

Rotated Component Matrix ^a		Component	
		1	2
ER4	Recognising voluntary participation of employees in CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	.906	.105
ER3	CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employees' retention in the long-run.	.889	.055
ER2	The Covid-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	.885	.133
ER1	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	.824	.048
ER8	CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	.317	.056
ER6	The leadership of the company is implementing effective employees' retention strategies during the Covid-19 era.	.113	.925
ER5	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	.043	.899
ER7	CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	.142	.857

Figure 14 represents the scree plot for the variable employees' retention, and it can be reflected from the plot that there is only one component has an eigenvalue above 1. However, according to the scree plot, component 2 has an eigenvalue below 1, hence this component will not be considered. Therefore, it can indicate that only one component can be used for ER in conducting further analysis, and the item with the highest score for component 1 will be considered as the proxy, which is the item ER4.

Figure 14: Scree Plot of Employees' Retention

Based on the assessment of the factor analysis that is applied through PCA, it is determined that there are 2 proxies that each for the variables CSR, employee engagement and employee planned behaviour whereas only 1 proxy is considered for the variable employee retention based on the rotated component matrix and the scree plot.

4.8 Regression Analysis

Regarding regression analysis, Astivia and Zumbo (2019) referred to it as a statistical approach that serves the objective of assessing the relationship that exists between the dependent and its independent variables. It is further stated that regression analysis indicates the magnitude of the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The present study utilises an ordinal regression analysis which as per the views of Harell (2015), is used when predicting the dependent variable with ordered multiple categories of independent variables.

As explained in the above PCA analysis, the items with the highest values in the rotated component matrix were chosen as the proxies which will represent the said variable as summarised in table 27. As the study intends to find the impact of corporate social responsibility on employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention individually, hence, CSR has been considered as the independent variable and the remaining EE, EPB and ER will be the dependant variables. These variables have been analysed using ordinal logistic regression analysis using the GRETL software. The below table summarises the chosen proxies to represent the variables based on the PCA outcomes and discussion above.

Table 27: Identified Proxies for Variables

Variable	Code	Item
Corporate Social Responsibility	CSR7	CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour
	CSR4	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company
Employees' engagement	EE3	The Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities
	EE6	The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of Covid-19.
Employees' planned behaviour	EPB7	The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease
	EPB2	CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks
Employees' retention	ER4	Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run

4.8.1 Impact of CSR on Employees' Engagement

Model 1: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: EE3

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR7	1.36802	0.194316	7.040	<0.0001	***

Table 28: EE3=CSR7

From the table above (model 1), it is identified that the CSR has a significant impact on the employees' engagement based on the P-value less than 0.05. CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour. Sarfo et al. (2020) explained that when organisations incorporate environmental and social issues with their business functions and communications with key stakeholders, they are able to motivate their employees to demonstrate higher ethical behaviour. However, the Covid-19 outbreak has limited the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities as Covid-19 has caused the unemployment levels to go up (Bank of England, 2021). These impacts of Covid-19 have reduced the number of employees working in the banks' premises for banks to participate in CSR activities and have limited employees' engagement opportunities. This is apparent by the high significant (p-value=<0.0001) between the two variables (EE3=CSR7).

Model 2: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: EE6

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR7	0.602349	0.161318	3.734	0.0002	***

Table 29: EE6=CSR7

According to the model 2 it can be understood that CSR has a significant impact on employees' engagement. Companies adopted different strategies to manage the effects of COVID-19 by providing support to their employees. Many businesses in the UK, including banks, made use of the government funded furlough schemes to support employees who would have otherwise been laid-off, which eventually also supported businesses to survive and jobs to be protected (Bank of England, 2021). Furthermore, business strategies were also implemented which allowed employees to work from home, adopted flexible work arrangements and introduced

virtual tools and resources to support employees during the pandemic (Forbes, 2020). It is thereby understood that when businesses also focus on internal CSR and support employees, specifically in dealing with a pandemic situation, it helps employees to trust their employer which leads employees to be engaged in their jobs, display ethical behaviour and increase productivity. This is evident by the significance of the two variables (EE6=CSR7) which produced a p-value equal to 0.0002. This is further confirmed by the many researches that have concluded that working from home increases employees' productivity (ONS.GOV.UK, 2021; CIPD, 2021).

Model 3: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: EE3

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR4	0.555645	0.181603	3.060	0.0022	***

Table 30: EE3=CSR4

Model 3 above suggests that CSR has a significant impact on employees' engagement. CSR initiatives assist in raising the working standards of a company. According to Glavas (2016), CSR activities help employees to bring more of their "whole selves" to work. This helps employees to enhance the quality of their work since they feel more engaged with their jobs. When companies participate in CSR activities, employees become more encouraged to implement high-quality work standards and develop socially acceptable working practices within organisations (Murmura et al., 2017). Covid-19 has impacted on businesses engaging in CSR activities due to the increased absenteeism levels and sick leave amongst employees. This also includes the impact of the preventive measures implemented in terms of working from home in order to maintain social distancing (Groenewold et al., 2020). These measures have caused limited interactions amongst the key stakeholders and restricted employees' engagement levels. The significance P-value= 0.0022 between the two variables (EE3=CSR4) is evidence that CSR activities encourage the implementation of high-quality work standards although the Covid-19 pandemic has limited CSR opportunities of employees and caused issues such as unemployment and absenteeism within the UK banking sector.

Model 4: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: EE6

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR4	0.437770	0.193503	2.262	0.0237	**

Table 31: EE6=CSR4

Finally, in understanding the relationship between CSR and EE, the above model 4 demonstrates that CSR has a significant impact on employees' engagement. In order to overcome the diverse effects of Covid-19, many businesses adapted the work-from-home technique to ensure that the business and its operations are not interrupted. During this period, it was important that companies provided sufficient resources and support to their employees to ensure their working standards are maintained. Support and resources include looking after the employees' well-being, mental health and counselling services to cope with the work and pandemic stress, virtual tools and training, work-life balance and effective communication within the organisation (Forbes, 2020). These are also considered as internal CSR activities as discussed in the literature review. Therefore, the significance p-value= 0.0237 confirms that CSR activities that include providing sufficient resources to employees, specifically in a pandemic situation, helps organisations to raise their work standards not only by providing good standards of service to customers through their work-from-home strategies to continue business operations, but also by enhancing employees' engagement through internal CSR (EE6=CSR4).

4.8.2 Impact of CSR on Employees' Planned Behaviour

Model 5: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: EPB7

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR7	0.614048	0.170157	3.609	0.0003	***

Table 32: EPB7=CSR7

The table above (Model 5) reflects the impact of CSR on the employees' planned behaviour. It is identified that CSR has significant influence on the employees' planned behaviour. CSR

activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour. Businesses that align their operations with social issues are able to motivate their employees to demonstrate higher ethical behaviour. The variable focused on determining whether banking employees are demonstrating corporate citizenship behaviour by donating to CSR initiatives focused on controlling the spread of the Covid-19 which are adapted by their employer banks. A motivated workforce demonstrates organisation citizenship behaviour and aligns their allegiance with the firm's mission and vision (Welch, 2015). There is a significance (p-value 0.0003) between the two variables (EPB7=CSR7). This is evidence that as a result of the ethical behaviour encouraged by CSR activities conducted by banks, employees have been motivated to donate their own money towards initiatives focused on controlling the spread of Covid-19.

Model 6: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: EPB2

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR7	0.300197	0.151280	1.984	0.0472	**

Table 33: EPB2=CSR7

Model 6 further demonstrates the impact of CSR on employees' planned behaviour. When organisations engage in different CSR campaigns, it fosters employees' corporate citizenship behaviour (Sarfo et al., 2020). Corporate citizenship behaviour encourages employees to participate in voluntary work and creates better social interactions amongst employees. Employees become more loyal and motivated to act in the best interest of their companies. As a result, employees avoid getting involved in behaviour or actions that may negatively impact their organisation's reputation. Hence, this variable focused on assessing how CSR practices encourage employees to act in the best interest of their banks. The significance (pvalue=0.0472) between the two variables (EPB2=CSR7) confirms that the ethical behaviour encouraged by CSR also influences employees to act in the best interest of their banks.

Model 7: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: EPB7

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR4	0.705922	0.201024	3.512	0.0004	***

Table 34: EPB7=CSR4

The above model 7 analysing the impact of CSR on EPB demonstrates high significance. CSR activities help employees to bring more of their whole selves, which helps them to live out their values at work. According to Drollinger (2010), people donate not with the intention of achieving the recipients' gratitude, but with the intention to earn the approval of the colleagues who partake under the philanthropic campaigns. When a company is running a CSR campaign to fight the spread of Covid-19, employees also participate in those campaigns and even donate their own money to demonstrate their commitment to the company and for the approval of their peers. Furthermore, when employees perceive that their organisation is providing benefits to society, they develop positive self-esteem as they experience an in-group identity (Mory, Wirtz and Göttel, 2017). This eventually increases employees' commitment and motivation towards the organisation, which leads them to maintain a high working standard to achieve organisational strategies. This is evident for the UK banking sector as the variables (EPB7=CSR4) indicate a significance of p-value= 0.0004.

Model 8: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: EPB2

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR4	0.829364	0.157846	5.254	<0.0001	***

Table 35: EPB2=CSR4

The final model to understand the impact of CSR on EPB is the above model 8, presented in Table 24. When employees feel a high level of satisfaction with their organisation who treats them right, they are motivated to provide support to their organisations as a mutual exchange. Additionally, CSR activities help employees to view their organisation as an ethical entity (Paul, Modi, and Patel, 2016). This, in turn, encourages employees to demonstrate more passionate behaviour in the form of organisation citizenship behaviour, as well as other positive behaviours towards customers, peers and the organisation as a whole. Employees dedicate themselves towards achieving business goals and uphold company values. The high significance (p-value=<0.0001) between the two variables (EPB2=CSR4) demonstrates that CSR activities help enhancing the working standards of the banks in the UK as CSR encourages employees to act in the best interest of their banks.

4.8.3 Impact of CSR on Employees' Retention

Model 9: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: ER4

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR7	0.699103	0.170078	4.110	<0.0001	***

Table 36: ER4=CSR7

The table above demonstrating model 9 shows the influence of CSR on the employees' retention. CSR has been identified to have significant impact on the employees' retention with a P-value <0.0001. Whilst CSR encourages employees to demonstrate ethical behaviour, if companies fail to recognise the efforts and voluntary work of their employees towards the company's CSR campaigns, it results in employee demotivation and hesitance to participate in voluntary CSR activities in the future. However, when employees' voluntary efforts are acknowledged, it not only helps in motivating and increasing employees' satisfaction, but also encourages the employees to stay with the organisation (Lee and Chen, 2018). When employees' voluntary work is praised by the company, employees are able to believe that their work is valued in the company. Having effective recognition programmes within the company positively influences employees' retention within an organisation (SHRM.org, 2022). The high significance (p-value=<0.0001) confirms that CSR encourages ethical behaviour of employees, and it is important that banks recognise the voluntary participation of the employees in CSR activities to ensure they retain these employees in the long-term (ER4=CSR7).

Model 10: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: ER4

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR4	0.595597	0.182987	3.255	0.0011	***

Table 37: ER4=CSR4

The final model, 10, under the regression analysis further understands the impact of CSR on employees' retention. The significance of p-value=0.0011 establishes that CSR activities help enhancing companies', specifically UK banks', working standards and recognising voluntary participation in CSR activities helps organisations to retain their employees (ER4=CSR4).

Voluntary participation and extra-role CSR activities create additional pressure on employees. According to Gallardo-Vázquez et al., (2020), extreme pressure on employees to volunteer in CSR activities would result in negative consequences on the organisation. Therefore, it is important to recognise employees' CSR efforts to ensure their motivation levels are maintained. Recognition can be offered through intrinsic or extrinsic rewards. Additionally, motivation can be achieved through motivation-hygiene factors, which strongly influences the retention of employees at the workplace (Chiat and Panatik, 2019). Therefore, it is crucial that UK banks recognise the voluntary CSR participation of their employees to ensure they are motivated and retained by the company in the long run.

4.9 Hypothesis Assessment

4.9.1 There is positive and significant impact of CSR on the Employees' Engagement

The first hypothesis developed for the analysis is the influence of the CSR on the employees' engagement. From the regression analysis, the P-value has been obtained to be below 0.05 in all four models of EE. It confirms the acceptance of the first hypothesis that indicates the existence of the significant influence of CSR on the employees' engagement. Furthermore, the coefficient obtained from the regression analysis indicates a increase in the employees' engagement due to the increase in the CSR and hence it confirms the positive relationship between the variables. Therefore, from the analysis, the impact of CSR on the employees' engagement has been indicated to be both significant and positive. The hypothesis has been indicated to be accepted and the finding is also aligned with the findings of the previous studies which have also identified the positive and significant influence of CSR on employees' engagement. Glavas (2016) has confirmed that CSR has the positive and significant influence on the employees' engagement. The study of Duthler and Dhanesh (2018) has also confirmed the positive and significant influence of CSR on engagement of employees.

Yadav, Singh and Reetika (2020) similarly conducted study towards examining the influence of CSR on employees' engagement. Their study has been undertaken through a qualitative approach where the primary method was employed from the perspective of CSR. The findings of their study suggested that the CSR activities of an organisations promotes the engagement of the employees where it contributes towards the development of the interpersonal skills. Similarly, Kim et al. (2018) demonstrated that a good CSR image of the company supports in

the development of a feeling of determination among the employees as the practices of CSR encourage the collaborations of both the employees and management. The study conducted by Roza (2016) further supports this present study by highlighting that the sustainability programme of CSR contributes towards high level of employee engagement from the perspective of morale and loyalty. Therefore, the programmes that are undertaken by the organisations encourage the workers and employees to cooperate with each for ensuring the effective delivering of CSR. In addition to this, the study conducted by Suganthi (2019) has illustrated that the CSR is considered to be an important aspect that creates value for both the society and employees. Moreover, Gangi et al. (2018) demonstrated that CSR is considered to have a direct proportional association with the employees' engagement as the organisations are developing policies that require both employees and management to collaborate with each other in achieving the objectives of CSR.

4.9.2 There is positive and significant influence of CSR on Employees' Planned Behaviour

The second hypothesis of the study has been developed for evaluating the influence of CSR on the employees' planned behaviour. The regression estimation of the model has confirmed the P-value lower than 0.05 in all four models of EPB which shows the significant influence between the variables. Furthermore, based on the coefficient of the regression analysis, it is obtained to be high and positive (0.7, 0.3, 0.7, 0.8). This indicates that there is an increase in the employees' planned behaviour when the organisation is engaged with the practices of CSR. Hence, it indicates the positive influence of CSR on the employees' planned behaviour. Therefore, the second hypothesis of the study has been accepted based on the regression estimation and confirms that CSR has significant and positive influence on the employees' planned behaviour. The findings that have revealed the acceptance of the hypothesis are also aligned with the previous studies as well. It is indicated from the research of Azim (2016) that the association between the CSR and the employees' planned behaviour is significant and positive. It is further also confirmed from the study of Zulfiqar et al., (2019) which has indicated positive and significant influence between the variables.

4.9.3 CSR has Positive and Significant Influence on the Employees' Retention

The third hypothesis of the study has evaluated the influence of CSR on the employees' retention. Two regression models have been used for the evaluation of the variables. It is

indicated from the analysis that the P-value of the CSR and employees' retention in both models are less than 0.05 which validates the significant influence of CSR on employees' retention. Furthermore, the coefficient of the regression has been identified to be 0.7 and 0.6 which shows that the increase in CSR tends to increase the employees' retention. Therefore, on the basis of the regression analysis, it is indicated that CSR has the positive and significant influence on the employees' retention. Hence, the hypothesis of the study has been confirmed. These findings are aligned with the other studies conducted in this domain. The study of Kim, Milliman and Lucas (2020) has also highlighted positive and significant relationship between CSR and employees' retention. Similarly, the study conducted by Shen and Benson (2016) demonstrated that CSR influences on the commitment level of the employees as CSR influences on both behaviour and attitude of the employees based on the organisational justice and citizenship behaviour. In addition to this, the study conducted by Bharadwaj and Yameen (2020) examines the influence of CSR on the retention of employees in the long run where the study also examines the organisational identification as the mediating variable. Bharadwaj and Yameen adopted the questionnaire survey which was distributed and gathered from 126 respondents. The findings of their study indicated that the employees' retention is significantly and positively impacted by CSR whereas the organisational identification is determined to have significant and mediating effect between both CSR and employees' retention. Furthermore, the study of Kim, Milliman and Lucas (2020) has also supported the acceptance of the hypothesis of this current study where it is indicated that the activities of CSR provides the feeling of prestige, salience and belonging that further influences employees' retention for the long-term. In addition to this, the social identity theory also supports the acceptance of the hypothesis where employee attitudes and citizenship behaviours are highly connected with the CSR and is also applied with the employees' retention that is determined to engender a pleasurable and positive state for the employees. Zainee and Puteh (2020) have also examined employees' retention where their study has indicated that organisations are faced with challenges and difficulty in retaining employees for the long-term. Thus, their study was conducted to evaluate the influence of CSR on employees' retention where the findings have also demonstrated that it has a positive influence for employees' retention.

4.10 Discussion by Objectives/Research Questions

4.10.1 Objective 1: To evaluate the relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and Employees' Engagement in the UK Banking sector

The first objective of this study is to evaluate the influence of corporate social responsibility on employees' engagement in the banking sector of the UK. The review of the literature has indicated that CSR tends to shape the employees' engagement towards the organisation. Therefore, the study has developed the hypothesis that there is significant and positive influence of CSR on the employees' engagement. The hypotheses were tested using statistical analysis including correlation and regression. The questionnaires were distributed among employees of the UK banking sector and the responses obtained were analysed using these statistical analysis techniques. From the correlation analysis, it was analysed that the relationship between the CSR and employees' engagement is positive and significant. Furthermore, the regression analysis indicated that CSR tends to have positive and significant impact on the employees' engagement. Therefore, it was concluded that there exists positive and significant relationship between the CSR practices of the organisation and the engagement of the employees. This is because the value for the organisation to engage in the practices of CSR especially for contributing towards the wider society and its people has increased. The employees attach much value to the organisation that thinks more about the benefit of society. Therefore, they exhibit higher engagement towards the organisation that is engaged in CSR practices.

The findings of the present study is consistent with the previous studies. The study conducted by Yadav, Singh and Reetika (2020) investigated the impact of the corporate social responsibility on the employees' engagement. Their study incorporated the qualitative primary analysis for understanding the perspective of the employee on the CSR and how it influences their work behaviour. The study has provided that the employees' interpersonal skills are improved when the organisation and employees are engaged in the activities of CSR. The study has also implied that the CSR activities involvement of the employees might lead to the higher engagement of the employees. The study conducted by Ferreira and de Oliveria (2014) has also explored the dimensions of the CSR and identified its impact on the employees' engagement. The study was conducted based on a quantitative primary research through questionnaire surveys. The questionnaire intended to identify different scenarios of CSR and how it impacted

on employees' engagement. The first scenario considered companies that only participate in CSR as a legal obligation, the second scenario considered companies that participate in external CSR while the third scenario being companies that participate in internal CSR. The findings of the study reflected that the employees' engagement tends to be affected significantly by the CSR practices. However, there has been no statistical difference between internal and external CSR impacting on the employees' engagement.

Furthermore, Gross and Holland (2011) conducted a study to explore the relationship between CSR practices and employees' engagement. The findings obtained from their research studies and surveys have been used in their study for identifying how CSR tends to impact on employees' engagement. This current research has concluded based on the previous research and the survey analysis that there is the positive and significant influence of CSR practices on the employees' engagement. Hence, it supports the findings of this study. Another study by Bapat and Upadhyay (2021) has investigated the impact of CSR practices on employees' engagement. Their study has considered the case of the Indian companies that face the mandatory requirement of engaging in CSR practices as per the Companies Act 2013. Their research also intended to identify the increase in the employees' engagement caused by the engagement in CSR practices. The researchers gathered the primary data from different HR officials, CSR officials and the employees of the 23 different organisations that belong to 10 main industries of India listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange. The main findings of the study is that the participation of the employees in CSR practices affects positively on the employees' engagement since it is identified to be increasing the four specifically recognised parameters of the employees' engagement. Hence, this also supports the findings obtained in the current study.

Kweyama (2013) investigated the impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on employees' engagement. This research has considered specifically the case of Eskom, which is a state-owned electricity utility company in South Africa. The study incorporated three different dimensions of CSR practices such as awareness, involvement, and environment and two dimensions of the employees' engagement which are job engagement and organisational engagement. The study incorporated the quantitative primary research using the data obtained from the questionnaire survey. Based on the analysis conducted in this study, it is inferred that the CSR practices tend to have positive and significant impact on the employees' engagement. Bokhari (2019) has also evaluated the relationship between corporate social responsibility and the employees' engagement in the banks of Bangladesh. The findings are also supporting the

current research findings by providing that CSR tends to have a positive and significant influence on the CSR practices. However, there are some studies that have been inconsistent and negate the findings of Bokhari's study.

Glavas (2016) also conducted a study to explore different dimensions of the impact of CSR practices on employees' engagement. The study findings have shown that the CSR practices tend to have insignificant impact on the employees' engagement. Chaudhry (2017) has further also negated the findings of this current study as it has presented that the corporate social responsibility is influencing insignificantly on the organisations' employees' engagement. However, the inconsistency in the findings are due to the different context and settings of the research. The findings of this current study have provided the scope to the organisation to get involved in the practices of CSR for motivating employees to become engaged in their job so that the performance of the organisation and its employees are enhanced significantly.

In light of the points presented above, it is considered crucial to reiterate the views of Chaudhary (2017), who claimed that the notion of corporate social responsibility has occupied major importance within the banking sector citing the amount of goodwill that is attached. There has been a significant number of practices that were regarded to be inappropriate and served the objective of undermining the core tenets of the values that the banking sector usually espouses (Besieux et al., 2018). Moreover, it is stated by Sarfraz et al. (2018) that in the modern era, there are more expectations placed on the banking sector to develop such practices that are considered to be in line with its consumer base's preferences.

Moreover, as per the views of Suganthi (2019), the notion of corporate social responsibility is found to hold the possibility of creating value not only for society in general but also for the organisation's employees in particular. These findings are found to concur with the views elucidated by Tuan (2018) who similarly claimed that the notion of corporate social responsibility is found to serve the objective of improve the level of employees' engagement that is pursued and is evident in terms of their respective behaviour. Moreover, the author describes this as a benchmark within which an employee feels engaged with the entity considering their roles and responsibilities.

In addition, as per the study conducted by Gangi et al. (2018), the workforce's engagement level is considered to share a directly proportional relationship with corporate social responsibility since they are more likely to exert more efforts in an event where they found their respective companies are more involved with facilitating with such policies that are directed towards catering to their social responsibility. Following on with the views of

Venturelli et al. (2019), it can be further stated that within the modern era, the element of corporate social responsibility is considered effective in terms of not only attracting more employees but also to reduce the turnover rate in the organisation. Based on these views, it is found to be consistent with the study conducted by Sarfraz et al. (2018) who also similarly claimed that the notion of corporate social responsibility is regarded as an effective measure in terms of levying a considerable impact on the workforce that is found to serve the objective of creating a viable impact on their respective behaviour. Such behaviour is considered to be conducive for the organisation and is also regarded to be aligned within the organisation's set goals and objectives respectively.

As per the results of Sarfraz' study it can be said that there is a significant association between CSR and employees' engagement. The study has incorporated three different dimensions of the CSR practices such as awareness, involvement, and environment and two dimensions of the employees' engagement which are job engagement and organisational engagement. It has been observed that CSR activities can encourage employees and increase the motivational level and it further causes the duties and operations to be performed in an effective manner. The past literature indicates that there is a direct correlation between organisational justice and employee perspective about CSR. Lee, Park and Lee (2013) indicate that the level of employee commitment is important to consider the impact of CSR activities on employees' engagement. Organisational commitment is linked to the sense of belonging and personal attitude towards the firm, and this causes roles and responsibilities to be segregated in an effective and efficient manner. Moreover, employees also become more motivated to accomplish the goals of their organisations by acting in the best interest of their companies.

The research study that has been proposed by Advantage (2020) has highlighted that economic and social attributes have a huge impact on environmental factors. In order to increase their branding image, companies are focusing on the implementation of CSR practices. Ethical aspects are considered because they help in maintaining good relationships in communities and among different individuals (Gilchrist, 2019). It is considered to be the essential component that is linked with corporate public relations. Similarly, it helps the leaders and the managers to motivate the employees and the workers to perform well. It also increases the skills and qualities of the employees. A research finding by Li et al., (2019) has shown that employees face many issues in competing efficiently at their workplace. In order to reduce the rate of issues, CSR plays an essential role in increasing the skills of the employees that helps in tackling such issues. Another research's findings have shown that there is a relationship

between profitability and employees' engagement profitability creates an emotional connection with the firm. Moreover, it also affects the attitude of the employees or the workers towards their clients in order to increase service levels and customers' satisfaction.

Another research study has concluded that many organisations in the UK are following such measures that help in increasing employees' engagement (Smith and Bititci, 2017). It has been observed that the feedback and assessment plans are made, especially in the business organisations and banking sectors, to record the issues that are faced by the employees and the customers. The results from the collected data have shown that these practices have helped UK-based organisations to attain prominent positions in the global marketplace. Several studies have been structured to research the issues that are faced by the employees and who are neglected by the organisations (Dundon and Rafferty, 2018). Dundon and Rafferty's data shows that organisations only pay attention to the business expenditure and the rights of the employees are neglected. As a result, companies face severe challenges. Employees' engagement is an approach that is adopted by organisations to maintain a healthy workplace environment (Al-dalameh et al., 2018). It chooses the right conditions for the employees to give them comfort and a satisfying experience Employees are encouraged on the basis of their work performances. CSR focuses on the well-being of the employees in any organisation.

During the Covid-19 pandemic, employees' attitudes and wellbeing has been compromised to a great extent (Prati, 2021). It has been a huge challenge for organisations to compete with the challenges and to maintain the workplace environment. UK based organisations have tried harder to resolve such issues by enhancing their communication skills and reducing the affairs of external factors.

In addition, a research study that has been proposed by Obeidat (2016) has studied the relationship between CSR practices and employees' engagement. The research findings that were observed on the basis of collected data have highlighted an image about the skills that are present in the management department of the UK-based banking sectors. Researchers have concluded that motivated employees are the pillars of success for an organisation (Obiekwe, 2016). Moreover, it has been stated further that commitment and dedication of employees towards the organisation are very beneficial for the organisation, whereas employees' satisfaction and interest are important for employees' performance. Another research study has aimed to evaluate the impact of CSR practices on the Islamic banking sectors (Platonova et al., 2018). It has been evaluated that banking sectors are developing by looking towards the societal benefits and community advantages. CSR helps in creating ethical standards and friendly

relations among the employees and the customers. Anagnostopoulos, 2018 revealed that the government of the UK has characterised the criteria for the banking sectors and made policies so that the legislation and rules are followed for maintaining ethical standards. In the UK, all banks should adhere to the Banking act 2009 in their operations.

Conclusively, it can be said that the research addresses the first research question, *How does corporate social responsibility influence employees' engagement in the UK banking sector?* It has been identified from the findings or results of this current research that there is a significant and positive effect of corporate social responsibility activities on employees' engagement. According to the findings of this research, the more actively the company engages in the activities of corporate social responsibility, the more engaged the employees are. In addition to this, sustainability programmes play an essential role in employees' engagement and employee satisfaction. Other than this, the value of an organisation is enhanced and increased through the practices and activities of corporate social responsibility. Moreover, it also contributes to society and its people in a positive way. Hence, it results in higher engagement towards the organisation which is engaged in corporate social responsibility practices. As per the findings of this study, the interpersonal skills of employees are improved through the activities. The research has also demonstrated that the involvement of the employees in CSR activities might lead to the higher engagement of the workers within the organisation. It has been identified in the study that a proposed CSR works as a pathway through which the workers can find true meaning because they would have a sense of contribution towards society. As a result, with the implementation of the best practices of corporate social responsibility in the organisation, the employees are more likely to engage in cooperative behaviours or attitudes towards their co-workers and the company too, therefore, it promotes high quality and close relationships among the employees.

4.10.2 Objective 2: To examine the impact of CSR on Employees' Planned Behaviour

The second objective of this study was to investigate the impact of CSR practices on the employees' planned behaviour. It has been obtained from the literature review of previous studies that corporate social responsibility practices have an important role to play on the behaviour and attitude of the organisation's employees. For addressing the objective, the study has incorporated quantitative primary research using the questionnaire survey. Furthermore, the statistical analysis has been conducted for the identification of the relationship between

CSR practices and the employees' planned behaviour. The statistical analysis used for conducting the research included the correlation analysis and regression analysis. From the correlation analysis, the researcher has concluded that CSR and employees' planned behaviour have a significant and positive relationship. Furthermore, the regression analysis has indicated that the CSR tends to have a positive and significant influence on the employees' planned behaviour. Based on the analysis, it is implied CSR tends to have an increasing level of influence on the employees' planned behaviour towards their job performance and hence organisations have to shape the positive behaviour of their employees by using the strong practices of CSR. The findings of the research are consistent with the previous studies as well which also provides that the impact of the CSR on the employees' planned behaviour is positive and significant.

In terms of the capability of CSR while also considering retention of employees', Potdar et al. (2018) infers that CSR is considered to be a viable metric that helps in gauging the legitimacy of the organisation. Since CSR is deemed to be a prerequisite for every organisation, Liu et al. (2020) suggests that it is subjected to an array of perspectives, most importantly the aspect of employee attitude and their erstwhile behaviour respectively. However, as per the views of Cheema et al. (2020), one of the aspects that is fervently probed by the organisation is the concept of organisational commitment of the employees. Within the banking context, it can be stated through the study conducted by Kong et al. (2021), who claimed that a bank's position is considered to be unique since the financial institutions are considered to operate in similar conditions however the singular goal of all the financial institutions is considered to be geared towards facilitating their consumer base as per their financial requirements.

In addition, as per the study conducted by Kumar and Das (2019), since employees are considered to be an integral part of an association based on which the sustainability of the organisation rests, it is considered crucial for the organisations to develop a better set of policies that are considered to be directed towards creating value for their employees, since the employees' commitment and morale are considered to share a directly proportional relationship with the organisation's success. It is further stated that the success and failure of an organisation is based upon its respective workforce where increase in employee turnover rate is regarded as a damage to the organisation's respective image as well as the goodwill it shares with its consumer base. Within a market share context, it can be stated that in an event where the organisation is found to be lacking in their CSR, Russell et al. (2021) states that this failure is

directly linked with the company's loss of power in its respective industry and also is susceptible to the possibility of losing their market share.

The aforementioned findings are found to concur with the views provided by Helm (2011) and Farooq et al. (2014) who similarly mentioned that for a majority of the organisations that are operating in the modern business environment, the personnel are regarded to occupy major importance since they are deemed in a position to exert their influence on their employer business' decisions albeit indirect influence. Moreover, these authors further claim that businesses can either accord success or incur loss that is solely dependent on their CSR principles. Such policies are considered to be responsible for improving the image of the organisation and thus help in the possibility of sustaining the business's image in its respective industry. On the psychological front, Raza et al. (2021) states that the policies designed by the organisation are considered to have a direct impact on the employees, evident from the fact that such policies are found to serve the objective of developing a positive perception regarding the organisation.

As identified in the literature, the planned behaviour theory has been identified and it states that the intention of an individual to practice behaviour is affected by an individual attitude towards the intentions related to behaviour. Furthermore, Ruiz et al., (2021) studied that the HR managers of UK banks have identified the attitudes of employees that has caused several aspects to be identified and has led to the overall practices of the company to be amended. HR professionals can also help organisations by acting as change agents under the change management process of their companies. CSR has the capability of determining the plans of employees and it causes new practices to be developed. It is important for the HR department to retain their talented employees as failure in doing so would cause the company and CSR to be affected in a negative manner. The role of CSR capabilities cannot be neglected while helping organisations to achieve strategic competitiveness in their industries and it causes employees' planned behaviours to be identified in an effective manner.

The research study by Kashif et al. (2018), discussed the ethical behavioural intentions of employees in the banking sector. It has been stated that employees in the business sectors are linked with multiple people and individuals. CSR practices help in improving behaviours of the employees with their customers. The findings have highlighted that citizenship behaviour among the organisations has been improved and employees' engagement has been increased. Unethical behaviours of the employees affect the organisational image (Veetikazhi et al., 2021).

It has been mentioned in research that the organisational environment can be maintained with respect to the quality management practices by the implementation of CSR strategies that can result in the employees' interest and better performances (Wikhamn, 2019). The research findings of the study by Garg et al. (2018) stated an idea that banking sectors are becoming advanced, and the IT and HR departments are using such tools and software that strengthen the connection between the organisation and the customers. CSR practices are very significant in detailing the loyalty standards and satisfaction rates among the employees by motivating and inspiring them to step ahead towards innovation (Sivapalan and Jebarajakirthy, 2017). CSR results in increasing their skills and enhancing their motivation levels to compete strongly with the competitive markets and similar organisations.

Similarly, a research study conducted by Song and Zhou (2020) has outlined the scenario of the pandemic crisis all over the world and its impact on employees' behaviour. The research findings have shown that UK-based organisations have modified their strategic plans for both the organisation and their employees by the adoption of CSR practices so that they could reduce work pressure and environmental stress. As a result, it has been found that the banking sector in the UK has shown great output in stabilising the organisational environment. Undoubtedly, the CSR planning and strategies have helped the employees to face the challenges and pandemic complications (Tan et al., 2021). It has been stated in many past researches that the international business markets and organisations around the world try to adopt technological interventions and believe in taking firm steps to deal with future complications. These plans help them in reducing political and socio-economic burdens. The research findings of the study by Wen et al. (2019) highlighted an idea that customers' perceptions and perspectives are gaining more attention by HR departments because the growth and development of any organisation depend upon the satisfaction levels of its customers. Moreover, it was noticed that customers are following the phenomenon of word of mouth. Social interactions and social statuses are playing their role in promoting any organisation and increases customers' loyalty and satisfaction simultaneously.

In addition, a research study by Khasawneh et al., (2017) has discussed the CSR practices in the banking sector in the UK and their impact on the employees' planned behaviour. The research findings have shown that organisations are moulding their strategies and policies in order to grasp the attention of the customers (Acheampong and Moyaid, 2016). Their findings highlighted another aspect; that employees' behavioural aspects are the reflection of the organisational aims. Managers and the management departments analyse the issues that are

faced by the employees so that they could be resolved on time. The research findings of another study by Agbozo et al. (2017) highlighted a scenario about job satisfaction rates among the employees in the banking sector. It has been discussed by Agbozo et al. (2017) that CSR attributes have raised the standards of the organisational environment that has ultimately affected the employees' behaviours. On the other hand, there are several research studies that have outlined the issues faced by the employees due to organisational factors. Moreover, societal attributes increase the burden and challenges on the workers that have huge potential of disturbing organisational culture and environment. Planned behaviour of the employees can be recognised or identified on the basis of certain circumstances that are faced by them (Johnstone and Lindh, 2018). They reflect their ideas through their performances and working patterns.

Finally, this work has successfully addressed the second Research question, *What role does employees' planned behaviour play in employees' participation in a company's CSR activities?* It has been identified from the findings of the research that the activities of corporate social responsibility plays an essential role in forming the planned behaviour of employees. As per the results of the study, there is a positive and significant relationship between corporate social responsibility and employees' planned behaviour. In an organisation, the workers are considered as an important resource, hence, employee engagement and employee satisfaction should be given prime consideration. The findings of this research interpret that the activities of corporate social responsibility increase the rate of employee planned behaviour along with the provision of substantial contribution to the organisation. Alternatively, in companies where there is a lack of corporate social responsibilities or the CSR activities are not considered as beneficial, then that company is more likely to experience failure. For instance, loss of market share. In addition to this, the organisation implementing the activities of corporate social responsibility greatly influences the behaviour and attitude of employees through enhancing the organisational image in the market. Moreover, corporate social responsibility influences the attachment of employees to the organisation; therefore, it affects work-related behaviours and attitudes.

4.10.3 Objective 3: To investigate how CSR influences Employees' Retention in an organisation

The third objective of the research pertained to investigating how CSR can influence towards the employees' retention in an organisation. The nature of the research was determined to be both qualitative and quantitative where the qualitative research evaluates the literature for investigating the role of CSR on the employees' retention while the quantitative perspective is emphasised towards examining the findings from the questionnaire survey to determine whether CSR influences on employees' retention. As signified from the study of Ong et al. (2018) the behavioural and attitude of the employees are highly connected with the external information of the organisation. The external information is concerned with the activities of the organisation such as whether it is taking the initiative towards the improvement of the environment along with its brand image and positioning in the market. Similarly, Lu et al. (2020) have demonstrated CSR acts as a catalyst towards the employees' behaviour and attitudes. The importance of retaining employees can be reflected to the study of Paul, Modi and Patel (2016) which states that employees are considered to be a primary asset of the organisation that has a strong perception towards the working environment. Therefore, it is critical for organisations to take initiatives towards retaining skilled and talented employees that can support their employer organisation in gaining competitive advantage along with enhancing the overall productivity and performance. In this manner, the study conducted by Sarfraz et al. (2018) has demonstrated that CSR activities have a significant and positive influence on the behaviour of employees as they influence on generating a sense of satisfaction along with fostering corporate citizen behaviour among the employees.

However, in terms of CSR influence on employees' retention, there is a lack of studies that investigate whether the activities of CSR can support organisations in retaining their employees' long term, in respect to the UK banking sector. Thus, the following research attempts to fill the research gap and contribute to the literature as to whether the activities of CSR can significantly aid organisations among the UK banking sector in retaining their employees. The objective of the research was explored through the questionnaire survey that was distributed among participants of the workforce in the UK banking sector for exploring the employee's perspective towards CSR. The data was obtained from 250 participants, incorporated in an excel file and was further tested through SPSS and GRETL for conducting the statistical analysis. Several statistical techniques were utilised, including reliability testing, correlation analysis and regression analysis. However, the most suitable technique that enabled

achievement of the objective was regression analysis. The findings from the regression analysis technique have demonstrated that CSR has a significant and positive influence on the employees' retention in the banking sector of the UK. Therefore, the results imply that the UK banks which emphasise CSR activities are able to enhance the retention level of their employees. Similarly, the study of Supriyanto (2013) has demonstrated that employees are highly concerned with the identification of the organisation in terms of values and interest. Employees are considered to be highly motivated towards accomplishing the goals of the organisations that also act for the interest of other stakeholders such as customers, community, government and others.

There is a specific belief and attitude among employees concerning the company's HRM policy. Employees' beliefs differ depending on how information is conveyed to them. Employees are constantly exposed to external information, and their behavioural and attitude responses to that information may differ (Kim 2020). In the case of workers, the firm's CSR actions demonstrate how committed the company is to the country in which it operates. People associate a firm's corporate social conduct with the assumption that if the corporation is worried about its surroundings, it must also be concerned about its employees and their needs. In the case of a firm's personnel, positive CSR initiatives result in beneficial consequences. As a result, the notion of employee CSR functions as a catalyst for employee CSR action. Furthermore, if corporations fail to acknowledge their workers' efforts or volunteer work as part of CSR initiatives, they may become demotivated to engage in such activities in the future and will have a poor view of their company (Bharadwaj 2020). The authors also claimed that applauding employees' achievements as part of CSR programmes not only improves their happiness with the company, but also drives them to remain longer. Employees believe that their labour is valued at their companies when they receive acknowledgment from their employers or management.

CSR has an influence on employee behaviour, and as a result, CSR also has an impact on the organisation's overall outcomes. The perspective of CSR is considered as a standard benchmark to guide employee actions and attitudes connected to their employment with the organisation. Employees' behaviour and attitudes are influenced by their perceptions of fairness. Corporate social responsibility may influence not just overall commitment, but also several other behaviours and attitudes of employees, such as the organisation's civic behaviour (Chatzopoulou et al., 2021).). To compete with market expectations, businesses are ensuring that employees are more engaged in corporate social responsibility activities. Furthermore,

engagement contributes to the overall position of the firm by achieving the real-time benefits of CSR. Effective CSR activities and initiatives aid in the development of a favourable image as well as corporate branding, since they influence existing employee commitment. Furthermore, it raises the company's worth in the eyes of potential workers. According to Ikram et al., (2021), in discussing the workers' attitudes and opinions of sustainable growth and CSR, three ideas were considered, namely the influence of the organisation's stakeholders on its CSR functions, CSR insights, and a CSR action plan. According to the author Ikram (2021), CSR was only utilised to address concerns of social responsibility that were tied to financial benefit. Employees are the firm's most valuable asset, and they have strong opinions about the environment in which they work and the market environment in which the company operates. Employees also generate some motivational and directed flows that must be accounted for in order they thrive. CSR initiatives have a favourable influence on employee behaviour by instilling good emotions in them. This, in turn, aids in the development of corporate citizenship among personnel. As a result of this study, it can be deduced that the greater the employees' acquaintance with CSR activities, the more motivated they will be to engage in corporate citizenship behaviours (De Silva and Lokuwaduge 2019). There are three degrees of motivation that a corporation must have in order to successfully execute CSR initiatives. The ultimate degree of ethical incentive, however, is linked to the human capital held by such businesses. As a result, the implementation of CSR initiatives inside the firm boosts employee enthusiasm. Motivation is a vital mechanism for boosting and managing output and performance, and it is a key that is required to enhance work productivity and overall performance.

When organisations implement CSR initiatives, employees have a tendency to assume that there is organisational fairness. Employee opinions of managerial justice and equality are directly influenced by CSR efforts. Employees use organisational justice as a criterion to evaluate the company's efforts (Gorgenyi-Hegyes, 2019). According to previous research, there is a direct link between organisational justice and employee perceptions of CSR. Employees' perceptions of company fairness and justice are directly influenced by CSR findings. Furthermore, past studies have found that employee viewpoint is favourably associated with organisational fairness. According to previous research, there is a direct link between organisational justice and employee perceptions of CSR. Employees' perceptions of company fairness and justice are directly influenced by CSR findings. Furthermore, past studies have found that an employee's perspective is positively related to organisational fairness as well as their degree of job satisfaction.

In addition to this, Shen and Benson (2016) argue that CSR often tends to influence on the commitment level of the employees within the organisation, as CSR is found to have influence on the behaviour and attitude of the employees in respect to organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational justice. Furthermore, the study of Malik (2015) has demonstrated that CSR activities can support the organisation in enhancing the motivation level of the employees along with generating higher commitment level. Therefore, CSR initiatives tend to have positive correlation with the financial performance of the organisation (Sinthupundaja et al., 2019). As indicated from the study conducted by Kim, Milliman and Lucas (2020), the employees' perception of CSR is reflected to the judgement of the organisation's CSR which in result influences on the employees' attitudes and behaviour. Their study has mainly assessed whether the activities of CSR influences on the employees' retention through their quality of work life. The data for their study were gathered from a questionnaire survey that was distributed among the employees of Casino Hotel Company in the USA. The findings from the research has demonstrated that CSR has significant and positive influence on the employees' intention to stay for a long period. Furthermore, the quality of life was also found to have a significant and moderating effect between CSR and intention to stay (Kim, Milliman and Lucas, 2020)

Moreover, the study conducted by Gimenes et al., (2022) has demonstrated that CSR has led to increasing the motivation of employees to be engaged in their field of work as they perceived that the organisations that tend to focus on CSR are performing well in the market. Furthermore, the research conducted by Zainee and Puteh (2020) has demonstrated that the employees' retention is identified to be highly discussed research topic in the field of human resources as it is argued that many of the business organisations are facing difficulty, challenges and struggle towards retaining their talented employees for a long period. Therefore, their research attempted to determine whether the CSR influences on the employees' retention among employees from Generation Y (Gen Y) (born between 1982-1996) in the accounting profession. The data was gathered from 377 Gen Y accounting personnel through a questionnaire survey among organisations located in Klang Valley, Malaysia. The data was analysed through correlation, descriptive and regression techniques. The findings from the study have demonstrated that CSR elements have a significant association with employees' retention. Therefore, their research implies that CSR is considered to be an important activity that contributes towards the retention of Gen Y employees in respect to finance-based organisations in Malaysia.

In respect to the study conducted by Gond et al. (2011), companies are always emphasising towards strengthening their human resources. In addition, Jamali et al. (2015) has demonstrated that employees are recognised as the most important assets and thus, it is imperative for any company to enhance the planned behaviour of the employees through making necessary activities and investments for their growth and development. Thus, HR professionals are often considered to be responsible towards guiding the behaviour of the employees for ensuring their successful execution and implementation of their responsibilities. In this respect, the research conducted by Bharadwaj and Yameen (2020) has investigated whether CSR influences on the retention of the employees for the long-run, where the study has also demonstrated organisational identification as the mediating variable. The data was particularly gathered from information technology companies in India which the questionnaire instrument was used in the collection of data. A total of 126 respondents responded to the questionnaire where the findings of the research demonstrated that the employees' retention is significantly and positively influenced by CSR while organisational identification was also determined to have significant mediating influence between CSR and employees' retention.

With respect to the results of this current research, it was determined that CSR has significant and positive influence on the employees' retention. Hence, answering the 3rd research question, *How does CSR influence employees' retention in an organisation?* The results of the study imply that the activities of CSR that are conducted by the financial institutions of the UK have positive influence on the employees' retention. Hence, this provides implications to the HR managers of the UK's financial institutions to encourage the overall management to take CSR initiatives as they can support the organisation in managing and retaining their employees. The findings of this study are in the line with the research of Kim et al. (2020) in which organisations that are emphasised on the activities of CSR are able to positively influence on the employees' retention. CSR is highly important in the current post-pandemic era as it not only influences on the welfare of the country but is also connected with the financial performance of the organisation. Furthermore, the engagement of CSR is considered to be a favourable and prestigious social attribute as it provides employees with the feeling of belongingness and pride (Paruzel, Klug and Maier, 2021). The findings of this current study are further in line with the social identity theory (SIT) which suggests that employee attitudes and citizenship behaviour are associated with CSR. Social identity theory applies with the employees' retention as it is characterised through the positive and pleasurable work experience of the employees. Thus, on the basis of the findings from the regression analysis, the third objective of the study is achieved in which CSR has significant and positive influence on employees' retention.

As per the results of this study it can be said CSR has an influence on employees' retention and CSR causes an increase in the motivation level of employees. It has further been observed that employees' retention is the most discussed research topic in the field of human resources and many of the firms are facing difficulty, challenges, and struggle towards retaining talented employees in the organisation. HR personnel are often required to guide the employees and ensure successful implementation of CSR activities and this ensures that employees of the company are being retained in an effective and efficient manner. Moreover, this causes the motivation of employees to increase, and it leads to the overall employee commitment to be enhanced. Employees are also known as the internal stakeholders of the organisation and the loss of an employee causes the company costs to be affected and increases the training costs of the firm. As identified in the literature, employees' engagement is influenced in some of the cases because organisations were laying off employees. Moreover, CSR causes motivation of employees to be affected and an increase in motivation causes the CSR activities in the company to increase in an effective manner.

4.11 Chapter Summary

This chapter consists of the findings of the statistical approaches covered in the preceding parts which are presented in this section. The data for the study was collected from 273 respondents, and after removing irrelevant and unrequired data, the study employed responses from 250 banking sector employees. This chapter explains how to understand the findings of SPSS and GRETL. It begins by describing the respondents' demographics, which include their age, gender, education, and bank designation. In addition, a frequency analysis has been supplied to elaborate on the replies to each of the questions. A correlation analysis has also been given in order to further illustrate the strength of the link between the study's variables. Principle component analysis was conducted for dimension reduction and to identify proxies to represent the variables. The impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable is also investigated using regression analysis. Lastly, a commentary is offered based on the study's objectives, highlighting the findings from past research. It reveals whether the study findings are compatible with those of past studies and whether these findings have any implications for the study. It contains a critical analysis of the conclusions derived from the data gathered in this part, as well as literature and hypotheses. It also includes a description of the hypotheses for the data set.

Chapter 5: Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Introduction

This section of the study has aimed to highlight the summary of findings that has been obtained from the collected data and the results of this research study. The previous sections have comprised the discussion on the objectives and the results that are summarised here. Moreover, it will summarise the research findings of the past literatures and connect them with the findings of this research study. It also presents recommendations as per the obtained results and findings that will help in improving future researches that are associated with a similar research topic, aims and objectives. This chapter of the dissertation has concluded all the aspects from the previous chapters with the main details and key points.

5.2 Summary of the findings

It has been discussed in a research study by Kianto et al., (2020) that organisational performances are the reflection of the efforts of the workers and the strategies that are opted by them for the development and growth of the firm. Moreover, it has been observed that the traditional organisational practices for bringing innovation and advanced organisational aspects are changing. Furthermore, it has been stated in a research study by Amrutha et al., (2020) that the human resource department is a very significant pillar for the strength of an organisation in the business markets. HR managers have to deal with the internal and external parameters that can easily impact an organisation (Thunnissen and Buttiens, 2017). Banking sectors are associated with several other organisations all over the world to increase their business growth. It has been concluded in several studies discussed in the literature that corporate social responsibilities have a great influence on the employees' engagement and practices. It has been mentioned that CSR practices engage employees by enhancing their loyalty and commitment levels (Carlini and Grace, 2021). According to the research study by Almeida et al. (2019), CSR helps in promoting closer relationships among the employees and higher quality performances. CSR proves the ethical behaviour of an organisation towards local and wider communities and societies. Management departments in the banking sector in the UK try to build good relationships with their stakeholders so that legitimate interest for the business can

be attained. The banking sector contributes a higher portion in stabilising the economic values of a state. In the light of another study, the research findings have concluded that there is a direct relationship between the employees' satisfaction and CSR practices (Tangngisalu et al., 2020). It has been stated further that CSR enhances several aspects that are related to the contentment of the employees such as sense of belonging, self-esteem, motivation and security needs etc.

In addition, another research study has concluded about the economic growth of the banking sectors in the UK (Dhingra et al., 2016). It states that employees have changed their working patterns to accomplish their goals. It has been observed that the growth and development of any organisation are based on several parameters such as collective efforts, skills, strategies, resources and good leadership. These factors have helped the organisations in planning for future complications and building good relationships in the marketplace. Corporate social responsibility has helped UK-based organisations during the pandemic (He et al., 2020) which was a global issue, and no organisation was ready to deal with it. The Covid-19 pandemic has marked the worst influence on the economic stability of the business organisations around the world. However, UK-based organisations have dealt with the economic issues resulting from Brexit and the staff had recent experience of having to deal with complications affecting their organisation. The research study conducted by Drach (2019) concluded that organisations within the banking sector of the UK are looking forward to globalisation and internationalisation so that they may get more advantages. These aims are a step towards the establishment of a more modern and advanced banking sector. On the other hand, multiple business firms could collaborate for the accomplishment of bigger social goals together rather than those done alone.

Undoubtedly, promotion and advertisement of companies are achieving more advancements by the influence of social factors. Customers are following the concept of word of mouth that works in favour of promotion and branding image (Popp and Woratschek, 2017). It was concluded by these researchers that the scenario of marketing has been changed by the customers' perceptions and needs. Customers are more interested in facilities and services rather than quantities (Strotmann et al., 2017). Marketing logistics have been changed by the adoption of technological gadgets and tools. The banking sector in the UK is well established and highly equipped so that the workers have to be trained to access new software and electronic devices (Navimipour et al., 2016). Advanced technological products have helped the employees to stay updated and to access the issues and problems of their clients in a timely

manner. Moreover, these technological products also help in maintaining connectivity among the organisational departments as well as the external world. UK based organisations are always counted in the list of modernised organisations with the best management strategies and tools. These beneficial assets have helped in raising the position of the banking sector of the UK in the global marketplace. In the light of a research study that has been proposed by Pradhan et al., (2020) the efficacy and effectiveness of CSR practices for the employees' behaviour is explained. The findings have shown that employees' weaknesses and issues are resolved to a great extent with the help of such interventions. Moreover, training and guidance helps them to perform well.

In order to develop reliable and authentic findings of this current research, cause and effect models were used that allow the researcher to examine the strength of relationship among a set of variables. The researcher has conducted categorisation of the questionnaire items which were allocated under Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Employee Engagement (EE), Employee Planned Behaviour (EPB), and Employee Retention (ER) variables. In fact, categorisation has been conducted based on the outcome expected to be achieved for that question. The Frequency analysis revealed that the banking sector employees are worried about the changes in their company's policies during the Covid-19 pandemic which has also affected their ability to participate in CSR activities and on their engagement levels.

Banks that involve in CSR activities reduce the employees' intentions to leave the organisation which is apparent through the frequency analysis. CSR leads to an increased job retention rate by positively impacting on the job satisfaction of the employees. CSR activities focused on reducing the escalation of the virus have impacted on the employees' retention rates positively. The descriptive statistics reveal that the variable CSR has the mean value of 3.34. It reflects that the average response for the questions relating to CSR is 'neutral'. On the other hand, the employee engagement has the mean value of 3.69 that shows the average response for the employee engagement questions is inclined to the response 'agree'. Similarly, the employee planned behaviour has the mean value of 3.69 that suggests the average response of questions linked to the employee planned behaviour is even towards 'agree'. Lastly, the employee retention has specified a mean value of 3.72 which too represents the average respondents as 'agreed' to the questions with regards to the employee retention

The cause-and-effect models that were used in this study include correlation and regression analysis. To develop findings, CSR's influence was tested through three sub-sets comprising employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour, and employees' retention. The impact

of CSR was checked on all these three dependent variables. In this context, the study concludes, that the relationship between CSR and employees' engagement was found to be significant in the case of the UK banking sector on the basis of $p < 0.05$.

In the case of the relationship between CSR and employees' planned behaviour, similar results are obtained. It has been found that the relationship between the two variables is positive and significant as reported by P-value ($P < 0.05$). The value of coefficient signifies that the impact of CSR is positive on employee retention in the UK banking sector. This also implies that banks in the United Kingdom can predict planned behaviour of their workers by adopting CSR practices. This also implies that employees are much more focussed towards CSR approaches being conducted by their firm. This could be due to increased awareness among employees about environmental protection and societal welfare. Lastly, in the case of relationship between CSR parties and employees' retention, the relationship is found to be positive and significant among variables. The P-value ($P < 0.005$) signifies that the strength is significant, and the value of coefficient signifies that the impact is positive. Based on these findings, the study successfully addressed the three Research questions and achieved the three research objectives.

Overall, the research study concludes that employees' engagement is positively impacted by CSR practices adopted by banks in the United Kingdom. This could be due to the reason that the awareness and concern of both internal and external stakeholders about environmental protection and benefits to society has been increased. Employees have a strong preference for firms to adopt green initiatives and they also expect their company to focus more towards green projects. The contributions made by this research are initially, it emphasises on the idea of internal CSR and identified the central mechanisms associated to it. Therefore, this research enhances the knowledge in the area of CSR primarily on internal CSR studies and offers a foundation for future studies on this issue in other countries or in other sectors. Second, this research contributes to the body of current studies regarding the impact of CSR on engagement of employees, their planned behaviour and the retention rates in the population of banking workers in the UK.

5.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that this research has found positive and significant relationship between CSR measures, and employees' engagement, employees' planned behaviour and employees' retention. These findings are also in line with the conclusions made by other researchers where they argued that in order to engage, and retain, workers appropriate CSR measures have to be taken. The previous researchers argued that with the rise of global concerns related to the environment, regulations and laws imposed by environmental protection agencies and the impact of CSR on society as a whole, highlighted by government bodies, employees are more concerned about work ethics and organisations following and undertaking CSR measures.

This study has also extended the current knowledge regarding the influence of CSR on attitude and behaviour of workers in terms of employees' retention and their planned behaviour. Eventually, it concludes that the impact of several CSR dimensions on employees' engagement could be significant and positive. Consequently, this research contributes to the knowledge related to the degree to which the financial sector, specifically in developed economies, have adopted internal CSR practices and spread knowledge associated with the influence of internal CSR practices on EE in the UK's developed economy. These findings, thus, can be helpful for developing countries also, where banks can recognise the significance of CSR in terms of engaging their workforce and improving their retention and productivity and then developing appropriate CSR policies accordingly.

This also implies that firms that offer an optimistic, healthy, and safe working conditions and environment, organisational support, job resources, and a psychologically satisfactory working climate, inspire their workforce to give their finest effort and productivity and go the extra mile to increase the effective operations of their organisations. Furthermore, workers perform in an improved way when they receive positive feedback at work, being treated with dignity, respect, opportunities to grow their careers, sufficient reward for their personal well-being and recognition for higher performance. All these aspects are related to having robust internal and external CSR measures within the banking sector and they are of vital importance for firms to enhance worker engagement and subsequently aid their firms to flourish. This is due to the point that involved workers are also more likely to view their firm as a vigorous environment and consequently more likely to retain in the firm.

From the findings, it can also be concluded that by implementing different CSR projects which improve the well-being of society, top management can upsurge the organisation's

identification of their workers, which in turn, can lead staff to experience success or failure of their employer's business as their own success or failure. This, in turn, can inspire staff to engage under those organisational citizenship behaviours that can assist their firms to accomplish their aims as demonstrating such optimistic attitudes and behaviours would reflect positively on their firms and by association, on the workers themselves.

5.4 Recommendations

With regards to the link between CSR and employees' engagement in the UK Banking Sector, it can be said that more research must be conducted in more depth (Gupta, Bhasin and Mushtaq, 2021). As for the disclosure of CSR in company annual reports, greater role of the leaders and executives will encourage both the interest of the shareholders as well as other stakeholders (Slack, Corlett and Morris, 2015). Moreover, as per the study conducted by Platonova et al. (2018), the duality of the managers effects on the disclosure of CSR. Considering an agency theoretical perspective, it recommends that influential managers may stimulate transparency with regard to the CSR activities of the banks for their reserved benefits that can even be enjoyed by the employees through strong engagement practices (Tricker, B. and Tricker, R.I., 2015). As this can mean that the influential managers are under specific pressure for appeasing the concerns of the stakeholders, they might misuse their power through the provision of a greater degree of the disclosure of CSR, it can even be a symbol of executive risk repugnance or the private prestige concerns of the managers (Shnayder, Van Rijnsoever and Hekkert, 2016).

There is no way for modern businesses to negate the significance of sustainability as the subject has been developing as a significant apprehension for all. Due to the rising concern with regards to social responsibility, particularly the accountability for the environment, it is significant to realising the human effect on the company's performance related to the environment (Ansari, Farrukh and Raza, 2021). As employees tend to spend a large quantity of their time at work, it is central for them to comprehend that their behaviour can help regarding the company's effect on the environment. With regards to the study conducted by Shahzad et al., (2021), it is definite that the probability for the effective environmental change rises when the organisations assimilate sustainability or CSR procedures into the key business functions, such as their human resource management as well as the organisational management. Moreover, with regards to the study conducted by Kao and Saari (2019), now is the time for decisively discoursing the subject of environmental sustainability with the engagement of the

workers of an organisation in a proactive way, as this is one of the feasible approaches by which a better, as well as sustainable future, can be attained.

In his article, Mirvis (2012) discussed the different approaches a company can undertake in order to enhance employees' engagement through CSR. The first approach is a '*transactional approach to CSR*' whereby CSR actions are conducted to meet the requirements and interests on the part of the workforce who are interested in partaking in the company's CSR efforts. In this approach it is crucial that the company hires and retains talented employees and undertakes CSR activities that are parallel to employee benefits. When a company and its workforce together make a cooperative effort and commitment towards CSR it is known as a '*relational approach to CSR*'. This approach is specifically useful in maintaining a social identity for the company and its employees'. The final approach identified by Mirvis (2012) is the '*developmental approach*'. In this approach the organisation aims to create value for the company and the society by motivating and developing the employees. In this approach the employees act as a coordinator between the company and the society. The following table 15 discusses the perspectives and the key considerations of enhancing employees' engagement through CSR.

<i>Engagement Model</i>			
	Transactional	Relational	Developmental
<i>Company Perspective</i>			
Strategic Intent	HR Management	Socially Responsible Culture	Socio-Commercial Innovation
Intended Impact	Improved Recruiting/Retention	+Improved Organizational Identity/Image	+Enhanced Impact on Business & Society
Positioning	Employee Benefit	Joint Obligation	Joint Opportunity
Participants	Employee Segments	All Company	Full Corporate Ecosystem
<i>Employee Perspective</i>			
Personal Motivation to Engage	Need—What I want from my job	Identity—Who I am "Whole Person"	Purpose—Who I wish to be
Benefits of Engagement	Self-Satisfaction	+Self-Expression	+Self-Development
Personal Involvement	Individual Service	Collective Service	Service+Learning
<i>Key Considerations</i>			
Downside Risks	"Substitutable"	"Total Community"	"Challenging" Employees
Strategic Space	Modest Market for Virtue; Good Enough Value Proposition	Strong Market for Virtue; Compete via Cohesion and Differentiation	Strong Market for Virtue; Compete with CSR Innovation
Stage of CSR	Engaged	Integrated	Transformative
Serving Society	Reactive	Proactive	Leading
View on People	homo economicus	homo reciprocans	homo communicans

Figure 15: Employees' engagement through CSR (Adopted from Mirvis, 2012)

Likewise, according to the study conducted by Diamantidis and Chatzoglou (2018), training along with education must pay heed to the development of knowledge with regards to the environment. This is one of the key aspects to engage the employees. Furthermore, it may be highly effective to pay heed on both the group as well as individual level. According to the research conducted by Martín et al., (2021), although the training may incur costs, it will produce an improved outcome in the long run which will counterbalance such extra cost. Correspondingly, with regards to the research conducted by Aguilera et al., (2021), the monetary as well as non-monetary rewards for the employees of the company must be comprehensive in environmental projects and other CSR activities as rewards will encourage more employees, instead of only the already stimulated minority. Moreover, the environmental responsibility must be cohesive in the central management philosophy thus, the employees comprehend that it is significant for their organisation as well as management.

With regards to the study conducted by Filho et al., (2019), the major sustainability task that the managers must be accountable for is regarding the environmental matters at the group level as well as in the individual level (Klein et al., 2019). In fact, the personal emphasis may be on the core roles like the managers, leaders in the team as well as the staff along with the key operations. Bank managers may execute strategies for engaging the employee for increasing the level of the profitability (Orlitzky, Siegel and Waldman, 2011). Moreover, the bank managers are required to determine whether the employee engagement techniques are aligned with the vision and values of the business or not. The leaders must develop as well as execute the recognised engagement strategies for an effective impact on the employee engagement as well as the organisational results.

It is important that the bank managers execute different strategies for the purpose of engaging the employee for increasing the level of the profitability. Several researches have proposed that managers tends to have a vital role in terms of bringing enhancement in the employee engagement. Moreover, the findings of the research have discovered a constructive relationship between the managerial strategies, CSR as well as employee engagement (Tsourvakas and Yfantidou, 2018). Furthermore, the leaders must develop as well as execute the recognised engagement strategies to have a constructive impact on the employee engagement as well as CSR activities. Initiatives of CSR provides employees the opportunity to express the level of interest in philanthropy such as the community service and overall sustainability. This help employees tend to feel more of themselves as well as be highly connected to the firm. The studies prove that CSR is a progressively important aspect with regards to the employee

engagement (Gao, Zhang and Huo, 2018). CSR practices eventually lead to improved performance of the job, reduced costs that may have otherwise been incurred due to employee turnover, along with enhanced productivity.

Credit and Project Finance

- Invest in global markets, take steps to prevent potential harms to the environment and the society caused by projects financed by the bank

Business Behaviour

- Code of conduct, sustainability policies

Labour Relations

- Work-life balance, effective internal communication, equal opportunities and labour standards, training and development

Community Involvement

- Philanthropic efforts such as sponsorships to young entrepreneurs, scholarships
- Support for art and culture

Accountability

- CSR disclosure, sustainability reports, CSR policy statements

Environmental Awareness

- Green investments, environment-friendly projects

Financial Inclusion

- migrant financial and banking education, microfinance

Socially Responsible Investment (SRI)

- Invest in CSR compliant businesses, anti-corruption

Partnership and Networking

- Membership in CSR organisations and bodies such as World Business Council for Sustainable Development

Economic Aspects of CSR

- Investments in innovation, poverty reduction, skills development programmes

Figure 16: CSR best practices (adopted from EBF, 2008)

A publication by the European Banking Federation (EBF) highlighted different CSR practices that banks can incorporate in their CSR policy. The publication also emphasised different advantages that CSR compliant organisations gain, such as, enhanced profitability, positive identity within the community, employee satisfaction, and in-country and international performance (EBF, 2008). Figure 16 demonstrates the key CSR practices recommended in the publication that UK banking sector can adopt.

This study discussed different internal CSR activities that encourage intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and that CSR driven motivation led to engagement of the employees. Leaders need to determine which type of motivation is most suitable for its workforce (Zhang, 2010). Some employees may consider intrinsic factor most affective in motivation whilst others may be motivated through extrinsic factors. Similarly, intrinsic motivation differs from one person to another as what gives one employee internal satisfaction is different to another employee (Tampubolon, 2016). When a company involves employees in a CSR project, one employee maybe motivated as their personal values align with the company's values, but another may expect financial or non-financial recognition. Hence, it can be finally recommended that it is vital that the management pay attention to the motivating factors of its workforce while developing policies and practices, which also needs to be reviewed frequently with changing situations, to enhance employee's engagement.

5.5 Future implications and contributions

This research was aimed at analysing the CSR practices of the banking organisations in the UK. The study has evaluated the relationship that is present between corporate social responsibility, employees' engagement, and employees' retention in the UK banking sector. In accordance with this paper, the researcher has conceptualised the relationship through the use of the quantitative data. This relationship could be examined empirically using the in-depth interviews in the future for making valid descriptions with the use of the literature review. It may help to show the predominant practices of the employees' engagement with regards to CSR. This study can be expanded with the incorporation of specific names of the UK banks. As this study is confined to the banking industry only in the UK, in the future, a comparison of CSR practices and employees' engagement in the context of other countries, for example the US, Japan, etc, could be taken into consideration. The UK is a developed country. Thus, it would be significant to incorporate into future research the comparison of the countries which

have banks in the same powerful position in the world. Additionally, a comparative analysis can be conducted between CSR activities in banks in the developing countries against banks in the developed countries to analyse how the CSR's impact differs from one country to another based on the initiatives. Moreover, future research may explore the employees' engagement practices in the context of CSR in any other industry along with dissimilar countries for obtaining a systematic understanding with regards to such relationship.

In accordance with this paper, the researcher has conceptualised the relationship through the use of the quantitative data. This relationship could be examined empirically in the future for making valid descriptions with the use of the literature review. As per the contributions to the research as well as practice, the findings along with the insights obtainable in such a dissertation can even direct the researchers to new avenues for further research. Moreover, both the contributions as well as the limitations of such a dissertation tend to create stimulating pathways for the upcoming research.

A future study could involve the conceptual explanation with regards to the barriers in terms of the employees' engagement in the context of CSR. The incorporation of the theory could even be used for conducting the empirical tests on the employees' engagement or even nonengagement in the domain of CSR. The particular background, as well as the role with regards to the values that are needed for employees' engagement, must be also considered. Correspondingly, the future study could even add the context of investors while adding information about companies.

The theoretical method can be extended through the inclusion of the measures with regards to the value correspondence for the explanation regarding why employees do or do not involve themselves in CSR. Moreover, the dissertation may further incorporate the description with regards to the types of the engagement which could be clarified through the theory of planned behaviour. Additionally, a future study could also analyse the emerging trends on how specific demographic factors such as age, gender and education level may alter the influence of CSR on employee engagement and the retention levels.

This research has made some key contributions to the body of knowledge, policy makers and professionals. Predominantly, this study contributes to the literature by evaluating the impact of corporate social responsibility on the engagement of employees' which was able to fill the gap in the literature, specifically by containing an untouched sector. This is validated by the views of Činčalová and Hedija (2020) who confirm there is a significant requirement for the academic gap to be filled within this context as there has been lack of investigation regarding

the role of corporate social responsibility within the banking sector and the ways it can contribute to an organisation's success. The research also further extends the concept of planned behaviour by incorporate the theory specifically to identify the behavioural patterns of employees. The research on CSR and employees' planned behaviour has been conducted with the purpose of filling the gap in the present literature as employees' planned behaviour is identified to be an important dimension of an organisation. The study also served the objective of developing more clarity regarding the role of corporate social responsibility on employees' engagement since the theoretical framework will incorporate certain theories that will be directed towards addressing this concern. For an example, the findings of this current study are further in line with the social identity theory (SIT) which suggests that employee attitudes and citizenship behaviour are associated with CSR. Social identity theory applies with the employees' retention as it is characterised through the positive and pleasurable work experience of the employees. By participating in external CSR activities, organisations attract a good brand image and reputation which helps the employees to develop a sense of pride for being a part of the organisation and fulfils their social-identity needs (Jia, et al., 2019). Alternatively, the impact of internal CSR on employees' engagement can also be supported by the Social Exchange Theory (SET) which suggests that employees reciprocate what they receive from the company and when the organisation offers employees' with good working conditions, fairness amongst the employees and development opportunities, then the employees will display more engagement towards their jobs and reciprocate the corporate actions through dedication and commitment towards the company and its goals (Jia, et al., 2019). Finally, the research also contributes to knowledge by confirming the relationship that exist between CSR, Employees' engagement, Employees' retention, and their planned behaviour, which further verified the findings of the previous researchers.

Furthermore, as emphasised by Agyemang and Ansong (2017), it can be stated that with deeper understanding regarding corporate social responsibility, there is a greater possibility of the banking sector designing policies that can be directed towards motivating employees and to further their engagement with the respective organisation. With the implementation of this study, it can be confirmed that with the correct execution of corporate social responsibility and its policies, business can not only enhance their employees' engagement and retention levels, but it could also help increase the potential of attracting employees' who possess the prerequisite skills required by the banking sector. As previously highlighted, the unengaged proportion of employees itself costs the UK economy £37 billion a year. The banking sector

plays a crucial role in stabilising the economic values of a country. Hence, a banking sector with effective CSR policies could lead to a decreased unengaged workforce within the UK and diminishing its effect on the economy which in turn would encourage a more stable economy. Consequently, the findings of the research could also help policy makers, managers, and professionals in other industries within UK as well as other developed countries implement effective internal and external CSR strategies that encourage employees' engagement and employees' retention. These findings, thus, can be helpful for developing countries also, where banks can recognise the significance of CSR in terms of engaging their workforce and improving their retention and productivity and then developing appropriate CSR policies accordingly.

Finally, it can also be stated that the study has made methodological contributions by incorporating multiple analysis methods to understand the relationship between the variables. The study conducted a frequency analysis, correlation analysis, principle component analysis to determine the inclusion items for each variable and also a ordinal logistic regression analysis which helped reach the conclusion that there is a positive and significant relationship between CSR and Employees' engagement, employees' retention and their planned behaviour.

5.6 Limitations

The study effectively addressed the Research Questions and was able to meet the research objectives. However, it contains some minor shortcomings in terms of external environmental effects, data sample and the generalisability of the research.

The effect of CSR for the mitigation of the impact of climate change is not explicitly discussed in this research. The research was time consuming and also, it was difficult to compress the data while keeping in mind the key variables of the study. It was problematic to engage the employees in this study as it was hard to convince them to spare their time for this research.

Moreover, the researcher faced issues in representing the clear aspects of the targeted population due to the environmental consequences. The Covid-19 outbreak has affected the lives of every individual. In order to conduct this research study and to collect the relevant data was a serious challenge due to country wide lockdowns and work from home strategies implemented by banks. Moreover, the researcher faced difficulties in convincing the participants to enrol in this study. The outcomes of the research were very limited because the data that was collected was based on the responses of the participants. Furthermore, primary

quantitative research are very time consuming and expensive that had a huge impact of completing the research in a timely manner.

Although the research was completed successfully and data were collected amongst participants representing different regions in the UK, it was not possible to gather responses from banking employees in every city within the country. Similarly, the data were collected from a limited number of banks to represent the banking sector, and there is a possibility that the responses are not generalisable to those banks that were not a part of the research. Additionally, in Likert-scale close-ended questionnaires, there is a fundamental limitation as it lacks the ability to collect in-depth and detailed data, particularly about perceptions and experiences of the research participants. This limited the ability to obtain additional information and comments from the respondents.

5.7 Summary

The Conclusion and Recommendations chapter has summarised all the primary and secondary data findings. Recommendations for the UK banking sector to close the employees' engagement gap have been discussed in this chapter. Finally, the chapter has concluded the study by highlighting the future implications of the research and the limitations of the research.

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Appendix

Questionnaire

A Critical Investigation into the Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and Employee Engagement in the UK Banking Sector

I, Fathima Ikram, am currently pursuing my Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) degree at University of the West of Scotland. The purpose of this research is to investigate and evaluate the relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Employee Engagement in the context of the UK Banking Sector. Your participation will enable the collection of data which will form a part of the study being undertaken. I recognise the value of your time, and sincerely appreciate your support. Individual responses are anonymous and all data will be held in confidence. Please take 10 minutes to complete this survey and submit it at your earliest convenience.

Demographic Questions	
1- Age	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 18-25• 26-30• 31-39

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 40 or above
<p>2- Gender</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Male • Female
<p>3- Education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High School • Bachelor's • Master's • Doctorate • Other
<p>4- Designation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manager • Assistant Manager • Executive • Officer • Trainee • Other

CSR and Employee Engagement
<p>1- Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree

2- CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

3- Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

4- CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

5- CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

Strongly disagree

6- CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a work-life balance. Strongly agree

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

7- Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

8- Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

9- Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

10- The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

Strongly disagree

11- The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

CSR and Employee Planned Behaviour

12- CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

13- The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

14- CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve work-related problems in their banking institutions.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

15- CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.

- Strongly agree

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

16- Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

17- CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

18- CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

19- The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

20- The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19.

- Strongly agree

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

21- The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

22- Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

CSR and Employee Retention

23- When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

24- The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

Strongly disagree

25- CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

- Strongly disagree

26- Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

27- CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

28- When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

29- CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.

Strongly agree

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

30- The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

****Thank you for your time****

A Critical Investigation into the Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and Employee Engagement in the UK Banking Sector

University of the West of Scotland

Project summary

The purpose of this research is to Investigate and evaluate the relationship between CSR and Employee Engagement in the context of the UK Banking Sector. Your participation will enable the collection of data which will form a part of the study being undertaken.

Why have you been asked to participate?

You have been asked to participate because you fit the profile of the population being studied; that is you are an employee in the Banking sector, in the UK.

Your participation is entirely voluntary and you may withdraw at any time.

Project risks

The research involves the completion of a questionnaire for later analysis. I am not seeking to collect any sensitive data on you; this study is only concerned with how Corporate Social Responsibility impacts your Engagement levels within your company. I do not think that there are any significant risks associated with this study. However, if you do feel that any of the questions are inappropriate then you can stop at any time. Furthermore, you can change your mind and withdraw from the study at any time – I will completely respect your decision.

How I protect your privacy

All the information you provide will be held in confidence. I have taken careful steps to make sure that you cannot be directly identified from the questionnaire form; there is no

information on this questionnaire that will identify you. Your personal details (e.g. signature on the consent form) and your questionnaire will be kept in secure locations by the researcher. When I have finished the study and analysed all the information, all the documentation used to gather the data will be destroyed.

YOU WILL BE OFFERED A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION SHEET TO KEEP

If you require any further information about this project then please contact:

Fathima Ikram

University of the West of Scotland

Email: [REDACTED]

Participant Consent Form

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

A Critical Investigation into the Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and Employee Engagement in the UK Banking Sector

University of the West of Scotland

Participant name (optional):

Name of Researcher: Fathima Ikram

Participant to complete this section: Please tick each box.

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.

3. I agree to take part in the above study.

Signature of Participant

Date

Fathima Ikram
 Name of person taking consent

Date

Ifrina
 Signature of person taking consent

Questionnaire Justifications

Question	Justification
CSR and Employee Engagement	

<p>31- Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>The respondents have been asked this question since it will help in determining their awareness of the positive impacts of CSR initiatives. In the article of Sarfraz et al. (2018) it is stated that CSR activities tend to generate a positive impact on employees' behaviour by inciting pleasant feelings in them, which in turn, foster corporate citizenship behaviour. In other words, it can be inferred that the higher the familiarity with CSR initiatives among the employees, the more encouraged they will become to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.</p>
<p>32- CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>According to Sun and Yu (2015), it was discovered that CSR activities tend to impact the performance of employees positively by encouraging them to generate better operating performance in comparison to those employees who work for less socially responsible organisations. This again is made possible by the corporate citizenship behaviour that are displayed by the employees whenever they participate in such activities (Sarfraz et al., 2018). Thus, the same positive impact of CSR activities/initiatives on banking employees' performance will also be measured by asking the stated question.</p>

<p>33- Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>Cook (2020) conducted a study to identify the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on employee engagement. The research studied various sectors such as telecomms, banking, and IT. The findings of this study noted that during COVID-19, employee engagement was highly influenced in some cases because companies were laying off their employees. However, the study also indicated that there are some companies whose CSR activities are providing awareness about combatting this pandemic situation. Therefore, this finding of Cook (2020) will be further</p>
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	<p>validated for the banking industry of the UK by asking the stated question.</p>
<p>34- CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>In the research of Al-Shuaibi (2016), the use of CSR practices was supported by the authors in the organisations studied (especially those firms that are operating in developing countries). It was concluded by the author that this is because the adoption of CSR practices by firms and multinational enterprises in developing countries can help them to enhance both their productivity and ability to innovate, which in turn, can help them to improve their financial performance. Therefore, this finding of Al-Shuaibi (2016) will be further validated for the banking industry of the UK by asking the stated question.</p>

<p>35- CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>Glavas (2016) stated that CSR activities help employees to bring more of their whole selves to work. This, as a result, enables them to improve the quality of their work since they feel more engaged with their jobs. Similarly, Murmura et al. (2017) stated that when companies engage in CSR activities, they become more encouraged to implement high-quality working standards such as SA 8000 to apply, maintain, and develop socially acceptable working practices in their organisations. Thus, in the context of the UK banking industry, the same motivations or intentions of banking organisations to raise their working standards while conducting CSR activities will be assessed by asking the stated question.</p>
<p>36- CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a work-life balance.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral 	<p>According to Kiruthigha (2015), when organisations conduct CSR activities for their employees by implementing flexible work arrangements, both the performance and commitment of the employees to their jobs are significantly increased. This is because such flexible arrangements or working policies enable employees to maintain their work-life balance appropriately. Moreover, the author has further mentioned that when organisations put employee satisfaction first by implementing flexible policies as a part of</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>their CSR initiative, they are able to reap the benefits of engaged, high performing employees that also helps the firms to improve their financial performance. Thus, this same impact of flexible policies as a part of a CSR initiative will be assessed by asking the stated question from banking employees in the UK.</p>
<p>37- Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>The outbreak of Covid-19 has impacted many industries, including the banking sector all over the world. One such impact that has been noted to occur resulting from Covid-19 is increased absenteeism rates or sick leave among employees. This also includes the impact of the preventive policies or measures associated with working from home in order to maintain social distancing (Groenewold et al., 2020). Thus, the stated question will help in determining whether the outbreak of Covid-19 has reduced the ability of the banking sector to engage in different CSR activities due to the high absenteeism rate or lack of availability of employees on bank premises.</p>

<p>38- Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>In his paper, Davenport et al. (2020) mentioned that during a pandemic most businesses are closed and those companies that remained open started to lay off their employees. The fact that people who have served the company for the past couple of years have been laid off due to the current situation, contributes to the remaining employees' loss of trust and confidence in their employer company. Hence, the employees' level of trust in the companies will be evaluated by asking the stated question of employees of the UK banking sector.</p>
<p>39- Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral 	<p>According to a research performed by Koonin (2020), some organisations started to lay off their employees as well as cut salary packages of employees who were still working in the companies. As a result, the employees lost their confidence in the companies and the companies lost the loyalty of their employees. Based on the study performed by Koonin (2020), this question</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>will evaluate the employees' level of trust and confidence and how it affects the planned behaviour of employees.</p>

<p>40- The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>This question helps to analyse the problems due to the current pandemic situation on the job market and economic development plans, the job market methodological processes and estimation. In a study performed by Choi et al. (2020), it was indicated that an adjustment has been created to the methodology and estimation of the job market and economic conditions in order to reflect the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic situation more accurately. Therefore, this question will evaluate the job market and economic conditions and how these affect the employee retention.</p>
<p>41- The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>According to a study conducted by Ramanathan et al. (2020), companies adopted several coping strategies in dealing with the negative impacts of COVID-19. The results of this research demonstrated that many companies provide resources such as laptops, online training material and other gadgets in order to train and develop their employees to work in a collaboration remotely. Therefore, the stated question will help the current study to explore the coping techniques used by the banking sector of the UK.</p>
<p>Employee Planned Behaviour and CSR</p>	

<p>42- CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>In the research of Hansen et al. (2016), it is stated that when organisations engage in different CSR activities, they are able to create and foster an ethical climate. In this regard, the authors further stated that under such ethical climates, employees often become motivated to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour. These behaviours are usually demonstrated by the employees when they are encountered with questionable moral behaviours of the higherups. Hence, the stated question will validate this finding of Hansen et al. (2016) to determine whether CSR creates an ethical climate in the banks of the UK, and motivates</p>
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	<p>employees to display upward ethical leadership.</p>
<p>43- The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>Many employees have been observed to donate money or a portion of their salaries under the CSR campaigns that have been undertaken by their companies to stop the spread of Coronavirus (Huang and Liu, 2020). Thus, the stated question will also help in determining whether banking employees are also doing the same through demonstrating corporate citizenship behaviour in the form of donating a certain percentage of their salaries to different CSR campaigns that have been created to protect people from Covid-19.</p>

<p>44- CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve workrelated problems in their banking institutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>The research of Sarfraz et al. (2018) has provided evidence that CSR activities or initiatives encourage employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour. In this regard, Cheema et al. (2020) have also stated that when employees demonstrate such behaviour, they often become motivated to take those actions within their organisations (voluntarily) even though they are not considered as a part of their contractual tasks. The author provided examples which included helping colleagues with their work and solving organisational problems by working overtime. Therefore, such behaviour that are fostered by CSR activities may also be identified among the banking employees by asking the stated question.</p>
<p>45- CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree 	<p>According to Lin and Liu (2017), when organisations utilise or implement different socially responsible practices and engage in various CSR campaigns/activities such as reducing carbon emission, participating in philanthropic activities, and so forth, the turnover intentions of employees are significantly reduced. This is because employees often feel proud while working for such companies who engage in different</p>

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<p>CSR activities, leading to increased job satisfaction and reduced turnover intentions. Thus, this impact of CSR activities on the turnover intentions of UK banking employees will be further validated by asking the stated question.</p>
<p>46- Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>Evans et al. (2020) highlights in an article that employees during this pandemic who are working from home are facing many issues and one of the primary challenges is lack of coordination and support. The study further noted many challenges including lack of support outside the physical workspace, internet connectivity, and general anxiety due to social isolation. Hence, with the relevance of the research findings of Evans et al. (2020), the author of this present research will evaluate different challenges faced by employees of the UK banking sector during the COVID-19.</p>
<p>47- CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>In their article, Sarfo et al. (2020) have argued that when organisations integrate environmental and social concerns with their business operations and interactions with key stakeholders, they are also able to increase the motivation of their employees to demonstrate high ethical behaviour. The authors stated that this is usually observed when employees become more responsible about their work and act in the best interest of their customers by avoiding unethical behaviour/actions such as giving customers</p>

	<p>false information about the products or services. Therefore the stated question will help in validating this finding associated with CSR in the banking industry of the UK.</p>
<p>48- CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree 	<p>In the article of Sarfo et al. (2020), it was also stated by the authors that when organisations engage with different CSR campaigns, which as a result foster corporate citizenship behaviour, employees become more loyal and motivated to act in the best interest of these companies. This means that employees avoid indulging in those behaviour or actions that increase the risk for the company to face backlash from customers or that negatively impact the organisation’s image. Hence the</p>
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree</p>	<p>stated question will also assess this behaviour among banking employees of the UK.</p>

<p>49- The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>After the Covid-19 outbreak, it has been observed that many companies around the world (including banking institutions) are taking different CSR initiatives in the form of running awareness campaigns for maintaining social distance and washing hands properly to avoid the spread of coronavirus disease. Other similar initiatives include giving away free face masks, hand sanitisers, and so forth (Tandon, 2020). The stated question will try to determine whether the Covid-19 outbreak has influenced corporate citizenship behaviour among banking employees to participate in similar activities to those as stated above, related to preventing the spread of this virus.</p>
<p>50- The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>According to the study performed by Robertson et al. (2020), the COVID-19 pandemic situation poses a many challenges and risks to businesses such as loss of profits and revenues, decline of market share, loss of customer demand and so on. This question will address the business challenges and risks caused by the pandemic situation specifically in the banking sector of the UK.</p>

<p>51- The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>According to the study performed by Omary et al. (2020), there are many organisations who effectively deal with the current crisis. The results indicated that they keep their business operations running smoothly by allowing their employees to work remotely (Omary et al., 2020). Hence, this question will help the author to assess the effective steps taken by different companies to deal with this crisis in the context of the Banking sector of the UK.</p>
<p>52- Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically</p>	<p>Asadi et al. (2020), reported in a research paper that companies are drastically changing their working norms due to the</p>

<p>on the company's policies and work conditions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>pandemic. Their research findings indicated that some companies are imposing strict control on the employees who are working remotely and forcing them to give straight 8hour office time to the company. However, many employees do not wish to work at a fixed time and prefer to work flexible hours while they have to work remotely. With this research, the current study will evaluate the company policies of the UK banking sector during the pandemic.</p>
<p>CSR and Employee Retention</p>	

<p>53- When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>According to Lin and Liu (2017), organisations often try to reduce the turnover intentions of their employees by engaging with different CSR activities in order to improve their image or reputation. This, as a result, also helps these organisations to decrease their employees' attrition rate more effectively than those companies who fail to engage in CSR activities. This, as a result, also helps companies to avoid unnecessary costs related to hiring replacement or new employees. In this regard, the stated question will also enable to validate this finding of Lin and Liu (2017) in the context of UK banking sector.</p>
<p>54- The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>Employees' job security is highly affected during the COVID-19 pandemic (Adhitama and Riyanto, 2020). The results of this study reported that during this pandemic situation many people lost their job and the job market is zero. Therefore, the stated question will help in validating this finding associated with job security in the banking industry of the UK.</p>
<p>55- CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral 	<p>In the article of Carlini et al. (2019) it is argued that CSR activities can help organisations to improve their brand image, which in turn, enables them to enhance their employer branding strategy. The authors have stated that this is because employees (especially those who tend to have a high level of experience and expertise) typically become attracted to organisations</p>

	that take responsibility for their actions and positively
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>contribute to the welfare of people or broader society. This, as a result, also encourages employees to stay with these organisations in the long-run. Therefore the stated question will also validate this finding to determine whether CSR helps banks to improve their employer branding, leading to employee retention in the long-run.</p>
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<p>56- Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>While describing the importance of CSR campaigns in helping the companies to become more socially responsible, Lee and Chen (2018) stated that if organisations fail to acknowledge or recognise the efforts or voluntary work of their employees under the CSR campaigns, they become demotivated to participate in such activities in future. Moreover, the authors also stated that Recognising the efforts of employees under CSR initiatives not only increases their satisfaction with the companies but also gives them more reasons to stay in the organisation in the long-run. This is because upon getting recognition or formal praise from the employers, employees are able to</p>
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	<p>perceive that their work is valued at the company. Thus, this postulation of Lee and Chen (2018) on the impact of recognition on the retention rate of the employees will also be tested through the stated question.</p>
<p>57- CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>Many studies such as Appiah (2019) have indicated a positive relationship between job satisfaction of employees and CSR activities of their companies. However, in the research of Asrar-ul-Haq et al. (2017), it was concluded by the authors that engaging in socially responsible activities and, in turn, gaining positive reception or appreciation from the customers, increase the satisfaction level of the employees with their jobs dramatically and encourages them to continue working for their organisations in the long-run. Therefore, the stated question will also validate the finding of Asrar-ul-Haq et al. (2017) under the context of the banking sector of the UK.</p>
<p>58- When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to</p>	<p>Bode et al. (2015) stated that competition to capture (or recruit) top talents away from other organisations, including the risk of job</p>

<p>significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>poaching, can be mitigated by companies when they enhance their reputation and working environment by conducting different CSR activities. This is because such activities help in increasing the loyalty and commitment of top talents to work in the organisations in the long-run, rendering the efforts of competing companies related to poaching these employees irrelevant. Therefore, this finding will be tested/validated in the context of the UK banking industry by asking the stated question.</p>
<p>59- CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>After the outbreak of coronavirus, many companies, including banking institutions, were noted to engage in different CSR activities that were based on creating awareness among people (such as related to maintaining social distancing), as well as on reducing the spread of this disease (e.g, through the distribution of free masks or hand sanitisers) (Huang and Liu, 2020). In the article of Vinerean et al. (2013), it is stated that employees feel more pride or satisfaction for working for those companies that contribute to the wellbeing of its customers and society at large. This, as a result, encourages them to stay with these companies in the long-run. Thus, the stated question will also help in determining whether or not the initiatives taken by</p>

	<p>banking institutions to protect people from Covid-19 are making employees stay with these banks in the long-run.</p>
<p>60- The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID19 era.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree 	<p>According to the study conducted by Ajisegiri (2020), when Leaders acknowledge the work of their project teams and employees during meetings, they are able to enhance employee engagement and motivation positively. Ajisegiri further found that ensuring that their employees remain engaged helped companies significantly in retaining their employees in the long run. During the current COVID-19 era, companies must understand the importance of employee retention towards employee engagement and for future long-term economic benefit. Many companies have laid off employees due to the effects of COVID-</p>
	<p>19, however, these companies need to understand that employee retention is still important even during this challenging time. Prompted by this finding of Ajisegiri's, the author of the current study intends to find out</p>

	the retention strategies practiced by the UK banking sector.
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Frequency Table

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Valid	18-25	44	17.6	17.6	17.6
	26-30	108	43.2	43.2	60.8
	31-39	60	24.0	24.0	84.8
	40 or Above	38	15.2	15.2	100.0
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Education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High School	31	12.4	12.4	12.4
	Bachelor's	78	31.2	31.2	43.6
	Master's	95	38.0	38.0	81.6
	Doctorate	14	5.6	5.6	87.2
	Other	32	12.8	12.8	100.0
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Designation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Manager	28	11.2	11.2	11.2
	Assistant Manager	24	9.6	9.6	20.8
	Executive	11	4.4	4.4	25.2
	Officer	89	35.6	35.6	60.8
	Trainee	88	35.2	35.2	96.0
	Other	10	4.0	4.0	100.0
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Bar Chart

Age Category

Gender

Education

Designation

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Case Processing Summary

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Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
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Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	3.27	1.062	250
CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	3.31	1.111	250
CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	3.48	1.084	250
CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	3.55	.931	250
CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	3.30	.946	250
CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve work-related problems in their banking institutions.	3.33	1.040	250

CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	3.37	.986	250
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Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve work-related problems in their banking institutions.	CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.
Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	1.000	.658	.540	.292	.342	.551	.492
CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	.658	1.000	.621	.227	.316	.505	.497
CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	.540	.621	1.000	.254	.390	.378	.465

CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	.292	.227	.254	1.000	.643	.216	.180
CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	.342	.316	.390	.643	1.000	.228	.237
CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve work-related problems in their banking institutions.	.551	.505	.378	.216	.228	1.000	.738
CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	.492	.497	.465	.180	.237	.738	1.000

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	20.34	18.556	.690	.529	.797

CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	20.30	18.325	.677	.553	.799
CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	20.13	18.926	.625	.472	.808
CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	20.06	21.687	.397	.424	.841
CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	20.31	20.929	.482	.472	.830
CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve work-related problems in their banking institutions.	20.28	19.295	.615	.602	.810
CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	20.24	19.623	.618	.587	.810

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
23.61	25.997	5.099	7

RELIABILITY

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Reliability

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Case Processing Summary

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Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.873	.876	7

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	3.43	1.036	250
CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a work-life balance.	3.54	.918	250
Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	3.60	.900	250

Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	3.58	.925	250
The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	3.90	.853	250
The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	3.88	.772	250
Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	3.86	.802	250

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a worklife balance.	Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.
Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	1.000	.469	.494	.509	.324	.311	.392
CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a work-life balance.	.469	1.000	.801	.729	.375	.415	.426
Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	.494	.801	1.000	.784	.396	.359	.424

Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	.509	.729	.784	1.000	.377	.362	.397
The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	.324	.375	.396	.377	1.000	.786	.665
The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	.311	.415	.359	.362	.786	1.000	.777
Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	.392	.426	.424	.397	.665	.777	1.000

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	22.36	16.473	.536	.320	.874

CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a work-life balance.	22.25	15.956	.717	.687	.846
Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	22.19	15.979	.732	.739	.844
Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	22.22	15.985	.706	.658	.848
The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	21.90	17.022	.612	.641	.860
The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	21.92	17.362	.637	.745	.858
Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	21.94	17.064	.657	.641	.855

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
25.80	22.059	4.697	7

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/STATISTICS=DESCRIPTIVE SCALE CORR

/SUMMARY=TOTAL.

Reliability

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Case Processing Summary

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a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.906	.907	8

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	3.66	.859	250
CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	3.54	.901	250
The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	3.58	.867	250

The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	3.71	.877	250
The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	3.77	.861	250
Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	3.74	.889	250
The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	3.77	.846	250
CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	3.75	.853	250

Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	1.000	.647	.676	.381	.394	.404	.425	
	Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	CSR activities help in reducing employee turnover intention

CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	.647	1.000	.641	.364	.345	.341	.327
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Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	.676	.641	1.000	.396	.444	.443	.421
The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	.381	.364	.396	1.000	.787	.684	.760
The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	.394	.345	.444	.787	1.000	.791	.749
Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	.404	.341	.443	.684	.791	1.000	.770

<p>The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.</p>	.425	.327	.421	.760	.749	.770	1.000	
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CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	.394	.367	.452	.781	.669	.680	.822
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Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	25.85	23.468	.598	.556	.903
CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	25.97	23.650	.539	.507	.909
The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	25.94	23.189	.628	.569	.900

The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	25.81	22.108	.764	.744	.888
The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	25.75	22.189	.771	.751	.888
Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	25.78	22.084	.755	.703	.889
The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	25.74	22.175	.790	.780	.886
CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	25.77	22.275	.768	.749	.888

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
29.52	29.182	5.402	8

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Reliability

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Elapsed Time

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Case Processing Summary

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a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.793	.802	8

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	3.71	.858	250
The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	3.75	.808	250
CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the longrun.	3.75	.834	250

Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	3.70	.856	250
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	3.68	.823	250
The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	3.69	.770	250
CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	3.74	.780	250
CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	3.14	1.016	250

When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	.684	.611	.647	.089	.149	.147	
The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	1.000	.735	.763	.156	.217	.236	
CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the longrun.	.611	1.000	.816	.103	.140	.178	

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	.647	.763	.816	1.000	.135	.211	.203
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	.089	.156	.103	.135	1.000	.784	.633
The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	.149	.217	.140	.211	.784	1.000	.722
CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	.147	.236	.178	.203	.633	.722	1.000
CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	.223	.190	.181	.216	.051	.073	.097

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	25.45	14.297	.568	.516	.759
The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	25.41	13.978	.676	.673	.743
CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the longrun.	25.42	14.131	.620	.703	.751
Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	25.46	13.695	.677	.738	.741

When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	25.49	15.480	.395	.626	.786
The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	25.48	15.222	.483	.707	.773
CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	25.42	15.273	.465	.543	.776
CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	26.02	15.947	.214	.062	.823

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
29.16	18.716	4.326	8

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/EXTRACTION PC

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----- FACTOR ANALYSIS -----

Factor Analysis

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Syntax

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EXTRACTION ROTATION  
  
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Resources

Processor Time

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Elapsed Time

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	Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve work-related problems in the banking institution.
Correlation	Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	1.000	.658	.540	.292	.342
	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	.658	1.000	.621	.227	.316
	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	.540	.621	1.000	.254	.390
	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	.292	.227	.254	1.000	.643
	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	.342	.316	.390	.643	1.000

CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve workrelated problems in their banking institutions.	.551	.505	.378	.216	.228	
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Correlation Matrix^a

a. Determinant = .043

	CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	.492	.497	.465	.180	.237
Sig. (1-tailed)	Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).		.000	.000	.000	.000
	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	.000		.000	.000	.000
	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	.000	.000		.000	.000
	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	.000	.000	.000		.000
	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve workrelated problems in their banking institutions.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	.000	.000	.000	.002	.000

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.771
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	774.582
	df	21
	Sig.	.000

		Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	
Anti-image Covariance	Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	.471	-.176	-.083	-.043	-.025	
	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	-.176	.447	-.178	.014	-.015	
	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	-.083	-.178	.528	.016	-.104	
	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	-.043	.014	.016	.576	-.330	

	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	-.025	-.015	-.104	-.330	.528	
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Anti-image Matrices

activ

p

	CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve workrelated problems in their banking institutions.	-.105	-.050	.054	-.034	.015
	CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	-.002	-.026	-.099	.019	-.011
Anti-image Correlation	Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	.859 ^a	-.383	-.166	-.083	-.051
	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	-.383	.830 ^a	-.367	.028	-.031
	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	-.166	-.367	.828 ^a	.029	-.196
	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	-.083	.028	.029	.650 ^a	-.599
	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	-.051	-.031	-.196	-.599	.689 ^a
	CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve workrelated problems in their banking institutions.	-.242	-.118	.117	-.070	.032

CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	-0.004	-0.059	-0.211	.038	-0.023
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a. Measures of Sampling Adequacy(MSA)

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	1.000	.660
CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	1.000	.667
CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	1.000	.561
CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	1.000	.796
CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	1.000	.813

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.561	50.865	50.865	3.561	50.865	50.865	3.092	44.178	44.178
2	1.306	18.664	69.529	1.306	18.664	69.529	1.775	25.350	69.529
3	.763	10.900	80.429						80.429
4	.483	6.906	87.334						87.334
5	.333	4.756	92.090						92.090
6	.318	4.541	96.631						96.631
7	.236	3.369	100.000						100.000
CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve workrelated problems in their banking institutions.		1.000	.681						
CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.		1.000	.689						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Total Variance Explained

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
<hr/>		

Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	.804	-.116
CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	.798	-.173
CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve workrelated problems in their banking institutions.	.752	-.340
CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	.751	-.353
CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	.749	-.023
CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	.499	.740
CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	.581	.689

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. a. 2 components extracted.

Reproduced Correlations

	Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	
Reproduced Correlation	Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	.660 ^a	.662	.605	.315	.387
	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	.662	.667 ^a	.602	.271	.345
	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	.605	.602	.561 ^a	.357	.420
	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	.315	.271	.357	.796 ^a	.800
	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	.387	.345	.420	.800	.813 ^a

s	CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve workrelated problems in their banking institutions.	.644	.659	.570	.124	.203
	CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	.645	.661	.570	.114	.193

a
c

Residual ^b	Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).		-0.004	-0.064	-0.023	-0.045
	CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	-0.004		.019	-0.043	-0.029
	CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	-0.064	.019		-0.103	-0.030
	CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	-0.023	-0.043	-0.103		-0.157
	CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	-0.045	-0.029	-0.030	-0.157	
	CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve workrelated problems in their banking institutions.	-0.092	-0.153	-0.192	.093	.025
	CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	-0.153	-0.163	-0.105	.067	.044

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. a.

Reproduced communalities

b. Residuals are computed between observed and reproduced correlations. There are 12 (57.0%) nonredundant residuals with absolute values greater than 0.05.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.	.830	.028
CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve workrelated problems in their banking institutions.	.824	.040
CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.	.789	.210
Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).	.769	.263
CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.	.677	.321
CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.	.107	.886

CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.	.204	.878
--	------	------

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Component Transformation Matrix

Component	1	2
1	.890	.456
2	-.456	.890

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

FACTOR

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/MISSING LISTWISE

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/FORMAT SORT

/PLOT EIGEN

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/EXTRACTION PC

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Factor Analysis

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	Cases Used	LISTWISE: Statistics are based on cases with no missing values for any variable used.
Syntax		FACTOR /VARIABLES EE1 EE2 EE3 EE4 EE5 EE6 EE7 /MISSING LISTWISE /ANALYSIS EE1 EE2 EE3 EE4 EE5 EE6 EE7 /PRINT INITIAL CORRELATION SIG DET KMO REPR AIC EXTRACTION ROTATION /FORMAT SORT /PLOT EIGEN /CRITERIA MINEIGEN(1) ITERATE(25) /EXTRACTION PC /CRITERIA ITERATE(25) /ROTATION VARIMAX /METHOD=CORRELATION.

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	Maximum Memory Required	7376 (7.203K) bytes

Correlation Matrix^a

		Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a work-life balance.	Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	The company provides resources and enough support to the employees helping them through this era of COVID-19.
Correlation	Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	1.000	.469	.494	.509	.324	
	CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a worklife balance.	.469	1.000	.801	.729	.375	
	Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	.494	.801	1.000	.784	.396	

	Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	.509	.729	.784	1.000	.377
	The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	.324	.375	.396	.377	1.000
	The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	.311	.415	.359	.362	.786
	Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	.392	.426	.424	.397	.665
Sig. (1-tailed)	Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.		.000	.000	.000	.000
	CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a worklife balance.	.000		.000	.000	.000

Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	.000	.000		.000	.000	
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Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Determinant = .010

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.815	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1143.152
	df	21
	Sig.	.000

Anti-image Matrices

		Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a work-life balance.	Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	
Anti-image Covariance	Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	.680	-.032	-.032	-.089	-.023	
	CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a worklife balance.	-.032	.313	-.150	-.077	.038	
	Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	-.032	-.150	.261	-.132	-.043	

	Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	-0.089	-0.077	-0.132	.342	-0.012
	The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	-0.023	.038	-0.043	-0.012	.359
	The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	.024	-0.054	.041	-0.005	-0.175
	Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	-0.080	.007	-0.034	.004	-0.031
Anti-image Correlation	Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	.934 ^a	-0.069	-0.076	-0.184	-0.046
	CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a worklife balance.	-0.069	.830 ^a	-0.525	-0.235	.113

	<p>Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.</p>	-.076	-.525	.786 ^a	-.442	-.141
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Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	-.184	-.235	-.442	.865 ^a	-.035
The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	-.046	.113	-.141	-.035	.809 ^a
The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	.057	-.190	.160	-.017	-.578
Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	-.163	.021	-.110	.012	-.086

a. Measures of Sampling Adequacy(MSA)

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	1.000	.471

CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a worklife balance.	1.000	.798
Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	1.000	.846
Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	1.000	.810
The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	1.000	.806
The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	1.000	.889
Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	1.000	.795

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.037	57.673	57.673	4.037	57.673	57.673	2.904	41.488	41.488

2	1.378	19.682	77.355	1.378	19.682	77.355	2.511	35.867
3	.627	8.957	86.312					
4	.335	4.791	91.104					
5	.267	3.810	94.913					
6	.210	3.005	97.919					
7	.146	2.081	100.000					

Total Variance Explained

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Component Matrix^a Component

1

2

Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	.812	-.432
CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a worklife balance.	.804	-.389
Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	.791	-.428
Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	.766	.457
The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	.752	.568
The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	.734	.516

Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	.643	-.240
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Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. a. 2 components extracted.

h		Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a work-life balance.	Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions
	Reproduced Correlation	Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	.471 ^a	.610	.626	.612

Reproduced Correlations

CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a worklife balance.	.610	.798 ^a	.821	.803	.390
Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	.626	.821	.846 ^a	.828	.373
Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	.612	.803	.828	.810 ^a	.360
The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	.348	.390	.373	.360	.806 ^a
The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	.347	.384	.365	.352	.846
Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	.383	.438	.424	.410	.798

Residual ^b	Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.		-0.141	-0.132	-0.103	-0.025
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CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a worklife balance.	-0.141		-0.020	-0.074	-0.015
Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	-0.132	-0.020		-0.044	.023
Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	-0.103	-0.074	-0.044		.017
The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	-0.025	-0.015	.023	.017	
The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	-0.036	.031	-0.006	.011	-0.060
Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	.009	-0.013	-0.001	-0.013	-0.133

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. a.

Reproduced communalities

b. Residuals are computed between observed and reproduced correlations. There are 7 (33.0%) nonredundant residuals with absolute values greater than 0.05.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.	.897	.203
Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.	.879	.192
CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a worklife balance.	.863	.231
Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.	.644	.238

The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.	.199	.922
The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions	.219	.870
Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour.	.282	.846

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Component Transformation Matrix

Component	1	2
1	.758	.653
2	-.653	.758

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

FACTOR

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/CRITERIA MINEIGEN(1) ITERATE(25)
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Factor Analysis

Notes

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	Cases Used	LISTWISE: Statistics are based on cases with no missing values for any variable used.

Syntax	<p>FACTOR</p> <p>/VARIABLES EPB1 EPB2 EPB3</p> <p>EPB4 EPB5 EPB6 EPB7 EPB8</p> <p>/MISSING LISTWISE</p> <p>/ANALYSIS EPB1 EPB2 EPB3</p> <p>EPB4 EPB5 EPB6 EPB7 EPB8</p> <p>/PRINT INITIAL CORRELATION</p> <p>SIG DET KMO REPR AIC</p> <p>EXTRACTION ROTATION</p> <p>/FORMAT SORT</p> <p>/PLOT EIGEN</p> <p>/CRITERIA MINEIGEN(1)</p> <p>ITERATE(25)</p> <p>/EXTRACTION PC</p> <p>/CRITERIA ITERATE(25)</p> <p>/ROTATION VARIMAX</p> <p>/METHOD=CORRELATION.</p>	
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Correlation Matrix^a

		Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	Employees worried about effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on company's policies and work conditions
Correlation	Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	1.000	.647	.676	.381	.394	
	CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	.647	1.000	.641	.364	.345	
	The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	.676	.641	1.000	.396	.444	
	The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	.381	.364	.396	1.000	.787	

	The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	.394	.345	.444	.787	1.000
	Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	.404	.341	.443	.684	.791
	The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	.425	.327	.421	.760	.749
	CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	.394	.367	.452	.781	.669
Sig. (1-tailed)	Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic		.000	.000	.000	.000
	CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	.000		.000	.000	.000

The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	.000	.000		.000	.000	
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1

The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	.000	.000	.000		.000	
The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	.000	.000	.000	.000		
Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	

a. Determinant = .002

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.859
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1516.114
	df	28
	Sig.	.000

Anti-image Matrices

E

	Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	
Anti-image Covariance	Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	.444	-.174	-.174	-.005	.008
	CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	-.174	.493	-.153	-.037	.008
	The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	-.174	-.153	.431	.034	-.039

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	The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	-.005	-.037	.034	.256	-.118
	The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	.008	.008	-.039	-.118	.249
	Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	-.006	-.004	-.022	.015	-.122
	The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	-.049	.031	.020	-.023	-.038
	CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	.028	-.017	-.052	-.104	.036
Anti-image Correlation	Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	.836 ^a	-.372	-.397	-.015	.024

CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	-0.372	.841 ^a	-0.333	-0.104	.021
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The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	-.397	-.333	.846 ^a	.104	-.121
The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	-.015	-.104	.104	.865 ^a	-.469
The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	.024	.021	-.121	-.469	.849 ^a
Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	-.016	-.010	-.063	.055	-.449
The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	-.158	.094	.066	-.098	-.162
CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	.083	-.048	-.159	-.411	.143

a. Measures of Sampling Adequacy(MSA)

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	1.000	.778
CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	1.000	.768
The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	1.000	.770
The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	1.000	.806
The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	1.000	.800

Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	1.000	.768
The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	1.000	.844
CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	1.000	.781

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Total Variance Explained

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.898	61.231	61.231	4.898	61.231	61.231	3.898	48.723	48.723
2	1.417	17.717	78.948	1.417	17.717	78.948	2.418	30.225	78.948
3	.409	5.108	84.056						84.056
4	.369	4.611	88.667						88.667
5	.330	4.122	92.789						92.789
6	.284	3.550	96.340						96.340
7	.161	2.017	98.357						98.357
8	.131	1.643	100.000						100.000

Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2

The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	.871	-.294
The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	.853	-.269
The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	.850	-.289
CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	.850	-.244
Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	.841	-.248
The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	.685	.549

Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	.656	.590
CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	.603	.636

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. a. 2 components extracted.

Reproduced Correlations

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	Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	
Reproduced Correlation	Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	.778 ^a	.771	.773	.387	.401
	CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	.771	.768 ^a	.762	.328	.343

The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	.773	.762	.770 ^a	.423	.436
The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	.387	.328	.423	.806 ^a	.802
The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	.401	.343	.436	.802	.800 ^a
Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	.405	.349	.439	.786	.784
The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards <u>stopping the spread of this disease</u> .	.398	.338	.435	.825	.821
CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	.413	.357	.448	.792	.790

Residual ^b	Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic		-0.124	-0.097	-0.006	-0.007
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CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	-0.124		-0.121	.036	.001
The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	-0.097	-0.121		-0.027	.007
The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	-0.006	.036	-0.027		-0.015
The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	-0.007	.001	.007	-0.015	
Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	-0.001	-0.008	.004	-0.102	.007
The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards <u>stopping the spread of this disease.</u>	.027	-0.011	-0.014	-0.065	-0.072

CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	-0.020	.010	.005	-.011	-.121
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Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. a.

Reproduced communalities

b. Residuals are computed between observed and reproduced correlations. There are 8 (28.0%) nonredundant residuals with absolute values greater than 0.05.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.	.892	.219
The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19	.872	.211
The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.	.864	.230

CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.	.848	.250
Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.	.843	.241
CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.	.168	.860
Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic	.237	.849
The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.	.284	.831

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation

Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a a. Rotation

converged in 3 iterations.

Component Transformation Matrix

Component	1	2
1	.844	.536
2	-.536	.844

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

FACTOR

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/MISSING LISTWISE

/ANALYSIS ER1 ER2 ER3 ER4 ER5 ER6 ER7 ER8

/PRINT INITIAL CORRELATION SIG DET KMO REPR AIC EXTRACTION ROTATION

/FORMAT SORT

/PLOT EIGEN

/CRITERIA MINEIGEN(1) ITERATE(25)

/EXTRACTION PC

/CRITERIA ITERATE(25)

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Factor Analysis

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	Cases Used	LISTWISE: Statistics are based on cases with no missing values for any variable used.

Syntax

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FACTOR
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ER5 ER6 ER7 ER8
/MISSING LISTWISE
/ANALYSIS ER1 ER2 ER3 ER4
ER5 ER6 ER7 ER8
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Resources

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Elapsed Time

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Maximum Memory Required

9264 (9.047K) bytes

Correlation Matrix^a

	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	The leadership of a company is more effective in implementing retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.
Correlation	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	1.000	.684	.611	.647	.089
	The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	.684	1.000	.735	.763	.156
	CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	.611	.735	1.000	.816	.103

	Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	.647	.763	.816	1.000	.135
	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	.089	.156	.103	.135	1.000
	The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	.149	.217	.140	.211	.784
	CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	.147	.236	.178	.203	.633
	CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	.223	.190	.181	.216	.051
Sig. (1-tailed)	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.		.000	.000	.000	.080

The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	.000		.000	.000	.007	
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CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	.000	.000		.000	.052
Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	.000	.000	.000		.016
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	.080	.007	.052	.016	
The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	.009	.000	.014	.000	.000
CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	.010	.000	.002	.001	.000
CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	.000	.001	.002	.000	.210

a. Determinant = .010

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.797
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1139.476
	df	28
	Sig.	.000

	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	The
Anti-image Covariance	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	.484	-.140	-.032	-.058	.012
	The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	-.140	.327	-.079	-.090	-.002

Anti-image Matrices

effe

rete

CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	-0.032	-0.079	.297	-.157	-.013
Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	-.058	-.090	-.157	.262	.017
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	.012	-.002	-.013	.017	.374
The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	-.011	-.005	.032	-.034	-.203
CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	.014	-.029	-.022	.015	-.065
CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	-.072	.003	.008	-.036	.003

Anti-image Correlation	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	.889 ^a	-.351	-.083	-.162	.027
	The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	-.351	.859 ^a	-.253	-.307	-.006
	CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	-.083	-.253	.805 ^a	-.564	-.039
	Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	-.162	-.307	-.564	.797 ^a	.053
	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	.027	-.006	-.039	.053	.727 ^a
	The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	-.028	-.015	.109	-.121	-.612

	CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	.031	-.074	-.059	.042	-.156
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CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	- .107	.006	.015	- .073	.005
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a. Measures of Sampling Adequacy(MSA)

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	1.000	.681
The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	1.000	.802
CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	1.000	.794
Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	1.000	.831

When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	1.000	.810
The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	1.000	.868
CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	1.000	.754
CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	1.000	.104

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.522	44.030	44.030	3.522	44.030	44.030	3.209	40.114	40.114
2	2.122	26.519	70.549	2.122	26.519	70.549	2.435	30.434	70.549
3	.930	11.622	82.171						82.171
4	.430	5.371	87.542						87.542
5	.369	4.617	92.159						92.159

6	.251	3.141	95.300						
7	.211	2.641	97.941						
8	.165	2.059	100.000						

Total Variance Explained

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	.848	-.336
The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	.843	-.301
CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	.809	-.372
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	.749	-.348

CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	.306	-.100
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	.463	.772
The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	.537	.761
CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	.530	.688

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. a. 2 components extracted.

Reproduced Correlations

	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	
Reproduced Correlation	When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	.681 ^a	.736	.735	.751	.079
	The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	.736	.802 ^a	.795	.816	.158

CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	.735	.795	.794 ^a	.811	.088
Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	.751	.816	.811	.831 ^a	.134
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	.079	.158	.088	.134	.810 ^a
The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	.137	.223	.151	.200	.836
CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	.158	.240	.173	.218	.776
CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	.264	.288	.285	.293	.064

	CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	-.010	-.003	.005	-.015	-.143
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CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	- .041	- .098	- .104	- .077	- .013
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Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. a.

Reproduced communalities

b. Residuals are computed between observed and reproduced correlations. There are 11 (39.0%) nonredundant residuals with absolute values greater than 0.05.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.	.906	.105
CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.	.889	.055
The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.	.885	.133

When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.	.824	.048
CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.	.317	.056
The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.	.113	.925
When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.	.043	.899
CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.	.142	.857

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation

Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a a. Rotation

converged in 3 iterations.

Component Transformation Matrix

Component	1	2
1	.881	.473
2	-.473	.881

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

```
FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=Age Gender Education Designation CSR1 CSR2 CSR3 CSR4 CSR5 CSR6 CSR7 EE1 EE2  
EE3 EE4 EE5 EE6 EE7 EPB1 EPB2 EPB3 EPB4 EPB5 EPB6 EPB7 EPB8 ER1 ER2 ER3 ER4 ER5 ER6 ER7 ER8 CSR EE  
EPB ER log_CSR log_EE log_EPB log_ER FAC1_1 FAC2_1 FAC3_1 FAC4_1 FAC5_1 FAC6_1  
/BARCHART FREQ  
/ORDER=ANALYSIS.
```

Frequencies

Notes

Output Created

12-MAR-2022 17:44:30

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	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	<u>N of Rows in Working Data File</u>	<u>250</u>
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data.

Syntax	<pre> FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=Age Gender Education Designation CSR1 CSR2 CSR3 CSR4 CSR5 CSR6 CSR7 EE1 EE2 EE3 EE4 EE5 EE6 EE7 EPB1 EPB2 EPB3 EPB4 EPB5 EPB6 EPB7 EPB8 ER1 ER2 ER3 ER4 ER5 ER6 ER7 ER8 CSR EE EPB ER log_CSR log_EE log_EPB log_ER FAC1_1 FAC2_1 FAC3_1 FAC4_1 FAC5_1 FAC6_1 /BARCHART FREQ /ORDER=ANALYSIS. </pre>				
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<u>Processor Time</u>	<u>00:00:36.45</u>				
<u>Elapsed Time</u>	<u>00:00:21.43</u>				

Age Category
CSR initiatives he

Gender Education Designation Responsibility (CSR). the employees.
CSR improves the in raising the work productivity of the standards of a organisation. company.

loyees in the that are taken by
banking sector are organisations
familiar with the term positively
impact the
Corporate Social job
performance of

2 N	Valid	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Frequency Table

		Age Category			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25	44	17.6	17.6	17.6
	26-30	108	43.2	43.2	60.8
	31-39	60	24.0	24.0	84.8
	40 or Above	38	15.2	15.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	178	71.2	71.2	71.2
	Female	72	28.8	28.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High School	31	12.4	12.4	12.4
	Bachelor's	78	31.2	31.2	43.6
	Master's	95	38.0	38.0	81.6
	Doctorate	14	5.6	5.6	87.2
	Other	32	12.8	12.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Designation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Manager	28	11.2	11.2	11.2
	Assistant Manager	24	9.6	9.6	20.8
	Executive	11	4.4	4.4	25.2
	Officer	89	35.6	35.6	60.8
	Trainee	88	35.2	35.2	96.0
	Other	10	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Employees in the banking sector are familiar with the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	20	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	35	14.0	14.0	22.0
	Neutral	74	29.6	29.6	51.6
	Agree	100	40.0	40.0	91.6
	Strongly Agree	21	8.4	8.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CSR initiatives/activities that are taken by organisations positively impact the job performance of the employees.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	20	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	37	14.8	14.8	22.8
	Neutral	69	27.6	27.6	50.4
	Agree	94	37.6	37.6	88.0
	Strongly Agree	30	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CSR improves the productivity of the organisation.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	19	7.6	7.6	7.6
	Disagree	22	8.8	8.8	16.4
	Neutral	65	26.0	26.0	42.4
	Agree	108	43.2	43.2	85.6
	Strongly Agree	36	14.4	14.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CSR initiatives help in raising the working standards of a company.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Disagree	27	10.8	10.8	12.8
	Neutral	78	31.2	31.2	44.0
	Agree	105	42.0	42.0	86.0
	Strongly Agree	35	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CSR activities encourage employees to demonstrate upward ethical leadership behaviour.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	3.2	3.2	3.2
	Disagree	40	16.0	16.0	19.2
	Neutral	91	36.4	36.4	55.6
	Agree	90	36.0	36.0	91.6
	Strongly Agree	21	8.4	8.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CSR activities encourage employees to actively or voluntarily solve work-related problems in their banking institutions.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	18	7.2	7.2	7.2
	Disagree	27	10.8	10.8	18.0
	Neutral	85	34.0	34.0	52.0
	Agree	94	37.6	37.6	89.6
	Strongly Agree	26	10.4	10.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CSR activities encourage employees to display ethical behaviour.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	14	5.6	5.6	5.6
	Disagree	28	11.2	11.2	16.8
	Neutral	82	32.8	32.8	49.6
	Agree	104	41.6	41.6	91.2
	Strongly Agree	22	8.8	8.8	100.0

Total	250	100.0	100.0
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Employee engagement is significantly impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	15	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Disagree	26	10.4	10.4	16.4
	Neutral	77	30.8	30.8	47.2
	Agree	100	40.0	40.0	87.2
	Strongly Agree	32	12.8	12.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CSR initiatives based on implementing flexible working arrangements and policies increase the engagement of the employees and helps them to maintain a work-life balance.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	12	4.8	4.8	4.8
	Disagree	11	4.4	4.4	9.2
	Neutral	83	33.2	33.2	42.4
	Agree	117	46.8	46.8	89.2

Strongly Agree	27	10.8	10.8	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Covid-19 outbreak and the resulting unemployment in the banking sector have reduced the ability of employees to engage in CSR activities.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	10	4.0	4.0	4.0
	Disagree	15	6.0	6.0	10.0
	Neutral	65	26.0	26.0	36.0
	Agree	134	53.6	53.6	89.6
	Strongly Agree	26	10.4	10.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Employees are losing trust on their employer companies during the COVID-19 era.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	10	4.0	4.0	4.0
	Disagree	16	6.4	6.4	10.4
	Neutral	73	29.2	29.2	39.6

Agree	121	48.4	48.4	88.0
Strongly Agree	30	12.0	12.0	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The COVID-19 pandemic is having a high impact on the job market and economic conditions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	3	1.2	1.2	1.2
	Disagree	15	6.0	6.0	7.2
	Neutral	42	16.8	16.8	24.0
	Agree	135	54.0	54.0	78.0
	Strongly Agree	55	22.0	22.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The company provides resources and enough support to the employees to help them through this era of COVID-19.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	2	.8	.8	.8
	Disagree	8	3.2	3.2	4.0

Neutral	55	22.0	22.0	26.0
Agree	138	55.2	55.2	81.2
Strongly Agree	47	18.8	18.8	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Employees' loss of confidence and trust negatively influences their planned behaviour:

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Disagree	5	2.0	2.0	4.0
	Neutral	55	22.0	22.0	26.0
	Agree	140	56.0	56.0	82.0
	Strongly Agree	45	18.0	18.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Employees are currently facing multiple challenges while working remotely during the pandemic

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	1.6	1.6	1.6
	Disagree	19	7.6	7.6	9.2

	Neutral	67	26.8	26.8	36.0
	Agree	127	50.8	50.8	86.8
	Strongly Agree	33	13.2	13.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CSR practices encourage banking sector employees to act in the best interest of their banks.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	2.4
	Disagree	24	9.6	9.6	12.0
	Neutral	76	30.4	30.4	42.4
	Agree	116	46.4	46.4	88.8
	Strongly Agree	28	11.2	11.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The outbreak of Covid-19 has increased the tendency among banking employees to demonstrate corporate citizenship behaviour.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	2.4

Disagree	16	6.4	6.4	8.8
Neutral	85	34.0	34.0	42.8
Agree	114	45.6	45.6	88.4
Strongly Agree	29	11.6	11.6	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The company's leadership effectively manages the business challenges and risks that have arisen due to COVID-19

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	2.8	2.8	2.8
	Disagree	11	4.4	4.4	7.2
	Neutral	68	27.2	27.2	34.4
	Agree	126	50.4	50.4	84.8
	Strongly Agree	38	15.2	15.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The company ensures adequate planning to engage its employees and is effectively managing this crisis.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	2.4
	Disagree	8	3.2	3.2	5.6
	Neutral	68	27.2	27.2	32.8
	Agree	124	49.6	49.6	82.4
	Strongly Agree	44	17.6	17.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Employees are worried about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic specifically on the company's policies and work conditions.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	2.8	2.8	2.8
	Disagree	9	3.6	3.6	6.4
	Neutral	71	28.4	28.4	34.8
	Agree	119	47.6	47.6	82.4
	Strongly Agree	44	17.6	17.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the behaviour of banking employees by encouraging them to donate their money towards CSR campaigns that are directed towards stopping the spread of this disease.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	2.4
	Disagree	8	3.2	3.2	5.6
	Neutral	64	25.6	25.6	31.2
	Agree	131	52.4	52.4	83.6
	Strongly Agree	41	16.4	16.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CSR activities help in reducing employees' turnover intentions.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	3.2	3.2	3.2
	Disagree	5	2.0	2.0	5.2
	Neutral	67	26.8	26.8	32.0
	Agree	132	52.8	52.8	84.8
	Strongly Agree	38	15.2	15.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, the attrition rate of their employees is dramatically reduced.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	2.4
	Disagree	13	5.2	5.2	7.6
	Neutral	63	25.2	25.2	32.8
	Agree	133	53.2	53.2	86.0
	Strongly Agree	35	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The COVID-19 pandemic affects the job security of employees.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	2.4
	Disagree	5	2.0	2.0	4.4
	Neutral	69	27.6	27.6	32.0
	Agree	135	54.0	54.0	86.0
	Strongly Agree	35	14.0	14.0	100.0

Total	250	100.0	100.0
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CSR helps organisations to enhance their employer branding strategies, leading to employee retention in the long-run.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	2.8	2.8	2.8
	Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	5.2
	Neutral	66	26.4	26.4	31.6
	Agree	135	54.0	54.0	85.6
	Strongly Agree	36	14.4	14.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Recognising voluntary participation of employees in the CSR activities can help banking organisations to retain them in the long-run.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	2.8	2.8	2.8
	Disagree	10	4.0	4.0	6.8
	Neutral	68	27.2	27.2	34.0

Agree	131	52.4	52.4	86.4
Strongly Agree	34	13.6	13.6	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

When banking organisations engage with different CSR activities, they are able to significantly reduce the risk associated with job poaching.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	2.8	2.8	2.8
	Disagree	8	3.2	3.2	6.0
	Neutral	72	28.8	28.8	34.8
	Agree	135	54.0	54.0	88.8
	Strongly Agree	28	11.2	11.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The leadership of the company is implementing effective employee retention strategies during the COVID-19 era.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	2.0	2.0	2.0

Disagree	11	4.4	4.4	6.4
Neutral	62	24.8	24.8	31.2
Agree	151	60.4	60.4	91.6
Strongly Agree	21	8.4	8.4	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CSR campaigns based on reducing the spread of Covid-19 have positively impacted employees' retention rates in financial institutions such as banks.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	1.6	1.6	1.6
	Disagree	8	3.2	3.2	4.8
	Neutral	68	27.2	27.2	32.0
	Agree	138	55.2	55.2	87.2
	Strongly Agree	32	12.8	12.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CSR activities positively impact the job satisfaction of banking employees leading to an increased retention rate.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	17	6.8	6.8	6.8
	Disagree	47	18.8	18.8	25.6
	Neutral	84	33.6	33.6	59.2
	Agree	87	34.8	34.8	94.0
	Strongly Agree	15	6.0	6.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

CORRELATIONS

/VARIABLES=CSR EE EPB ER

/PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG

/MISSING=PAIRWISE.

Correlations

Notes

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Comments		
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	Cases Used	Statistics for each pair of variables are based on all the cases with valid data for that pair.
Syntax	CORRELATIONS /VARIABLES=CSR EE EPB ER /PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG /MISSING=PAIRWISE.	
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Correlations

		CSR	EE	EPB	ER
CSR	Pearson Correlation	1	.608**	.406**	.366**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	250	250	250	250
EE	Pearson Correlation	.608**	1	.585**	.488**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	250	250	250	250
EPB	Pearson Correlation	.406**	.585**	1	.726**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	250	250	250	250
ER	Pearson Correlation	.366**	.488**	.726**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	250	250	250	250

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*GRET*L Output

Model 1: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: EE3

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR7	1.36802	0.194316	7.040	<0.0001	***
cut1	0.653622	0.615016	1.063	0.2879	
cut2	1.87057	0.612829	3.052	0.0023	***
cut3	3.94504	0.696661	5.663	<0.0001	***
cut4	7.34325	0.820579	8.949	<0.0001	***
Mean dependent var	3.604000	S.D. dependent var		0.900236	
Log-likelihood	-259.8103	Akaike criterion		529.6207	
Schwarz criterion	547.2280	Hannan-Quinn		536.7071	

Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 130 (52.0%)

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-square(1) = 158.538 [0.0000]

Model 2: Ordered Logit, using observations 1

Dependent variable: EE6

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR7	0.602349	0.161318	3.734	0.0002	***
cut1	-2.94212	0.936295	-3.142	0.0017	***
cut2	-1.27882	0.628911	-2.033	0.0420	**
cut3	0.953886	0.578407	1.649	0.0991	*
cut4	3.62888	0.663228	5.472	<0.0001	***

Mean dependent var	3.880000	S.D. dependent var	0.772000
Log-likelihood	-270.6159	Akaike criterion	551.2319
Schwarz criterion	568.8392	Hannan-Quinn	558.3183

-250

Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 139 (55.6%)

Likelihood ratio test: Chi square(1) = 86.38 [0.0000]

Model 5

Dependent variable: EPB7

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR7	0.614048	0.170157	3.609	0.0003	***
cut1	-1.79122	0.729674	-2.455	0.0141	**
cut2	-0.874632	0.643127	-1.360	0.1738	
cut3	1.27602	0.606164	2.105	0.0353	**
cut4	3.83435	0.691603	5.544	<0.0001	***

Mean dependent var 3.772000 S.D. dependent var 0.845503

Log-likelihood -285.3319 Akaike criterion 580.6639

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250
Schwarz criterion

598.2712

Hannan-Quinn

587.7503

Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 132 (52.8%)

square(1) = 86.5571
[0.0000]

Model 6: Ordered Logit, using observations 1

Dependent variable: EPB2

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR7	0.300197	0.151280	1.984	0.0472	**
cut1	-2.73364	0.651274	-4.197	<0.0001	***
cut2	-1.00364	0.547376	-1.834	0.0667	*
cut3	0.708114	0.531856	1.331	0.1831	

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

cut4	-250	3.11379	0.576168	5.404	<0.0001	***
Mean dependent var		3.544000		S.D. dependent var		0.900727
Log-likelihood		-316.6647		Akaike criterion		643.3294
Schwarz criterion		660.9367		Hannan-Quinn		650.4158

Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 114 (45.6%)

square(1) = 76.4014
[0.0000]

Model 9

Dependent variable: ER4

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>
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Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

CSR7	0.699103	0.170078	4.110	<0.0001	***
cut1	-1.39138	0.678263	-2.051	0.0402	**
cut2	-0.417041	0.613707	-0.6795	0.4968	
cut3	1.68914	0.605030	2.792	0.0052	***
cut4	4.38911	0.711424	6.169	<0.0001	***

Mean dependent var	3.700000	S.D. dependent var	0.856114
Log-likelihood	-284.6934	Akaike criterion	579.3868
Schwarz criterion	596.9941	Hannan-Quinn	586.4733

Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 132 (52.8%)

square(1) = 94.761 [0.0000]

Model 6: Ordered Logit, using observations 1

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

-250

Dependent variable: ER6

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR7	0.221637	0.146034	1.518	0.1291	
cut1	-3.16578	0.723447	-4.376	<0.0001	***
cut2	-1.95257	0.549484	-3.553	0.0004	***
cut3	-0.0467171	0.509193	-0.09175	0.9269	
cut4	3.15750	0.584427	5.403	<0.0001	***
Mean dependent var	3.688000	S.D. dependent var	0.770083		
Log-likelihood	-267.0719	Akaike criterion	544.1438		
Schwarz criterion	561.7511	Hannan-Quinn	551.2303		

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250
Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 151 (60.4%)

square(1) = 76.8131
[0.0000]

Model 3

Dependent variable: EE3

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR4	0.555645	0.181603	3.060	0.0022	***
cut1	-1.32409	0.680137	-1.947	0.0516	*
cut2	-0.314702	0.629935	-0.4996	0.6174	
cut3	1.37329	0.639666	2.147	0.0318	**
cut4	4.21535	0.722252	5.836	<0.0001	***

Mean dependent var 3.604000 S.D. dependent var 0.900236

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

	-250			
Log-likelihood	-296.6247	Akaike criterion	603.2495	
Schwarz criterion	620.8568	Hannan-Quinn	610.3359	

Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 133 (53.2%)

square(1) = 84.9088
[0.0000]

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Model 4

Dependent variable: EE6

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR4	0.437770	0.193503	2.262	0.0237	**
cut1	-3.34300	0.994308	-3.362	0.0008	***
cut2	-1.68227	0.771888	-2.179	0.0293	**
cut3	0.497370	0.699582	0.7110	0.4771	
cut4	3.07477	0.763972	4.025	<0.0001	***

Mean dependent var	3.880000	S.D. dependent var	0.772000
Log-likelihood	-276.3584	Akaike criterion	562.7169
Schwarz criterion	580.3242	Hannan-Quinn	569.8033

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250
Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 138 (55.2%)

square(1) = 74.895 [0.0000]

Model 7

Dependent variable: EPB7

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR4	0.705922	0.201024	3.512	0.0004	***
cut1	-1.39886	0.727568	-1.923	0.0545	*
cut2	-0.479960	0.713038	-0.6731	0.5009	
cut3	1.70061	0.734135	2.316	0.0205	**
cut4	4.29576	0.841314	5.106	<0.0001	***

Mean dependent var 3.772000 S.D. dependent var 0.845503

Log-likelihood -284.1309 Akaike criterion 578.2618

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250
Schwarz criterion

595.8691

Hannan-Quinn

585.3482

Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 130 (52.0%)

-square(1) = 88.9592

[0.0000]

Model 8

Dependent variable: EPB2

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR4	0.829364	0.157846	5.254	<0.0001	***
cut1	-1.06511	0.616216	-1.728	0.0839	*
cut2	0.747520	0.522730	1.430	0.1527	
cut3	2.61037	0.567667	4.598	<0.0001	***

Likelihood ratio test: Chi

: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

cut4	5.22188	0.658056	7.935	<0.0001	***
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Mean dependent var	3.544000	S.D. dependent var	0.900727
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Log-likelihood	-301.2980	Akaike criterion	612.5960
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Schwarz criterion	630.2033	Hannan-Quinn	619.6824
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Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 116 (46.4%)

square(1) = 107.135 [0.0000]

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

Model 10: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: ER4

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR4	0.595597	0.182987	3.255	0.0011	***
cut1	-1.57596	0.688158	-2.290	0.0220	**
cut2	-0.618602	0.657563	-0.9408	0.3468	
cut3	1.43752	0.663367	2.167	0.0302	**
cut4	4.07873	0.753094	5.416	<0.0001	***

Mean dependent var	3.700000	S.D. dependent var	0.856114
Log-likelihood	-289.3549	Akaike criterion	588.7099
Schwarz criterion	606.3172	Hannan-Quinn	595.7963

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 130 (52.0%)

square(1) = 85.4379 [0.0000]

Model 12: Ordered Logit, using observations 1-250

Dependent variable: ER6

QML standard errors

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
CSR4	0.00623371	0.147066	0.04239	0.9662	
cut1	-3.86973	0.663959	-5.828	<0.0001	***
cut2	-2.66062	0.586288	-4.538	<0.0001	***
cut3	-0.768668	0.537493	-1.430	0.1527	
cut4	2.41132	0.561648	4.293	<0.0001	***
Mean dependent var	3.688000	S.D. dependent var	0.770083		
Log-likelihood	-268.5136	Akaike criterion	547.0272		
Schwarz criterion	564.6345	Hannan-Quinn	554.1136		

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-

Number of cases 'correctly predicted' = 151 (60.4%)

square(1) = 73.9297 [0.0000]

Ethics Approval

04/03/2021

Dear Fathima Ifrina Mohamed Ikram,

Your application 13976: A Critical Investigation into the Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and Employee Engagement in the UK Banking Sector, submission 13427, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

(please remove your mobile phone number from your participants form).

Good luck with your research.

Dr D Turner

Likelihood ratio test: Chi-